
**EFFECTIVENESS OF TRAINING AND
DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMMES IN UK
HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY FOR
MIDLEVEL MANAGEMENT.**

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

As the researcher worked with the hospitality industry as a management level employee, the researcher has gained experience regarding training and development programmes. This has enabled the researcher to recognise benefits reaped by the organisation by providing such programmes the Hospitality industry has many training programmes. The researcher has investigated if such programmes are effective in this study. Through research, the researcher is trying to gather the data regarding what are the technologies that have been used for the current training programmes. The topic is introduced, and the rationale for research is discussed in chapter one. Furthermore, the first chapter discusses the research question, sub-questions of the research, aim and objectives of the research. This study has looked at the currently available literature in this field, to obtain a comprehensive view of the progress made in this topic so far and to identify the gaps in the current output from other researchers in this field. Further, this chapter provides a review and effectiveness of the range of training programmes available to mid-level management employees in hospitality industry in the United Kingdom. Additionally, technology use in training programmes, role of technology in training programmes and training technologies in hospitality industry has also been discussed in the same chapter. In the third chapter, research methodology, used by the researcher to conduct the study, has been presented and discussed. The methods and techniques discussed here were used to conduct the questionnaire survey of management team members with regards to the effectiveness of the training programmes for middle level employees working in the hospitality industry. 100- 150 management staff were selected randomly from the Mitchel and Butlers Company. Fourth chapter of the study deals with presenting analysis of the data collected from different sources. In the current study, the researcher used both qualitative and quantitative methods to analyse the data. Here the researcher developed different themes and used demographic characteristics of the participants. The researcher has clearly explained for readers to understand that how and what did in the research. The researcher's aim was to develop the idea of how training and development important to hospitality industry. Furthermore, the thesis was not hesitated to explain how training and development have moved forward in different way in 21st century.

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1.CHAPTER ONE: **INTRODUCTION**

Introduction:

The Introduction chapter explains about the background of the topic, significance and rational of the study, aims, objectives, research questions. these clarifications are a clear road map which will make a clear path to the researcher. furthermore, introduction provides rational for dissertation. It is very important to explain that how aim, objectives and research questions are essential things to the dissertation. Moreover, the introduction will give more theoretical understanding of the topic. The researcher has done the investigation about how Effectiveness of training programme available in UK hospitality industry for midlevel management. Aim, objectives, and research questions are done due to existing issues in the society.

The hospitality industry consists of hotels, events, casinos, cruises, amusement parks, entertainment, restaurants, clubs, cafes and more. The industry is also made up of tourism related services. According to Kale (2020) the industry is important not only for business organisations, but also for customers, employees, governments, and other such numerous stakeholders as well. The industry has been divided into four main components – food and beverages, travel and tourism, lodging, and recreation. These segments comprise the hospitality industry, as they provide different types of services to the customers with the objective of fulfilling their varied needs and demands

A hospitality unit such as a bistro, lodge, or an amusement park consists of divisions such as facility safeguarding and straight procedure. Servers, housekeepers, porters, kitchen staff, bartenders, management, marketing, and human resources, and many more are also included in this industry. The hospitality business is a multibillion-dollar industry that depends on the accessibility of leisure occasion, disposable returns, and absolute consumer fulfilment.

The food and beverage sector of the hotel generally present foodstuffs which are unique in taste. Along with every hotel tries to create food that gives healthy and rich taste to the customers. As hospitality industry is diverse and dynamic for that reason company must create foods which are obtainable by every customer who visit their hotels. Travel and tourism are also part of hospitality industry this part serve services to the customers and help them to move from one place to another. And for moving from one place to another customer needs buses, cabs, ships, trains, planes, and other transport to travel; all these comes under travel industry.

Another part of hospitality industry is lodging which means space for a time or a place to sleep for one or more nights. Modern hotels, hostels for youngsters, elder hostels, camps, motels, and other commerce that give a place for customers to sleep during the night are all within the lodging business (Waqanimaravu and Arasanmi, 2020). The lodging sector promotes its services to other markets like business, leisure, long stay, budget, and special travellers such as those working for the government, military and others. Recreation is some action that people do for have a rest, relaxation, and pleasure. The objective of recreation is to refresh a personnel body and brainpower. Any company that gives actions for relax, recreation and pleasure, to pep up a person's body and brain is in the recreation company. Entertainment businesses which offer shows such as picture or drama, attractions which are places of particular concern of visits such as zoos and museums, viewer games and participatory games are all fractions of the recreation company.

Hospitality industry generally deals into very complex and dynamic environment that simply means that employees and workers of the company always need advanced training and development sessions. And for dealing in such waste industry training is extremely essential. The industry is getting day by day more advanced filled with innovative technology; business who are operating their organization within hospitality industry need to develop and operate their business with advancement. Customers in hospitality industry have extremely wide scope they have several alternatives, so for operating business effectively and making their company leader then it must provide training to their employees.

Globally, over 200 million people are economically active due to the hospitality and tourism industries. It is one of the largest sectors worldwide and contributes to the global GDP of more than 10 percent. Despite large number of people being employed by this sector, all of them do not have monolithic roles. The variety in their roles range from being an accommodation provider or being an entertainer or a tour operator. There is plenty of scope for many people with a range of skills and abilities to be involved and make the customer experience memorable and pleasant.

High rate of growth of hospitality industry is remarkable. More than thirty three percent of services trade is contributed by this industry worldwide (United nations report, 2008).

Moreover, Anuradha (2011) describes that this industry offers a plethora of choices for people to be involved in than other traditional industries. Traditional industries have only a few limited options for multiple businesses to be involved in. She further elaborates that all businesses that are keen to take care of their customer's

leisurely needs and are intent on providing excellent customer satisfaction, can be classified under this hospitality industry. Hence, the variety and breadth offered by the hospitality industry.

Training and development are always essential for the keeping employees engaged and making them specialised in their field. More skills in their job are provide ability to complete tasks with more efficient manner. Training and development programme helps an individual to enhance their core ability and developed new skills which are essential for performing tasks. Within hospitality industry every level and divisions' workers need training. The business environment is constantly changing and for becoming frontrunner companies need to adopt several new and advanced technologies. Herein, for operating and functioning well with new technology company must provide training to their employees so that they can effectively operating function well with technology.

Businesses that are operating within the hospitality industry are providing effective training to their employees. At present they are focusing on introducing new and fresh talent within their business but for recruiting them company also provide training to them. So, this is clear that the company must provide training to all the workers whether they are fresher or older staff. In the competitive environment of hospitality industry every company is focusing on creating their company on top. And for making company on top business need high quality technology, effective human resource, and strong relationship with clients and effective management.

In UK the company in hospitality industry focus on providing 50% training to the employees. That means training is essential factor in organisation system. Training and development session increase and produced new skills that provide quality of work. Along with it also provide motivation to the workers which eventually results positive and increase their performance level as well as organisations performance as whole. From the above data, it is clear company do concern for providing training to their employees. So herein, for operating effectively and functioning with smooth consistency company need to provide training and development sessions and workshops for their employees. For giving roper training company need adequate structure and outlay.

With proper training structure company can enjoy more benefits. Along proper structure also not create havoc and burden on employee's head. If the company does not create I t properly employees think that it is an extra burden that they have to be performing with their tasks. They really do not enjoy their learning session and less concentrate while workshops. That simply reflect less engaged employees, and this will turn decline in the level of performance of employees as well as organisation as whole. Company who has effective and engaged workforce that business definitely achieve success; on the other hand, if company does not effective employees that company does not achieve their desirable position within the market.

Staff training and development is generally beneficial to any industry and any organisation. In this study, the researcher focusses on the effectiveness and impact of such training programmes aimed at mid-level management staff in UK hospitality industry. Providing training and development facilities to employees working at middle levels can be beneficial for the company. This is mainly due to the reason that training the employees will give the management confidence about abilities and skills of the employees. Furthermore, this will also boost employee morale and productivity, thereby enhancing overall performance of the organisation. In addition, well-trained employees can also ensure that needs and demands of employees are fulfilled to the greatest possible extent.

In recent years the process of training and development for employees has changed significantly. Today, technology plays a crucial role in the way training is provided to the employees, regardless of their position or experience. Earlier trainings were carried out using traditional means such as workbooks, but with technological advancements and developments this has changed significantly. Furthermore, technology is also being considered as one of the key factors that tend to have a significant impact on the process of training and development of employees in an organisation (Patiar et. al, 2021).

The training programs which are being used by the organisations for providing training to the employees depends on the several factors. In the context of hospitality industry several types of traditional training methods are being used for providing training to the employees such as on job training, lectures, cases, role playing, job instructions and many more. But the technological development had shifted the learning towards e-learning and this is being used by the organisations for providing training to

the employees. Using technologies for the training helps the hospitality industry to trainee the employees in an effective manner and developing the skills and knowledge of the employees.

The organisations are using different technologies for providing training such as videos, computer-based instructions, online training programs, web-based training and interactive video training and many more. Although it is expensive to use the technologies but once there are being established in the organisation then it provides several benefits as it reduces the cost of organising the training sessions, cutting the cost of transportation, fees of tutor and cost of meals and the cost of other resources as it. Hence, it can be said that using technologies in the training provides several benefits to the organisations so the companies should focus on using better technologies in the training and development programs.

1.0 Researcher Background and the relevance of this topic

Training and development are important for every organisation operating in diverse industries. Effective training is important for the employees as it helps them in developing their skills and enhancing their knowledge which is important for delivering high quality performance in the organisation. Training helps the employees in working on their weakness and using their strengths to the fullest so that they can deliver better services in the firm. It is important for the organisation to focus on the training and development of the employees as it is having significant impact on several other things.

Employee performance is one of the highly affected factors which is directly linked with the training provided to the employees for delivering better performance in the organisation. It is important for the organisations to develop different kinds of training programs for the employees of the organisation based on the diverse departments in which they are working and on the basis of their job roles. Performance of the employee is also depended on the level of their job satisfaction.

Satisfying the employees with their job roles should be the core responsibility of the organisation as it is having an impact on the employee performance. If the company is organising effective training programs for the employee which are providing positive outcomes and are improving the skills of the employees, then it will lead to job satisfaction which will lead to better performance of the employee in the organisation. It is not an easy task for the companies to develop a training program as it requires a lot of resources and it needs to be successful in developing the skills of the employees. The firms need to focus on all the factors which are having an impact on the training and development of the employees in the organisation. Training is specifically important for the new hired employees as it is important for the company to fill the skill gap among the employee's skills and the skills required for the specific job role.

If we discuss training and development of employees in the context of hospitality industry, then it becomes more significant. Hospitality industry is a customer driven industry and the satisfaction level of the customer play a major role in the success of the organisation. Development of skills and knowledge of employee working in hospitality industry is essentials as it is having an impact on the way in which the employee interact with the customers and quality of the service which is being delivered to the customers. Quality of the service delivered to the customer is directly having an impact on the brand value and reputation of the organisation and due to this the

organisations providing hospitality service needs to pay more focus on training and development of their employees.

Large number of employees are working in a hospitality service providing organisations in the diverse departments. In this industry all the different departments are important as they are delivering a diverse service to the customers. Employees working in all the diverse departments such as front office, food and beverage, housekeeping and others needs to have specific skillset based on the department in which they are working and, on the service, they are delivering to the customers. Organisations operating in this industry needs to organised effective training programs which can help the employees in developing their skills.

Hospitality service providing organisations operating in UK focuses on the training and development of their employees. Diverse range of training programs are being conducted for the employees by the organisations. If the organisations just hire the employees without providing them better training regarding their roles and responsibilities and for the development of skills which is important for delivering better quality work to the organisation. It is very important for the organisations to understand the importance of training and development of employees and its impact on the productivity and job satisfaction of the employees. Along with this the companies needs to understand that how training is having an impact on the overall performance of the organisation and its success. If better training is provided to the employees and they are delivering high quality work to the organisation and satisfying the customers with their services, then it will led the company towards success.

I have obtained a Baccalaureate degree majoring in Economics. Subsequently, I was interested in higher education and successfully achieved my Master's in Business Administration. Further to my higher education, I chose to pursue my career in the hospitality industry and have obtained considerable experience. During my work, I had recognised the "importance of training in the hospitality industry". Worldwide, the United Kingdom hospitality industry has prestigious recognition.

Further, at my work I realised that the organisation benefits greatly by providing adequate training to improve the skills of the staff members. It further improves their productivity and job satisfaction as well. This is in alignment with the findings by Bell et al. (2003). Despite the significance of training the staff adequately, I found that my organisation and several other organisations where my friends worked were forced to hire staff without any training as filling the staff vacancy was better than having none

to perform certain duties that are required by the challenging environment in the hospitality industry. This seems to be the common challenge faced by organisations across the globe in this industry. It is very dynamic and fast paced and the businesses must make use to the available talent and train them where they lack certain skills (Christina Pomoni ,2009).

It is imperative for the human resources department to develop the staff skills and keep them up to date. Christina Pomoni (2009) has correctly identified the need for human resources department to keep abreast of the changes that are happening globally with different aspects of the business functionalities and the interaction between these functions can alter the entire business process. Hence, I think that it is important to understand how the current students who are aspiring to enter this industry are feeling about their career prospects, on job training available with the organisations, skills that they could develop and achieve their career goals and ambitions. This will help them to obtain job satisfaction and which in turn will help the organisation by keeping the staff attrition low. Hence, I have attempted to research this topic.

With the ongoing changes in the world, technology is playing a major role in every department and in all the industries. In the context of the training which is being provided to the employees the companies need to focus on using better technologies which can help them in providing effective training to the employees. Human resource department of the company should focus on organising proper and effective training and development programs for the employees. Technological advancement is providing better opportunities for the organisations to make better use of the technologies for providing effective training to the employees. Incorporating the technologies in the learning environment will provide several benefits to the organisation and it will prepare the workforce for the upcoming technological advancements as well.

The organisations operating in the hospitality industry are using the existing methods for providing the training to the employees, but they should look forwards towards using latest technologies which can help them in providing the training in an easy and effective manner. The development of the technologies in the hospitality industry had made it possible for the company to enhance the effectiveness of the training and learning among the employees. Using the latest technologies for providing the training is not easy for the organisations as it is quite costly. On the other hand, introducing the technologies such as e-learning for training the employees provide several benefits due to which it is beneficial for the companies to use technologies for providing training to the employees.

Nature of the current study is exploratory. This means that the study focuses on exploring the cited research topic in order to determine new aspects about the subject matter and enhance its overall value as well. This study is based on the existing literature available in the public domain. Since all representatives need preparing and advancement regardless industry they are in, other enterprises' experiences might offer new viewpoints to the inn business (Jones and Wynn, 2019). One more requirement in this paper is the term preparing to envelop both preparing and advancement. Preparing is the exercises that are intended to give staff the information and abilities required for their current positions while improvement is the discovering that goes past the present work and has an all the more long haul centre.

Although training and development normally go connected at the hip, they vary all things considered everything staff can do preparing, though their bosses or supervisors as a rule attempt improvement (Haugen and Tønnessen, 2019). Preparing additionally will in general be more explicit while advancement takes a gander at the drawn-out proficient objectives. The coach will show explicit abilities and information to the learner to acquire explicit objectives for their current position. During the advancement cycle, staff will meet with their administrator as well as supervisor to talk about their qualities and shortcomings, and how to further develop work exhibitions to help extend and expand their present vocation way.

Researcher is focusing on the effectiveness of training programmes available in UK hospitality industry for midlevel management. Researchers focus on how the technology has impacted on training programmes for management level staff in hospitality. Researcher finding the training programmes which are available and past 10 years how that training tools and development programmes changed how does that effected to their development.

Effective training and development can be defined as the process of providing such training and development opportunities to the employees, so that they can perform their tasks and duties in the most effective manner possible. Further, effective training enables the employees in understanding their roles and responsibilities better and ensure that the firms' goals and targets are fulfilled.

1.1 Significance of the Study

Training and development are an important factor for the organisation and the firms needs to focus on this topic. These training programs are having a huge impact on the company as it is related with the productivity of the organisation. When the company designs the training programs for the employee then they need to focus on the gaining maximum benefit from the training programs and these programs should successfully develop the skills and knowledge of the employees.

For the hospitality industry the training provided to the employees is more important as it is having an impact on the work which is being delivered by the employees in the organisation. It is important topic for the organisation to have proper knowledge regarding the significance of the training and development of the employees. In this research study the researcher is focusing on the analysing that does the technologies leading the organisations towards developing effective training programmes for the employees. This research is specifically focusing on the hospitality industry of UK and the development of mid-level hospitality staff. Limited literature is present on this topic, so it is important to focus on this research topic for providing better understanding to the organisations regarding using technologies in the training and development programs.

1.2 Rationale of the study

In hospitality industry, the use of technology for providing training programmes has not been evaluated. Hence, there is a need to measure the quantitative and qualitative effectiveness of technology to provide such training programmes successfully and measure how it helps the development of staff to their fullest potential. In this research, researcher assessed the flow preparing programs through the meetings and optional information, just as specialist is hoping to accumulate the data concerning what are the current preparing programs. This examination will first and foremost foster a writing audit on the connected regions, friendliness industry, innovation, preparing projects to foster cordiality staff abilities. Subsequently, researcher provides models to assess the effectiveness of such training programmes.

To obtain a comprehensive view quantitative and qualitative data is obtained and it further establishes the characteristics of research questions that are relevant in this area of study. The purpose of this study is to measure and identify the relationship between variables to understand how the mid-level management staff in UK hospitality

industry find the technology aspects to be relevant and useful for their development programmes.

A reasonable and result oriented data collection strategy is by utilising primary and secondary data collection strategies and eventually using modern research validating methods the exact relationship between use of technology and the results obtained by mid-level hospitality staff due to such training programmes. The research will be declared in a mathematical representation where the management and related stakeholders will gain a comprehensive view of the research results obtained from this study. The resultant outcomes will be bringing the recommendations to enhance the effective training programmes through use of technology.

1.3 Research question

Does the use of technology lead to the design of more effective training programmes in UK for the development of mid-level hospitality staff?

1.4 Sub Research Questions

1. Currently, what are the training programmes available in UK for the development of mid-level hospitality staff?
2. How effective are the current training programmes for mid-level of employees in UK hospitality industry?
3. How can technology be incorporated into the training programmes in hospitality industry?
4. How can technology improve the efficacy of such training programmes?

1.5 Research aim

To evaluate the effectiveness of training programmes available in UK hospitality industry for midlevel management staff members and derive recommendations about how technology can be incorporated to enhance such training programmes.

1.6 Research objectives

- Evaluate the current training programmes available in UK hospitality industry for midlevel management staff members
- Assess the effectiveness of training programmes available in UK hospitality industry for midlevel management staff members
- To explore how technology can be incorporated into providing training programmes for UK hospitality industry staff
- To find out if the use of technology improves the efficacy of such training programmes in developing the mid-level staff potential.

1.7 Hypothesis

Hypothesis is also known as testable prediction which researcher can apply as test. The researcher can propose the answers through assessing number predictions. There are some hypotheses applied to the research.

1. Training and development positively associate with Mitchells and Butler.
2. Mitchells and Butlers always develop training programmes that help the development of mid-level staff members.
3. Technology always could improve and contribute training programmes for id level of employees in Mitchells and butlers.

The end of the chapter 01, researcher has explained about the background of the research, aim, objectives and research questions clearly. it shows why hospitality industry needs effective training programmes and technology to enhance hospitality

industry in the United Kingdom. As well as clearly defined how researcher tended to build the hypothesis through Mitchells and Butler. Moreover, researcher has tried to explain how Mitchell and Butlers useful to enhance effective training development and the technology in the hospital industry.

The chapter 02 is about Literature Review which is an overview of the previous submit work on related topic.

02. CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE
REVIEW

Introduction

The literature review is one of the main academic requirements to fulfil the research. Because researcher has to find out other research information and statistics to fulfil its research requirements. The researcher has thoroughly researched about relevant research topics from variety sources such as websites, articles, books and many more.

2.0 Training and development

As Rodgers meaning of the preparation is the correct method to do what to accomplish a thin objective (Rodgers 1986). Lloyd and Leslie clarify the comparable thought regarding preparing is a course of realizing, which has got ideas, rules, and guidelines, gained sets of abilities to expand the exhibitions of representatives in an action or set of exercises (Lloyd and Leslie 1997). Preparing and advancement help to individuals further develop them - self and perform well on their exercises. Association needs to comprehend about the spaces that should be improved and what are the abilities should be improved. As indicated by Van Wart preparing is both the cycle and the intend to distinguish and foster required abilities in various and circumstances (Van Wart et al. 1983).

Through trainings individuals can change their mentalities and their conduct. Armstrong has unmistakably clarified about preparing is the altering of individual conduct through learning and encounters (Armstrong 1999). McClelland says preparing is an action to change individuals' conduct (McClelland 2002, 7). Through preparing individuals can work on their abilities and information as per the work job and in regard to works. As indicated by Edwin B Flippo preparing is a demonstration to build the information and abilities on determined work. Preparing and representative's exhibitions have direct relationship. Through schooling, guidelines, improvement, and encounters are officially changes representative's conduct (Michael Armstrong, 2000). Preparing showed the most common way of changing and working on representative's mentalities and conduct to perform well on their work job and work (Chetty, 2016). Chris clarifies about the preparation and advancement intend to be specialized turn of events, human and administrative turn of events and self-awareness for individual and hierarchical development (Chris 1996). Motivation behind preparing and advancement is to foster the abilities and gaining the information box trainings (Isyaku 2000).

Rosner contends that preparation isn't the answer for execution in certain circumstances, as preparing experts might suspect preparing could be a misuse of cash and assets and occasionally it very well may be a wise venture (Rosner, 1999 referred to by Smith and Mazin, 2004). Some preparation comes up short, as it needs more destinations to centre and give guidance to the workers. As Mullins said absence of the board develop and support are significant motivations to come up short on trainings (Mullins, 2007). Ambardar A (2013) Training is observed to be one of the main human assets rehearses in any industry. The execution of these practices in legitimate way chooses the general presentation of any association (Cohen, 2017).

Different authors had defined the training in diverse ways such as:

"Training is the systematic modification of behaviour through learning which occurs as a result of education, instruction, development and planned experience" (Armstrong 1999)

"A planned process to modify attitude, knowledge or skill behaviour through learning experience to achieve effective performance in an activity or range of activities. Its purpose, on the work situation, is to develop the abilities of the individual and to satisfy the current and future manpower needs of the organisation". (UK Manpower services commission, 1981)

Armstrong expresses that the basic point of preparing is to assist associations with accomplishing their motivation by adding to their secret weapons for example individuals they utilize (Maity, 2019). Putting resources into preparing implies that workers will need to perform better and engage themselves to utilize their innate capacities (Guchait et. al, 2016). Preparing and advancement are procedures for moving to representatives' important abilities, information, and skill to work on representatives' exhibition in current positions and future task (Bakotic, 2013).

Needs of training and development programmes

Globalization, need of administration, increased worth put on theoretical resources and human resources, Focus on connection to business methodology, Customer's administrations and quality accentuation, New innovation, High exhibitions model at work framework, Economic changes, Attracting and holding ability are the necessities of coming down programs (Hajjar and Alkhanaizi, 2018). Breaking down the training needs is a key to redesign and reshape the advancement programs in all

industries and needs of preparing can recognize the hole between what are the abilities worker ought to need to do on their task job and what are the abilities representative really needs to finish their task job (Jain and Gautam, 2014). As indicated by Breiter and woods needs of preparing is an appraisal of the recognizable proof of hole between ideal exhibitions and real exhibitions (Breiter& Woods, 1997, p 88).

If the important of training is discussed in the context of the hospitality industry, then it became more significant topic of concern for the organisations (Kafui et al, 2016). With the increasing globalisation across the world, it has become essential for the organisations to provide training to the employees so that they can develop the skills and knowledge which is important to fit appropriately in the job role and description (Rodriguez and Walters, 2017). In the context of the hospitality industry the employee belonging to diverse socio-economic backgrounds are working together in the industry and along with this they are offering services to the customers belonging to diverse socio-economic backgrounds (Kang et. al, 2016). When the employees are working in such an industry then it is training become more important for them so that they can deliver better- and high-quality service to the peoples belonging to different parts of the world (Ling et. al, 2017). Globalisation had led the training and development to be more important for the hospitality sector and needs to be effective so that the employees can be trained in a better way (Luong, 2015).

Better training programs are essential as it will help the organisation in developing the workforce as per the aims and objectives of the organisation (Malik et. al, 2017). If the hospitality service providing firm is focusing on delivering better service, then they need to have a workforce which can successfully deliver better services to the customers which is the main aim of the company (Maxwell, 2012). Also developing the skills is important for the employees which enables them to have a better future and being a better employee for the company (Adekiya and Ibrahim, 2016). While designing the training programs for the employees the company should try to align it with the organisational strategy which helps them in developing better and effective training and development programs (Mills et al, 2014).

Effective training programs for the development of skills and knowledge of the employees working in the hospitality in also necessary as it is having a significant impact on the customer satisfaction (Munzhedi, 2016). The organisations need to

emphasise on the quality of the service which is being delivered to the employees. Whenever the employees interact with the customers then are required to deliver better performance as it is having an impact on the satisfaction level of the customers (Anyanwu et. al, 2016). If the customer is satisfied with the quality of the service which is being offered to him then it will provide several benefits to the company (Montargot and Lahouel, 2018).

Training programs are also having an impact on the employee retention and job satisfaction of the employees (Oshins, 2017). The organisations need to understand that if they are providing better training to the employees then it will help the employees in working effectively and delivering better service in the organisation. If the employees are delivering better performance in the organisation, then it in having positive impact on the job satisfaction of the employees and helps the company in employee retention (Osmani and Maliqi, 2012). If the talented employees are leaving the company, then it became difficult for the organisation to regularly hire new employees and it also has an negative impact on the organisational performance (Pramjeeth et al, 2017).

Technological development had also increased the demand of effective training in the hospitality industry (Ranggadara and Sahara, 2017). Latest technologies are being used by the hospitality service providing organisation due to which it has become important for the organisations to trainee the employees so that they can also use the technologies for delivering better service to the customers (Rodriguez and Walters, 2017). For using latest technologies such as big data and information from the social media platforms it is essential to have proper knowledge so that the employees can develop their skillset for improving the quality of the service which is provided to the customers (Ryan, 2018).

With the changing world, training is becoming more important day by day (Clarke and Higgs, 2016). All the employees already working in the organisation and the new hired employees both needs to develop the skills effective and continuously focus on developing the skills and should have a learning attitude towards new concepts (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012). The organisation should organise the training programs for all the employees of the organisation in a particular time which can help them in better developing and also promote improvement in the overall performance and productivity of the organisation. It can be said that it is essential for the organisations to understand the importance of training and development (Shrafat et al, 2018).

Training Needs Assessment (TNA)

Need Assessment or necessities examination; is the technique for deriving and tending to representative expertise shortfalls through current or arranged training and expert advancement programs, just as deciding the kinds of training and development programs required and which parts of training and development ought to be focused on (Sonnenschein, 2020). Needs evaluation likewise is utilized to distinguish the gap(s) between ideal execution and genuine execution (Breiter& Woods, 1997, p 88). Training Needs Analysis (TNA) is the way to reshaping the eventual fate of Continuing Professional Development (CPD) being customized in all enterprises and instructive organizations it is a fundamental part of training software engineers (Spencer and McLaren, 2017).

It is a pivotal part of learning for finding out both the requirements of the students and the association and as such it gives a key connection applicable and compelling educating and learning measures (Suharnomo et. al, 2017). It decides and recognizes the hole between what is expected of an individual to play out their obligations ably and what they really know as a reason for starting restorative measures or potentially medicinal training (Ting et. al, 2019). Training Needs Analysis can be a staggering cycle. It is a strategy for overcoming any issues between the necessary exhibition and the genuine presentation. It is additionally a strategy for figuring out what abilities are required, and assuming this is the case, what preparing is needed to fill the space (Vembar and Amritharaj, 2014). The substance of TNA is to find the overall spaces of work and medical care where improvement is fundamental and that require CPD. It centres around recognizing the requirements of representatives, fostering a reasoning for a preparation program, distinguishing required information sources, deciding system content, and laying out program objectives (Verevka, 2019).

To make Continuing Professional Education programmes more effective, TNA is required prior to designing and conducting any training or workshops and to analyse the organization's needs and employee performance (Vnouckova, 2016). It is essential that the needs of an organisation are known before any training programmes are integrated. Without that clarification, training will do little but waste time, effort, and resources. A training programme must be carefully tailored on needs analysis (Wheeler et. al, 2017).

Benefits of training and development

Bratton and Gold have distinguished the significance of preparing as a base for the executives (Bratton and Gold, 2003). Benefits of the training and development are increment representative occupation fulfilment, inspire for compelling and productivity on worker's work job, it increments reception limit with regards to new innovations and new work procedures and techniques. Then again training and development lesson representative turn over and hazard the board (Imran and Tanveer, 2015). As per Wilkinson trainings permits to embrace to changes in business climate and it is utilizing as a device to change the hierarchical culture (Wilkinson et al. 2006).

Training and development assists with working on the effectiveness of human asset which can assists with further developing their accomplishments separately just as authoritatively (Benson, 2006). Group joint effort blossom with training and advancement. Associations can take powerful choices and deals with serious consequences regarding issues when they have all around prepared staff individuals. Uncommonly the training and development assists with fostering the authority abilities, mentalities, self-inspiration, and best group ever (Armstrong, 2008) (Bratton and Gold, 2003) (Pont, 2003) (Price, 2007).

Effectiveness of training and development

As per Echard and Berge (2008) successful training strategies can give brilliant client assistance, advancement on creations, and acquiring new abilities. Huang clarifies that the knowledgeable and all-around prepared labour force is critical to the business' upper hand in worldwide economy Echard and Berge, (2008). Have successful training and development programs in associations can get a good deal on trainings. Studies are all the more exorbitant, yet successful training projects can set aside more cash, which have squandered on modest and inaccurate training programs (Ginsberg, 1997).

As Mohamed E Ibrahim clarifies training adequacy estimating by how the learners respond on preparing projects and abilities and information, they are overcoming training Mohamed E Ibrahim (2004).

Following the traditional approach in determining the effectiveness of a training program an accurate estimate is made of the total benefits found after training and this compared to previous performance levels (Khan, 2016). In this way a link is made between the individual effect of training to the organisation's Profit and Loss account (Yap and Ineson, 2016).

It may be possible, with certain categories of training that the performance of employees regarding fixed operational tasks can be measured prior to and then post training through different approaches (Yusliza et. al, 2019). Although it is possible to measure improvements in organizational performance resulting from training programs, there are definite limitations to the opportunity to conduct these kinds of studies. Success of the task would be measured by the accurate recording of any definite improvements in the organisation after employee training (Zaitseva et. al, 2016). Using an example there should be seen an increase in profit post training program, and it should be evident that training is at the core of improvements rather than any other factor (Hervie and Winful, 2018). It could be argued that a training program should not be given too much credence when it cannot be properly assessed as to direct impact on organisational performance (Afzal et al, 2010). Therefore, it is essential that acceptable criteria of measuring the effectiveness of training in departments beside operations must be established.

Process of Training

The actual organization and management of training should be studied to fully understand training effectiveness. There are two major elements of measuring training effectiveness, the first being “output benefit” which is the traditional approach. Through this method the effectiveness of training is measured in improvements in individual performance (Abbas and Asghar, 2010). The second is the training process effectiveness, which is used to assess improvements to an organisation irrespective of the individuals on training courses. Studies may find that despite intensive or specialised training programs an organisation finds very little improvement (Akpaniteaku, 2019). Whereas competitors may be found that gain enormous success with similar training programs. This is due to the training process; effectiveness of training varies with individuals and groups being trained; perhaps management has little control on who is being trained, whereas it could be honed to better suited trainees (Aravamudhan and Krishnaveni, 2015). Thus, the difference between two extreme outcomes previously described lies in training management, not only in the training department but in the organization generally (Almanza, 2019).

Element of training

There are three elements used to measure the effectiveness of training: accurate identification of training needs; accurate selection of participants and appropriate course

content (Alves et al, 2017). These can be used to measure failings in training outcomes, such failings hinge on the specific objectives of the training. Factors such as poor selection, weak identification of training needs and inappropriate content and so on cause failings which can be measured through deviation from the ideal.

- Identification of training needs

There are two classifications of training needs: organization and individual needs. Organization needs are those structural aspects essential for success. Individual needs are those of matching the employees and their personalities with suitable skills (Anand et al, 2018). The employee's training needs are to be identified through the corporate system: skill gap analysis; training needs assessment, and performance appraisal, counselling sessions and periodic job evaluation. For training to fulfil the organisation's need, it must be directly related to core business activities (Atieno, 2015). The best means of identifying any employee skill gaps is for HR to utilize an organizational modelling human resources management package to rigorously match job specifications with the employee's personal profile (Poulet, R. 2008).

- Selection of participants

Training is best targeted for individual employees or groups where skills are lacking. This training has a tailored agenda with a means to build up an employee's ability within the organisation; a specific training statement can be used through an annual training programme for staff (Badran and Khalifa, 2016). Most organizations fail to target training effectively and so find that employees are sent through training programmes that do not suit them personally and so that despite training employees fall short of fulfilling the ideal (Barzun, 2000).

- Appropriate course content

Once a skill gap is identified and the staff are selected for a training programme to bridge the gap on a course that is assumed to meet organisational needs by training employees to purpose (Boella and Goss-Turner, 2019). However, the program structure needs to be suitable for the trainees with a skill set vital to their needs. One method of evaluating a course is to question the participants; a questionnaire is a useful method and can allow the organisation to read the opinions of the participants on aspects of the program. Poulet (2008) contends that once a course is evaluated and understood to meet the needed outcome it may then be finely honed to further meet the highest standards.

However, a course that fails to impart needed skills or knowledge can be dropped from a training programme and replaced due to the difficulties of improving a method that does not work (Bryman and Bell, 2011). The level of that skill and knowledge gained is the effectiveness of the training course and this can be measured; as to what standard and how efficiently did the course train up staff in meeting the target (Chen, Chang and Yeh, 2004).

Typically, course effectiveness can be measured by understanding the training process cost measurement; this measurement is obtained by multiplying together the cost of the course in question with the effectiveness percentage (Dardzi and Czamecka, 2017). The cost includes direct cost of trainers, accommodation such as training rooms, employee travel time, and so on. Appropriateness of a course can be further judged as to its value for money.

2.1 Kirkpatrick Four Levels of Evaluation:

In the literature there are different models to assess the preparation viability, for example, Phillip's model (1966), Galvin's CIPP (1983), Brinkerhoff's model (1987), Kraiger, Ford and Salas' model (1993), and Holton's model (1996). Be that as it may, Kirk Patrick's four-level model (1967) is the most broadly utilized.

Response assessment implies sensation of the preparation, and it is the way individuals respond in the wake of preparing programs and their encounters (Dessler 2005). Learning assessment is the estimation of the information before the preparation and programs and after the preparation programs. Conduct assessment is essentially did the learners utilize their insight through trainings in a viable manner at work? Result assessment is the impact on the associations after the further developed abilities and information through the preparation (Jarvis and Williams, 2017).

Training is defined by Phillips (1997) as a systematic process of examining the worth, value, or meaning of an activity or a process. No one method is suited to every evaluation therefore several methods of measurement have been developed. While there are several models developed for measuring HRD and training effectiveness, the most accepted model is that developed by Kirkpatrick (Jung and Yoon, 2016). The model asserts that there are four areas of a training program that require measuring for effectiveness: that is emotional reaction, achievement of objectives, behavioural changes, and organizational impact.

Furthermore, Kirkpatrick (1998) identified a four-level process of training evaluation: These being reaction, learning, behaviour, and results.

Emotional Reaction

The reaction refers to the emotional attitudes of participants post-training. A positive emotional reaction is found in those that find they can happily apply new skills and knowledge to the organisation (Kanwal and Arshad, 2017). Employees' general attitude, expectations and motivation can all be measured. Even though emotional responses are subjective, the reaction does provide useful feedback on a training course's style and content. This can aid in understanding the value of a course (Susomrith and Coetzer, 2015).

The emotional response can be learned from post training questionnaires. According to Baird, questionnaires should be aimed at measuring the trainees' attitudes toward content, process (presentation style), definition of course objectives, attainment of course objectives and overall course value (Kizildag and Kim, 2010). These measurements allow an understanding of trainee attitudes to course content and the training material. However, post training questionnaire methods have been criticized in terms of their accuracy and bias (Lgwenagu, 2016). They have been subject to criticism due to ad type questions influencing trainee answers. Despite attempts to improve questionnaires it can be understood that emotional responses are unlikely to be without bias due to its subjective nature. However, Kirkpatrick states that courses should be evaluated by trainee reactions to help improve design of courses (Majid et. al, 2019).

Achieving Learning Objectives

With this second level of measurement, the achieving learning objectives the gaining of knowledge and skills through the training course and to what extent they will translate to improving job performance can be measured (Michel Armstrong, 2001). An expanded practical skill set, and higher knowledge are measurable indications of successful training and a requirement for a meaningful HRD program.

Pre and post-test methods of evaluating training effectiveness will display levels of improvement: Using a benchmark helps to show to what extent knowledge and skills have been obtained from the training experience (Palka, 2017). Pre and post tests may be conducted in the classroom workshop and can yield direct results in a safe learning environment. However, the measuring is implemented the results obtained should be compared to the learning objectives (Brahmana and Fei Ho, 2018).

Learning can be described as the degree to which training has positively affected an employee's work-related attitude to the gained knowledge and skills and how far the new knowledge has expanded due to training (Pizam 2005).

Behavioural Changes

This third approach measures the effectiveness of training on an employee's behaviour within the organisation: evaluating work-based performance and moral as a result of training (Price 2007). An ongoing in-house employees' appraisal system can be utilised to help measure behaviour (Punia and Kant, 2013). However, it is very important to

understand that behavioural changes may not entirely result from training. Studying behavioural changes may take on too much detail and cross over into the general nature of behavioural change rather than that resulting directly from training (Saleem and Burney, 2008). One method of measuring behaviour is to set initial performance objectives, these then can be compared to set objectives and used as a measurement of transferring emotional reaction and learned knowledge into behavioural changes.

The executives by goals (MBO) are one of a few different strategies for estimating execution changes. MBO designs empower individual business-related destinations to be set with explicit spotlight on carrying out preparing encounters (Ritchie and Lewis, 2003). Morrissey, G. furthermore, Wellstead, W (1980) generally demand the members to announce individual and business-related goals in composed structure toward the finish of instructional courses. These goals are formalized and shipped off the learner following a time of multi week of preparing (Cheng-Hua, Shyh-Jer and Shih-Chien, 2009). This is followed up with bi-monthly training reports sent to the trainee. A certificate of completion of training is not issued to the participants until all feedback is received. Measuring behavioural changes is here conducted through meeting objectives. However, like the emotional responses, performance appraisal also suffers bias but when applied to measuring behavioural changes it is often the supervisor who can be biased (Beck, 2018). The techniques of reducing evaluator bias include using subordinate, peer and trainee feedback. Therefore, both supervisors and the individual under study should be questioned for their feedback. Also, peer feedback will give a closer analysis of behavioural changes since co-workers are performing the same function alongside the trainee (Batla, 2008). By using these three techniques, the biases inherent in the evaluation will be reduced to insignificant levels.

Impact on Organization

At long last the fourth region in Kirkpatrick's model covers the effect of worker training and development on the actual association (Aswathappa, 2000). Although a training program is judged fruitful just if the training result adjusts intimately with the association's objectives, estimating the effect on the association can be educated from estimating improvement in productivity, security measures, and so forth

Estimating the impact on an association is seemingly a troublesome undertaking on account of the perplexing construction of parts and their communication with the

outside climate: So isolating pre and post training and development may not really give a particular change in benefit or efficiency because of outer variables (Abbas and Asghar, 2010). Albeit passionate response and information learnt are significant in assessing preparing effectiveness, these elements are a momentary sign of the course of HR advancement of an association. Though conduct changes and effect on association are the other two estimates vital for human asset advancement; these address long haul assessment (Clark, 2019).

Albeit the four levels Kirkpatrick's model present are not approaches they do supplement each other. Without transient assessment estimations, training risks bestowing information that isn't adaptable or is unessential to the authoritative objectives (Darvishmotevali et. al, 2018). Similarly, without long haul assessment of social changes and effect on the association, preparing might be fruitful yet its advantages to the association might be restricted or even adverse. Phillips (1991) confirmed that Kirkpatrick's model is probably the most widely accepted framework for classifying different areas of evaluation. A survey conducted by ASTD (1997) indicated that a majority (81%) of HRD managers attached importance to evaluation that (67%) applied Kirkpatrick's model. The four levels of measurement on this model are assessed as a valuable framework that have proven themselves in evaluating the effectiveness of educational training. This goal – focus approach has stood the test of time (Dixon, 1996; Gordon, 1991; Phillip, 1991, 1997).

One normal analysis among a large number who study Kirkpatrick's structure is that the system is inadequate. The actual field has made considerable progress since the mid 1960's and a ton has changed from that point forward. Along these lines, it isn't unexpected addressed whether Kirkpatrick's structure is yet a viable instrument to create a compelling and healthy assessment of a program. The lone catch here is that it is as yet being utilized is as yet one of the most famous devices to use for assessing preparing. Since it was planned and created more than fifty years prior doesn't really mean it can presently don't be a powerful assessment device. That being said on the grounds that the field has developed and grown so a lot, maybe the structure can be changed a smidgen to consolidate the progressions and new material that has been found out with regards to great assessment and its bits, instead of being totally discarded.

2.2 CIRO (Context, Input, Reaction, Outcome) Approach

War, Bird and Rackham has fostered one more remarkable approach to characterize the assessment interaction. Which has got four levels setting, info, response, and result (Phillips, 1997). Setting is an assessment of training needs and training targets. Info assessment is the get-together data regarding what are the conceivable training assets and information them on elective training measure (Fan et. al, 2018). Response assessment is gathering the data about the responses of students and how to utilize them to work on the trainings and advancement. Result assessment is gathering the data about results of trainings and utilizing them for discoveries and result. To have a fruitful result assessment training programs should be carefully coordinated (Phillips, 1997).

Training as per the globalization

Globalization is the process where companies and other industries develop their businesses internationally. Due to the globalization lives of people become easier and better as well (Grimpe et. al, 2019). It means exchange of human capital, products, services, technologies, and other essentials of business all over the world. Due to globalization companies and every industry promotes and enhance their interaction among diverse areas and group of people around the globe. There are many advantages of globalization especially in hospitality industry (Beck, 2018).

Due to globalization, there are many customers who are travel oriented travel and explore around the world and increasing the number of travellers and visitors ultimately increase the revenue of hospitality business (Barzun, 2000). It can be said that globalization has positive influence on hospitality industry. As per the study of Zaitseva, et. al., (2016), globalization is boom for the hospitality business it is because due to it companies get better technology, productive employees and rich traders and stakeholder as well.

Increasing the number of visitors and attracting them hospitality business must create more luxurious and tourist-friendly destination. And this could be possible after providing effective training to the employees (Cheng-Hua, Shyh-Jer and Shih-Chien, 2009). As globalization deals in global context so herein companies must train their employees accordingly. Cultural differences around the world become hurdle and challenge for hospitality industry as per the study of Fan, et. al., (2018). Due to the globalization business access foreign culture as well as new technology that eventually

assists employees to serve quality services and enhance the level of customer satisfaction (Clark, 2019).

For hospitality business it is most significant that their potential customers will get satisfied by their services so that they can visit hotel again. And for serving quality services employees' training is one of the essential factors in increasing the productivity and growth of the companies (Guchait et. al, 2016). Globalization is leading to raise international standardization of training challenges and systems. Training has strong relationship with globalization. As many corporations reach crossways nation boundaries and globalization of the workplace turn out to be the fresh standard, industries must frequently settle into transforms (Beck, 2018).

According to the study of Yap, and Ineson, (2016), experts of every company must study to communicate in a different way. Company procedures are repeatedly adjusted to fit in with the increasing number of diverse background and ethnic group that associations work with. Businesses that are developing with this change ultimately gain a cutthroat benefit more than those who do not change their working pattern as per the globalization (Jones and Wynn, 2019). For increasing productivity companies must provide quality training to their employees.

In hospitality industry adequate training of employees is essential feature, by providing training to workers as per the requirements of globalization that a hotel will become more productive and gaining competitive advantages (Zaitseva, et. al., 2016). Cultural sensitivity, teamwork, managing intelligence, tech savvy individuals, change management and adopting customer behaviour are the core areas where hospitality industry needs to focus on for dealing with the challenges of globalization.

Cultural sensitivity

In simple terms cultural sensitivity is proper knowledge, understanding, awareness and acceptance of other cultures (Kang et. al, 2016). In hospitality industry it is significant that every worker must have proper training so that they can successfully navigate a diverse culture that they are interacting with. This is a primary aspect in training factor it is because it helps the organization to drive its functions smoothly (Kang, et. al., (2016).

Globalization is an international process herein, every industry need that their employees must have skills of cultural sensitivity (Kerry and Sommerville, 2007). If hospitality industry provides proper training related to the cultural sensitivity than the company will gain more productivity which ultimately helps hospitality industry to deal

with global aspects. Along with the workers of organization become more proficient and can deal better with diverse customers as well as clients (Nicolaidis, 2016). If the company provide proper cultural sensitivity training than company may enjoy several benefits.

The aptitude to interact effectively with people of different culture and background is growing day by day within the multicultural working environment (Kumpikaite and Ciarniene, 2008). Moreover, hospitality industry generally involves multicultural clients, customers as well as stakeholders, herein, every organization must prepare their workforce according to the globalization; it was stated in the study of Kang, et. al., (2016). As per the view of Torres, et. al., (2017), training of cultural sensitivity can facilitate the hospitality industry in several ways, it helps companies to enhance cultural competency as well as helps in preventing conflicts that generally occur within the companies due to favouritism, aggravation and retribution (Ling et. al, 2017).

According to the study of Malik, et. al., (2017), training of cultural sensitivity will increase the cultural awareness and helps the employees and other managers to distinguish and react to their unaware unfairness based on typecasts and unfair hypothesis. It is significant for every corporation that they provide training where workers can learn the skill of diversity sensitivity (Luong, 2015). In context of globalization in hospitality industry there are maximum company are becoming global and acquiring changes herein, for those companies it is essential that their workers must be culturally sensitive and change their behaviour accordingly. With the viewpoint of Jones, and Wynn, (2019), lack of cultural sensitivity can limit worker's communication skills.

Therefore, for creating an individual more effective and increase developed the skills of communication training of cultural sensitivity is extremely important. For dealing with diverse group of people within the hospitality industry communication skills plays essential role (Majid et. al, 2019). Further, it was stated in the study of Almanza, (2019), effective diversity sensitivity stimulates an individual to speak up and present their views and opinion within the group discussion. It motivates workers helps them to communicate, ask queries, raise concern, and report events of unfairness if they experience or examine (Mills et al, 2014).

Moreover, in short helps in increasing the level of motivation and selfconfidence of employees. Cultural diversity has great influence on hospitality industry. The study of D'Aniello, et. al., (2016), reveals that cultural sensitivity is highly important

hospitality business; it is because hospitality industry is directly related with global customers and clients. Hence, his phenomena are quite challenging due to the communication barriers and hurdle of teamwork. As per the study of Almanza, (2019), cultural sensitivity is essential because it allows workers to effectively functions in another culture.

Teamwork

This term teamwork is an essential and most important part of every business. The basic meaning of teamwork is employees trying to work together with each other by using their skills and giving positive feedbacks to their examiners. Sonnenschein, (2020), stated in their study that majority of people assemble to achieve common target is called as team. Along with they also stated that without team no company can achieve success and never become frontrunner. Collective efforts of workers called as teamwork. It performs a fundamental role in hospitality industry (Nicolaidis, 2016).

For maintaining the standard of products and services teamwork is necessary in hospitality business. For gaining productive outcomes and proficiency the company needs to create proper team structure and design according to the objective. As per the study of Guchait, et. al., (2016), organizations should design a team where every individual focus on achieving common objective and concern on increasing the customer satisfaction, quality of services and products (Leonard, 2019). For accomplish these there is need of well-designed team structure which helps team to perform their daily tasks as well as targets effectively.

Sonnenschein, (2020), stated in the study that for making an effective and effectual team leadership plays crucial role. The important traits of leadership are innovation and creativity in hospitality industry. Leadership is not just for customer services but it for enhancing their team and teamwork. The study of Ling, et. al., (2017), reveals that innovative leadership frequently provides learning. In the competitive environment of hospitality business and due to globalization companies needs to advance their training and try to attract customers. By developing the skills of leadership eventually increase more teamwork without any disputes and barriers which are generally occur in the organization (Kizildag and Kim, 2010). Along with this for developing the innovative leadership skills it takes extra time and more advanced training but if the leaders are willing to be flexible can build strong team and innovate new services which eventually increase the level of satisfaction of customers (Kang et. al, 2016).

Further, in the study of Guchait, et. al., (2016), innovative leadership is that kind of technique which contributes and influencing employees to produced innovative and creative ideas, services, and products. Innovative thinking is one of the crucial aspects in addition to the traditional business thinking (Heyden et. al, 2018). It eventually allows employees to bring new and fresh opinions that help company to solve challenges. Along with it also increase the pace of working of organization. The importance of leadership quality of manager in hospitality industry leads teamwork and eventually provides productivity to the business (Guchait et. al, 2016).

Moreover, teamwork can be increased by rewarding for accomplishment and this could be done by a leader or executor of the team. Along with by respecting employees also increase the team efforts and results into effective work done by workers (Liang, et. al., (2017). Giving respect to team member is the way to motivate them and encourage them towards achieving goals of organization. In the competitive era of hospitality industry and due to globalization, there is cutthroat competition among the companies herein, in this business need to put extra effort on creating their team more strong healthy (Franklin, 2012).

Managing diversity

Hospitality industry has been involving very broad range of career option. An individual can work in many areas within the hospitality industry (Dessler, 2005). One thing is most common in all the business that they require an effective leadership so that they can manage diversity on workplace. Managing diversity is totally depending upon the management system of the company. The management of the company must set example for the workers. Syed, and Ozbilgin, (2019), stated in their study that, for managing diversity within the hospitality industry company must be always respectful. It is accountability of the management of the company to show their workers how they want them to behave and treat one another (Coles, 2000).

Management can achieve this by being fair, trustworthy, and open with their work force. In view of the fact consumer service is a key phase of the hospitality industry, employees of the company are bound to differ and have diverse customs of dealing with the customers and troubles that take place (Fan et. al, 2018). When such troubles happen, management must put into practice the qualities mentioned over and treat each one uniformly. Another way of managing diversity within the workplace is management must create career-development programme for their hospitality

employees. In hospitality industry there are lots of opportunities available to move forward and an individual can learn new skills (Franklin, 2012).

Communicate with all of workers about their career goals and acquire vigorous steps to assist them attain them, such as helping them fill out a submission for a release position in another hotel or bistro activate by their company stated by the Suharnomo, et. al., (2017), in their study. By practicing management can effectively manage their diverse workforce along with every work will get more engaged in their jobs. According to the study of Badran, and Khalifa, (2016), diversity within workplace is significant it eventually helps company to increase their productivity, communication level, creativity, and innovation. Along with this diversity in the workplace permits business to produced and design more creative and advanced services to their guests and customers (Grover, 2015). Herein, managing diversity is one of the important parts and the management of the company must provide training to the seniors' executors who generally manage teams.

The companies who provide training for managing diversity that company eventually increase the productivity and proficiency along with grab more market share within hospitality industry (Hanafi et al, 2017). There are numbers of hotels that are working internationally, and it faces significant impact of globalization. If any organization that is operating in foreign country and that county is rich with multiculture society herein, company has responsibility to train their employees as per the preference and culture of the society. If the company is not doing its operations according to the society, then it might face challenges that drag down it level into hospitality market (Syed, and Ozbilgin, 2019). According to the viewpoint of Boella, and Goss-Turner, (2019), through effective managing diversity business can well enhance their customer services. Therefore, it is essential that every company have to more become more engage in providing training to their employees so that they can improve their core abilities and able to serve better services to the customers.

Emotional intelligence

Emotional intelligence is the aptitude of an individual to monitor one's and other person's emotions (Jain and Gautam, 2014). With the skill of emotional intelligence one can able to distinguish between different emotions and label them properly, by practicing this one can able to use emotional information to guide thinking ad behaviour in right place. This psychological theory was developed by the Peter Salovay and John

Mayer. Salovey and Mayer initially explain emotional intelligence “The aptitude to distinguish sentiment, to contact and produce feeling so as to help out thought, to comprehend feeling and emotional awareness, and to thoughtfully normalize sentiment so as to encourage emotional and logical enlargement.”

In the study of Jung, and Yoon, (2016), there are almost five components of the emotional intelligence such as self-awareness, self-regulation, internal motivation, empathy, and social skills. As per the study of Koc, (2019), self-awareness is the skill to distinguish and recognize individual mood, feeling and drives and the consequence of them on both self and others. Self-awareness depends on one’s capability to observe one’s own emotional situation and to properly recognize and the feelings being experienced (Jones and Wynn, 2019).

Increasing this aptitude is necessary for sensible self-assessment and constructs self-assurance and the aptitude to get oneself less critically (Kang et. al, 2016). Another component is self-regulation, this is the ability to control disorderly emotional desire and feel. It occupies the capacity to defer decision and holdup action to permit time for consideration. From a neuroscientific viewpoint, an individual can regularly examine this ability, or be deficient in of it, by study response era (Koc, and Boz, 2020).

Internal motivation is about functioning with and for an internal visualization of what is significant, an inquisitiveness and aspiration for knowledge and growth, a drive that goes further than outside rewards such as capital or position (Lgwenagu, 2016). There is frequently a well-built force to accomplish, confidence even in the face of breakdown and executive commitment. There are also threats, mainly in the occurrence of an unwarranted intelligence of strictness stated in the study of Darvishmotevali, et. al., (2018).

In hospitality industry it is significant that every worker must be self-aware by their own emotions and moods. Along with organization must provide training related to emotional intelligence (Madafg, 2017). It is because every employee must have command on their own emotions while dealing with customers. Every worker of the organization must learn for managing stress. As hospitality market has to deal with different and diverse culture people, therefore it is necessary to provide training and conduct workshops for stress management (Maxwell, 2012).

Along with, above skills one more skill is important that is social skills. This includes the aptitude to manage relationship, create strong networks, find common ground and build link. In the study of Koc, and Boz, (2020), it will frequently assist when leading transform, being influential, structure proficiency and getting immense

presentation from groups. At the same time as multifaceted and to some extent doubtful, Emotional Intelligence replicate a central set of competences inside what it is to be specialized (Punia and Kant, 2013). Learning in this part remains fundamental inside the occupation but in the more and more much demanding surroundings in front it might create the dissimilarity among achievement and breakdown.

Tech savvy individual

Tech savvy person is that kind of individual who have abundant of knowledge and information about modern technology and use their skills to take benefits of the present technology (Ritchie and Lewis, 2003). Savvy is considered as understanding or proper knowledge of how to do something. Tech savvy is important skill to be smarter and more advanced with technology. This is term that means utilizing one's awareness of the contemporary technology to resourcefully fit in it into private and specialized lives. This skill is essential within the hospitality industry because hospitality market deals in advanced and creative atmosphere. The customers want advanced technology to satisfy their needs and requirements. Technology is the key aspect of increasing one's level of satisfaction (Verevka, 2019).

Herein, it is significant that company must provide training to their employees so that every worker learns how to operate and present this skill in front of their potential clients and customers (Romanova et al, 2016). Because of globalization it is quit challenging for businesses. Dealing with diverse workforce and providing them training is one of the biggest challenge faces by companies in today's period. But for being frontrunner in hotel industry it is significant that companies adopt advanced technology and provide training to their workforce (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012). By practicing company ultimately grow and capture more market share within the hospitality market. It is mentioned in the study of Torres, and Mejia, (2017), that technology has played very vital role in advancement of the company and raising the bars of profits. Although adopting advanced technology raises expenses but still it helps in increasing the position of business especially in hospitality industry. In the investigation of Bharwani, and Talib, (2017), technology helps the company to reduced costs, enhance operational efficiency, and improve services along with increase customer experience. Within the hospitality industry optimistic customer experience is extremely essential. If the customer has positive experience, then eventually visit hotel again and ultimately with optimistic experience brand awareness increased (Shankar,

2008). In short for increasing brand awareness and value company must adopt advanced technology.

After adopting innovative technology company must build proper structure of training and conduct workshops for those employees who are adequate for performing and dealing with advanced technology (Sims and Ronald, 2006). Moreover, provide training and making every employee tech savvy is important for every business that is functioning in hospitality market. Digital solutions can present consumers with nextlevel ease and personalization at the same time as giving brands added imminent into customer first choice. In-room tablets permit visitors to set up 'Do Not Disturb' codes, order room service, book transport, manage illumination and radiance, alter TV channels, and lock/unlock their rooms (Udin et al, 2019). On the other hand, technology also present new dare to hoteliers. In the digital era, customers frequently experience like they previously identify the hotel before they even reach on the destination. In the digital area business must provide proper training to their workers so that they effectively deal with customers (Verevka, 2019).

Change management

Change management is the procedure tools and techniques to manage the human resources of change to attain the requirement o the business (Tulung and Ramdani, 2016). Change management centre on the community influence by the transform. Some modification to procedure, scheme, association arrangement and/or job position will contain a practical side and a group side. As per the view of Montargot, and Lahouel, (2018), a company functions on changing conditions, mutually inside and exterior. Such vibrant surroundings demand flexibility inside the association and as a result, potential to take up predictable transformation. Such focal point needs the dedication of unit's workers (Wadhwa, 2013). In the hospitality commerce, this is particularly so, allowing for the labour-intensive functions that act in response to the unstable trade and the seasonality of a consumable goods.

To implement changes within the hospitality industry company can adopt number of models (Yang, 2010). For changing management, it is significant that company creates strong structure and for those businesses can adopt models of change management. Katter's change management model is most popular and accessible in the entire world (Yin, 2009). This model is quite easy and can be adoptable by any company (Majid, et. al., 2019). Along with this model also focus on preparing workers for

adopting changes in organization. Rather than this model also focusses on the human experience and workplace communication.

Changing management involves several benefits. As per the study of Kruja, et. al., (2016), it assesses and understand the need and the impact of change along with helps in reducing time that needed to implement change. For adopting change company must prepare their workers for adopt change and work with different pattern and working style. Proper and adequate training will lead successful change management. With the viewpoint of Majid, et. al., (2019), change management is functioned by companies to help persons, teams, and the entire association in the change, by means of technique to readdress the utilization of assets, and other manner of action that considerably redesign a business or association (Zaitseva et. al, 2016).

According to the Oshins, (2017), training is the foundation stone of change management. For workers to carry regarding transformation successfully and find out flexible and buildable ability, they must take delivery of suitable and proper training. Each worker will extend training necessities as per the skills, awareness and behaviour necessary to put into practice the change (Boella and Goss-Turner, 2019). A helpful tool for producing these necessities is the training requirements evaluation investigation, an analytic instrument for shaping what training requirements to take place. This investigation collects information to decide how employees and the association can expand to achieve their objectives and targets (Beck, 2018). More prominently, this inspection must be carrying out not just for the workforce and their industrial skills, but besides for the executives and controller; if they require training to converse and direct the transformation.

Customer behaviour

According to the study of Kim, et. al., (2018), consumer behaviour comprises person decision-making (IDM). IDM has proposition in consumer fulfilment, devotion, and other behavioural purpose in the direction of the firms' goods and services. The number of companies in the marketplace for an exacting manufactured goods or service has led to the present high rank of rivalry in the marketplace. In adding up, customers have a broad variety of goods and services from which to decide in sort to assure their requirements (Barzun, 2000). This has turned out to be a main challenge to company. A company that is to carry on in the modern market must be capable to recognize, comprehend, and act in response to the wants of customers (Ardjmand and Daneshfar, 2020).

The units ought to offer that expands goods and services that are of high feature and value to meet up the demands of consumers. On the other hand, as per the view of Ting, et. al., (2019), the traditional business approach of centre on the increasing of the profits of the organization no longer be relevant in the existing marketplace. In spite of a business's considerate of the requirements of the customers. A business may expand goods and services that essentially please the wants of customers; though, additional forces may control the customer who might finish up buying and obtaining choice goods within the marketplace (Batla, 2008). Other business that deals in physical goods, the hospitality business is primarily concerned with services. The customers will be fulfilled by the excellence of the service offer as contrast to the value of the goods in further business atmosphere (Blayney et. al, 2020). The quality of the service is in revolving inclined by the interpersonal communication as well as the human resources connections.

It is then significant for the executive in the hospitality industry to recognize how the customers create assessment on the kind of services they require and from where to acquire the services. a variety of models have been developed in the latest precedent that effort to give details how the customers create a choice, ultimately acquire, and use a good and service (Chetty, 2016). Cognitive approach is consumer behaviour model that can be used by the company for dealing and understanding the behaviour of consumers. In the cognitive approach, the behaviour of a consumer is mainly qualified to one's internal cognitive aptitude, the capability to distinguish and course little knowledge (Chow, Haddad and Singh, 2007).

It is deeply attaching to the ground of Cognitive Psychology (Wang, et. al., 2019). According to the technique, the outside issues like surroundings of a person are calculated as motivation that makes information for internal management procedure. In this, there is need for proper training given to the workers so that they can understand and recognize behaviour of customers (Darvishmotevali et. al, 2018). As it is mentioned above discussion hospitality market has involves and deals with diverse range of customer so the business peer the behaviour of customers and give training to the employees accordingly (Kim, et. al., 2018). Culture is mainly dominant for associations in the hospitality industry that have prolonged their procedure to a worldwide market. Culture and lifestyle of individuals also affect the buying behaviour of an individual consequently it influences the operations of organization in the hospitality industry (Franklin, 2012).

Training as per the hierarchy

Training is the term that represents prime opportunity to expand the knowledge base of all workers. The employees are getting proper training as per their requirement that human is more capable to perform necessary and essential tasks for their company (Heyden et. al, 2018). Due to adequate training a worker will properly understand his/her responsibilities within the role along with they build their level of confidence. As per the study of Rodriguez, and Walters, (2017), the level of confidence ultimately helps and individual to enhance their performance and eventually company enjoy this benefit. Human resources who are capable and on peak of altering business standard assist the corporation grasp a position as a leader and tough player inside the hospitality industry (Kang et. al, 2016).

Further with proper training employee get extra satisfaction. With the viewpoint of Wheeler, et. al., (2017), if the company is investing into training it ultimately shows employees are valued by them.

The training constructs an encouraging place of work. Workers can increase access to training they would not have or else recognized about or sought out themselves (Kizildag and Kim, 2010). Human resources who experience valued and challenged by training prospect might experience extra fulfilment in the direction of their occupation. For increasing the level of satisfaction, it is significant that business organization should provide proper and required training their employee. In hospitality industry there is more need that employee of there are more satisfied and confident and for acquiring this company must conduct workshops and essential training programs for their workers (Kruja et. al, 2016). By practicing this company can get more engaged workers and, in the end, it increases their profit margin plus their brand value.

As per the research of Palka, (2017), the company conducts training programs the authority address weaknesses of their employees. Most human resources will have few weak points in their workplace ability. Training programs permit hospitality industry to reinforce those skills that every worker wants to get better (Liang et. al, 2017). An expansion curriculum carry workforce to an elevated rank, so they all have equal proficiency and understanding.

Further, with proper training the company can be able to create proper consistency. In hospitality industry employees must have proper awareness of process and functions of the company. From the viewpoint of Karia, et. al., (2016), a vigorous training and development course makes sure that workforce have a reliable awareness and background information. The uniformity is mainly applicable for the organization's

fundamental guiding principles and actions. All workers should be alert of the prospect and events inside the corporation (Maxwell, 2012). Along with enhance efficiencies in procedure results in economic growth for the business. In hospitality industry it is necessary that members of staff must have proper knowledge in context of business basic policies ad strategies.

Moreover, with an effective training company gets several benefits. On the other hand, it is a difficult and challenging for the management to decide who should be training and what kind of training should be provided along with a proper time. As per the study of Clark (2019), training should be given according to the company's hierarchy.

According to the study every person whether it is from upper, middle, or lower level each one need proper training to handle challenges in business environment (Nicolaidis, 2016). As it is mentioned that hospitality industry deals in wide range of operation along with it has great interaction with diverse customers so in hospitality business every level of management need training.

The word company hierarchy refers to the collection and association of persons inside a business as per to the control, rank, and job purpose. As per the view of Ardjmand, & Daneshfar (2020), in common, a hierarchy is any structure or associations in which group or individuals are grade one over the other according to position or power. At the same time as the majority corporations and industry have hierarchies, they can also be division of any group, with administration and any ordered religion (Pramjeeth et al, 2017). A corporate hierarchy defines both power and accountability, and delegate headship over a corporation's workers, subdivision, divisions, and other managerial depending on their position within the partition.

According to the study of Ranggadara, & Sahara, (2017), every job in the hotel industry demands a lot from its human resources, together with booking reservations, treatment of guest requests, catering weddings, outfitting place to stay, setting up elevators or leaky bathe, cooking for a company brunch and reserving theatre tickets and dinner dates (Ritchie and Lewis, 2003). Like in any other business, there is a totem extremity of place, from the uppermost position CEO to the lowest position dishwasher or parking lot assistant. But no issue what the position, each individual functioning in a

hotel represents on the hotel principles. Everyone who is functioning within hotel needs training according to their preferences and weaknesses (Saleem and Burney, 2008).

Top Management

From the research of Wiersema, & Bird (2017), top-level executors establish extensive tactical strokes for the business in all-purpose, and concern on the giant image. High level directors tend to have a considerable extent of understanding, preferably athwart a broad range of purpose (Shankar, 2008). There are several highlevel directors turn out to be fraction of a decision-making group by expertise their practical authority across assorted responsibility.

The top-level management is often fulfilled with all such skills and knowledge. In the hospitality industry it is essential that high level authority have such skills, it is because they must deal with diverse workforce plus different clients and customers who have broad requirements (Spencer and McLaren, 2017).

There are several responsibilities associated with top level management. As per the study of Yusliza, et. al., (2019), the main function of the managerial group, or the high-level directors, is to examine and scrutinize at the business as a complete and develop extensive tactical policy. Business policies, extensive economic investments, tactical agreement, planning with the board, stakeholder supervision, and other highlevel administrative responsibilities are frequently high-risk high return decisionmaking idea in nature (Ting et. al, 2019). High-level executive functions are consequently often high pressure and high manipulate roles within the institute. Therefore, top-level management also needs training according to their responsibilities. As it is mentioned that their jobs are filled with pressure and stress herein there is need to conduct training programs that gives education related to stress management in difficult circumstances (Wiersema, & Bird, 2017).

According to research of Tulung & Ramdani, (2016), training is must in high-level management. Hospitality industry is seeker of fresh talent, herein there is need to provide training to those individuals who are fresh recruits within the company. Along with this if the company is providing training to the top-level management, it must include such components which helps them to get more development opportunities (Torres and Mejia, 2017). The company must include these nine components in training course of high-level executors:

- A skilful and effectual curriculum manager

- Evaluation of requirements all through the corporation
- Training arrangement with business objectives
- Purpose that can be calculated
- Leaders' supporter for education
- Contemporary and applicable knowledge substance
- Imaginative ideas for training projects
- Continuing promotion to support participation
- Strengthening of what recruits discover

Such elements will enhance workers level of confidence and ultimately it helps them to perform in better way. So, it is clear from above discussion that high-level management also needs training (Wang et. al, 2019). As a result, hospitality industry also focus on providing training education for high-level executors; so that they can focus more creating and innovating new principles and standards for the business and eventually helps in capturing ore share within the market.

Middle management

Middle level management is including leadership level of hierarchical organization, is being subordinate to the higher administration but on top of the lowest levels of operational personnel (Yusliza et. al, 2019). For instance, operational controller may be measured middle executive; they might also be classifying as non-management employees, depending upon the strategy of the group. As per the study of Heyden, et. al., (2018), Middle level executors' responsibility might comprise numerous everyday jobs depending on their section. A few of their tasks are described below:

- Constructing and executing effectual teamwork and information classification
- Defining and observe team-level performance indicators
- Diagnosing and resolving problems within and among work groups
- Constructing and executing reward structure
- Supporting accommodating activities
- Reporting presentation information up the sequence of control and, when appropriate, recommend tactical changes

Because middle managers work with both top-level executors and first-level controllers, middle managers lean to cover admirable interpersonal skills linking to communication, motivation, and mentoring. From the research of Schubert, & Tavassoli, (2020), Leadership skills are also significant in hand over everyday jobs to first-level administrator. Middle administration may be reduced in business because of reform. Such changes include downsizing, 'delaying' dipping the quantity of

supervision levels, in addition to outsourcing (Wang et. al, 2019). The transform might happen to decrease expenditure; as middle managing is usually remunerated more than junior staff or to create the business flatter, which authorize recruits, leaving the business further modern and elastic (Heyden, et. al., 2018).

Every middle level manager who is performing jobs has some responsibilities towards their company. Middle-level executive can comprise common managers, division managers, and subdivision managers (Udin et al, 2019). They are responsible to the top-level administration for their section's occupation, and they allocate more time to managerial and directional occupation than higher administration (Schubert, & Tavassoli, 2020). A middle supervisor's role may emphasize:

- Executing managerial tactics in conformance with the corporation's strategies and the objectives of the top administration.
- Defining and conversing policies and information from top administration to lower administration.
- Most significantly, inspiring and granting guidance to lower-level administrators to help them in performance enhancement and achievement of company objectives.

Middle administrators might also converse increasing by offering feedback and suggestions to top administrator. For the reason that middle administrator is extra involved in the everyday workings of a business, they can give important information to top administrators that will assist them to get better the association's performance using a broader, more tactical view (Grimpe, et. al., 2019).

As it is stated that middle level management is engaged in constructing teamwork and look the performance of employees; herein, in this profession an individual need excellent communication skills and interpersonal skills (Sonnenschein, 2020). Company needs to provide training to the managers so that they can improve their interpersonal as well as communication skills. In hospitality industry, the company required fresh talent and this industry commonly deals with diverse kind of workers so they need that their workers must be well trained and good communicators (Glaser, et. al., 2016). For making an excellent team force company must provide training for middle level. They should conduct training programs which increase and enhance the skills which are required for middle level workers. This could help an organization to build an effective and effectual working environment (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012).

As per the study of Spencer, & McLaren, (2017), due to better communication and interpersonal skills works can effectively communicate with each other and increase the rapidity of operations. Further, it explains above that middle level require an effective headship, in this company need to conduct training programs which provide knowledge to an individual that how he/she could become a motivator and how he/she will enhance their capability to being an effective leader and a role model (Ritchie and Lewis, 2003). Within the hospitality industry it is significant that middle level management has effective leaders so that they contribute to making their team effective as well as help in creating their company frontrunner in hospitality market.

Front-line management

The front-line management includes highly skilled managers and even functional specialists. A first line executor is best situated when they focus on calculating and direct specific workers (Price 2007). If a first line manager thinks in terms of supervisors, team leaders, line managers, and project managers he could develop new opportunity in its existing job. From the viewpoint of Arjona-Fuentes, et. al., (2019), first line managers have different skills and ability. They need two different skills such as interpersonal as well as technical skills. Interpersonal skill is required for managing the human resource and technical skill is needed for executing functional tasks (Ritchie and Lewis, 2003). Therefore, front line managers are often extremely important team members with the adaptability and flexibility to contribute to various tasks and operation within the company.

In study of Jarvis, & Williams, (2017), core skills set of frontline managers can be alter depending upon the functions and what they are overseeing. With an effective interpersonal skill, they must be excellent in communication, observing and actively listening, providing, and receiving feedback, prioritizing, synchronize resources and ordering tasks and procedure of the company (Hanafi et al, 2017). With all these effective set of skills employees in front line management must perform their jobs with set of responsibilities. Hospitality business need front line employees must be committed to their job and do perform their tasks with responsibility (Franklin, 2012). By performing tasks with effective skills and accountability company will get desirable position in the industry plus it will facilitate top executors to make more innovative policies for their company (Arjona-Fuentes, et. al., 2019).

In hospitality industry many companies are operating advanced technology and front-line managers must execute and perform their daily operations by using technology (Chetty, 2016). Herein, every worker and manager know how to operate advanced technology. As per the view of Blayney, et. al., (2020), the managers also balance the books and understand enough of everybody's function to fill the gap. Front line managers also called as blocker remover, they must examine every works very carefully so that they can make list of their weakness and provide them training as the workers required for improving their core skills (Dardczi and Czamecka, 2017). Along with first line managers also need training sometime. For controlling and executing teams they sometime require training for being an effective communicator as well as a good listener.

Challenges in imparting training

When the organisations decide to make changes in the organisation and are looking for providing training to the employees, then several challenges are being faced by the challenges in the training results due to several factors (Baytieh and Soubjaki, 2017). If the organisation has a diverse workforce, then it became complex for the organisation to deliver effective training to all the employees as all the employees belong to different socio-economic backgrounds and due to which they have different perspectives towards the things. While imparting the training, different factors can develop obstacles for the organisation and human resource department for giving proper and effective training to the employees.

Punia and Kant (2013) had mentioned in their study regarding the different factors which are having an impact on the effectiveness of the training. The study had mentioned that factors such as motivation, attitude, emotional intelligence, support from the management and leaders, training style and environment, the openmindedness of trainer and certain job-related factors are having an influence on the training outcomes (Beyrouiti, 2016). This study suggested that the organisation should focus on all the factors which are having an impact on the training and should focus on using these factors effectively so that maximum outcomes can be gained through the training and performance of the employees and the entire organisation can be improved.

For the organisations operating in the hospitality, it is important to provide effective training to the employees so that they can deliver better performance in the company and better services to the customers. Many factors can create an obstacle for

the hospitality organisation in delivering better training to the employees. These factors include the different factors related to the human attitude and behaviour, factors related to the external environment in which the company is operating and several factors of the internal environment of the company.

It is important for the organisation to overcome all the challenges and have proper knowledge regarding the factors which are having the potential to create a challenge for the human resource department while providing training. For the human resource department, training and development are crucial and a matter of concern as it is having an impact on the organisational activity. Along with this better training and development helps the organisation in bettering the performance of the employees and different departments in the organisational setting.

Human Attitude and Characteristic related challenges

Effectiveness of the training is also affected by the attitude and characteristics of the individual to which the training is provided. Characteristics of the employee, such as age, experience, learning behaviour, attitude towards learning new things. Rajendra and Udayasuiryan (2015) had performed a study on evaluating the factors which are having an impact on the effectiveness of the training and development. The results of the study revealed that employee's perception towards the training is based on the demographic characteristics and the characteristics of the employee such as experience, age and gender are having an impact on the way they are influenced by the training programmes.

Vembar and Amritharaj (2014) had mentioned in their study to evaluate the demographic and environmental factors which are having an influence on the effectiveness of training and development in the hotel industry. According to this study, the demographical factors such as nature of the hotel, age of the employee, the experience of the employee and the types of training the individual had already undergone is having an impact on the effectiveness of the training in the context of the hospitality industry. On the other hand, environmental factors include the resources which are available for the company to train the employees is also having an impact on the effectiveness of training.

Moreover, the study had mentioned that in the hospitality industry the organisation needs to focus on developing the management skills, social skills, language, cultural skills, attitudinal changes, ethics, and competitiveness in the

employees who can help them in having a positive impact on the maintaining quality of the service provided and customer retention. Hence the study concluded that for the hospitality industry, both the demographic and environmental factors are important to evaluate the effectiveness of training.

Other job-related factors such as job satisfaction and commitment towards the organisation are the factors which affect the training and can create an obstacle for the firm in delivering proper training to the employees. The organisation needs to focus on designing the training program based on the organisation culture and environment. In the context of the hospitality industry, it is important to understand the impact of these factors on the training as human resource is the most important for the organisations operating in this industry. It is important for the organisation that the employees should have a positive attitude towards the training which is being provided to them. If the employee is willing to learn a new skill and want to enhance their knowledge, then training can be more effective. It can be said that if the organisation culture and environment promote learning and motivate the employees to learn new skills, then it becomes easy for the firm to get better outcomes of the training which is being provided to the employees.

Hanafi et al. (2017) had mentioned in their study regarding the connection between job satisfaction and effectiveness of training. According to this study if the employees are satisfied with their jobs and are having higher job satisfaction, then they are likely to respond positively towards the training. If the employee is having a positive reaction towards the training, then the training will give better outcomes as the individual will reflect a positive learning attitude towards learning the new concept. Employee's behaviour is also associated with his perception towards his performance and effectiveness of the training.

In support of this Shrafat, et al. (2018) had also mentioned in their study regarding the impact of job satisfaction on training motivation. The study had mentioned that job satisfaction and the employee's perception and commitment towards the organisation are having an impact on the effectiveness of the training. This study concluded that the job satisfaction of the employee has the potential to motivate the employee to learn the skills and gain knowledge effectively in training and motivate them to get the maximum benefit from the training. Hence, it can be said that job satisfaction is having an impact on the effectiveness of the training programs conducted by the organisation.

External Environment-related challenges

The external environment in which the organisation is operating is having a greater impact on the organisation and affects all the practices of the organisation. When training is provided to the employee, then the way in which the training is conducted is also having an impact on the effectiveness of the training. The study of Atieno, (2015) had mentioned that the changes which are taking place in the external environment of the organisation are having an impact on the training which is being provided to the employees. It can be said that the organisation should use the best ways of training the employees based on the external environment changes so that they can train the employee effectively.

Effectiveness of training is also affected by the resources used for training and the way in which the organisation conducted the training. Hajjar and Alkanaizi (2018) had mentioned in their study regarding the different factors which are having an impact on the effectiveness of the training. The study had mentioned that the training environment is having an impact on the employee's behaviour regarding the training and based on it the effectiveness of the training program also varies. Along with this the study also mentioned that the factors such as facilities and materials used in training, training schedule and the presentation styles which is used for providing training to the employees are having an effect of the training and the behaviour of trainees towards the training and based on these factors the employee learns the new things. In support to this Luong, (2015) had also mentioned in their study that the concept of the training, training process and the different techniques and technologies which are implemented in the training programs are having an influence on the training outcomes and its effectiveness.

Mills et al., (2014) had mentioned that several factors of the external environment of the company such as economic condition and legislature conditions of the country are having a significant impact on the way in which the organisation prioritises the need for training and design the training programs to maximise its impact on the performance of the employees. Legislature factors which need to be taken in concern while designing the training are health and safety laws, code of conduct and rules and regulations such as employment law, equality law and rules which are required to followed by the organisation. Based on it, the organisation also needs to have better economic condition and resources so that they are effectively developing a training program. The study concluded that the organisation should try to use the better resources so that they can use cost-effective and safe training environment for the

employees so that they can be effectively trained, and their performance can be improved.

Challenges related to the Internal Environment of the organisation

Several internal factors which are related to the internal environment are having an impact on the way in which the training is provided to the employees in the organisation. Leadership is an important aspect of the internal environment which is having a significant impact on the training. It can be said that a leader is the one who is responsible for everything which is having in the firm either directly or indirectly. Effective leadership is required for managing all the different tasks and departments effectively in the organisation. In the context of the hospitality industry where everything needs to be perfect and accurate as it is directly having an impact on the reputation of the company, so the firms need to be more concerned regarding the leadership and heaving an effective leader.

Afzal et al. (2010) had mentioned in their study about the role of leadership in training and development. The study had discussed that the leadership skills of the leader are having an impact on the training and development as it bumps up these processes in the organisation. Effective leaders are having better creativity skills and are having an ability to develop better training programs and along with this if the leader is effective, then it is having a positive impact on the training as it motivates the employees to have better skills and knowledge as of their leader. The study concluded that the leaders have an ability to enrich the training and development process in the organisation as the trainer are also influenced by the leaders. If the leaders reflect better communication skills and better situation handling skills, then the trainers will also try to adopt these skills and will be delivering the training in an effective manner.

Simiyu, (2015) had mentioned in his study that most of the organisations across the globe agrees that effective leadership contributes to the organisational performance and development. The author had discussed in their study that for making changes in the organisation and had mentioned that a leader with effective leadership skills is required for training, development and making changes in the organisation. In support of this study Choudhary, (2014) had also mentioned in their study of how leadership styles are having an impact on employee motivation and commitment in the organisation.

The study had mentioned that leaderships is having an impact on the way in which the employee performs and grow in the organisation. The author in the study had

mentioned that with the changing world it is important for the organisations to have an effective leader as it will have an impact on the way in which the employees learn new skills which are required to work effectively in the dynamic and changing working environment. Along with this, the study concluded that a better leader could motivate the employee to perceive the training effectively so that they can work effectively in the organisation and can reflect better commitment towards the company.

Abbas and Asghar (2010) had discussed the role of leadership in organisational change. The study had mentioned that due to globalisation the effective leadership had become important for the organisation for bringing the evolution in the entire organisation and bringing changes in the way in which the employees understand their roles and responsibilities and work in the organisation. If the leader has a better skill, then his/her characteristics can influence the employee to learn new things and is also having a positive impact on training and development. It can be said that effective leadership is required for conducting the training programs in an effective manner and getting outcomes from it. On the other poor leadership can have a negative impact on the management and on the way in which the training is provided to the employees. Hence it can be concluded that effective leader and leadership style is crucial for managing the challenges which can occur while imparting training to the employees in the organisations.

When the employees are recruited in the organisation, then it is essential that at that time, an appropriate candidate should be recruited as per the required roles and responsibilities he is required to perform in the organisation. If an appropriate candidate is selected for a job as per the job description and the individual fits properly with the job, then only they should be required for the job. Udinet al. (2019) had mentioned in their study regarding the impact of recruitment and training on employee performance. The study had mentioned that the recruitment, training, and employee performance are interconnected with each other.

According to the study if the organisation wants the employees should deliver high-quality performance in the company, then it is important that they should focus on proper recruitment and training of employees. The study had revealed that if an appropriate candidate is selected for the job and had provided effective training, then it would help him in learning the skills, knowledge and attitude which is essential for delivering better performance and helps them in being effective.

Kafui et al., (2016) had mentioned in their study that recruitment department of the organisation should be effective in recruiting the individuals with right skills and

abilities so that they can be successful in their jobs. If a proper employee is selected for the job, then the training provided to him would be more effective in developing the skills which would help him to fit in the job which is being assigned to him. This study concluded that organisations should understand that better recruitment is having a positive impact on the overall performance of the organisation.

It can be said that if the recruitment had been done in an appropriate manner and a correct employee is selected for the job based on his skills and knowledge and the job roles, then it became easy to give training to the employee. Along with this better recruitment can help the employees in learning new skills effectively and taking proper training as they already belong to the field for which they are getting training.

Effective management of the organisation is an important aspect of the internal environment which is having an impact on the training and development of employees in the organisation. It is important for the hospitality service providing organisations to focus on the performance of the employees as they are having an impact on the reputation of the firm. Effective performance management is important in the organisations so that they can analyse the performance of all the employee, groups, departments and of the entire organisation. Based on the evaluation of the performance, different training programmes can be developed and designed for improving the performance of the employees and departments in the organisation. It can be said that performance management needs to be effective so that the employees can be trained to work properly with adopting the changes occurring in the industry.

Baytieh and Sooubjaki (2017) had mentioned in their study that the performance management system of the organisation is responsible for improving the performance and effectiveness of the employees in the organisation. The study had mentioned that proper performance management is important for better learning and developing skills and knowledge of the employees through different training programmes. It can be said that effective practices and strategies of the performance management system can lead to better outcomes of the training which is provided by the organisation. Also, Munzhedzi, (2017) has mentioned in his study that performance management plays a pivotal role in getting better results of the training and development strategies and programs of the company by providing the individuals better knowledge regarding their performance management.

It can be said that if the organisation has improper performance management, then it will have a negative impact on the way in which the employee focus on gaining proper training towards development of skills and knowledge. If the performance

management system develops strategies for attracting the employees to enhance their performance by offering them several types of performance appraisals, then it will motivate them to learn the maximum from the training. Different internal factors of the organisations are having a significant impact on the outcomes of the training programmes which are being developed for training the workforce to effectively deliver the roles and responsibilities in the organisation. Along with this the company should have clear goals which can help them in developing better training programmes for the employees of the organisation so that they can effectively improve the performance of the organisation can lead it towards success.

Ways to improve training and development

For the organisation offering hospitality service to the customers, it is essential to have an employee who can deliver effective and desirable service to the customers and help them out in the best possible way. Several studies had revealed that an effective training program developed for the employees working in the hotel industry helps the company in managing the customers effectively and satisfying them with their services. Chaturvedi, (2016) had mentioned in his study regarding the factors affecting the training of employees in the hospitality industry. The study had mentioned that when the organizations are designing the training programs for the employees, then it is essential that they should develop an effective training program and should consider the human differences which are based on the psychographics, socio-graphic and demographic factors which can help them in designing the best training program for the workforce. Appropriate designing of the training program is essential as it will have an impact on the training outcomes. The results of the study mention that it is essential for the company to have better results of the training as it will serve as a function of innovation leading and help the company in improving its performance and serving the customers in an effective manner as well.

Organisations should try to improve the effectiveness of training and development. It is important for the organisation to focus on the development of skills and knowledge of the human resource as they are having an impact on the success of the company. For the hospitality industry organisations, it is essential to have an effective human resource as it is a customer-driven industry and the way in which the employees manage the customers and hold effective communication with them plays a vital role in the success of the hotel. Akpaniteaku (2019) had mentioned in his study

regarding several challenges which are being faced by the company while providing effective training to the employees. The human resource department should focus on making a choice of an appropriate candidate as a trainer and should logically select trainers.

When the company is selected the trainer, they should focus on the educational background, skillset, and experience of training the employees who can help the company in selecting an appropriate candidate and can provide better results of the training programmes. Along with this, the study had also mentioned that the top management should support the training and developing programmes of the company as their support is essential for gaining better outcomes from the training programmes. Moreover, the study had also mentioned that recruitment failures are also having an impact on the training and development of the organisation.

Majority of the challenges of training faced by the organisation are due to the wrong recruitment. When the employees are being selected for the specific job roles, then it is important for the company they should select an appropriate candidate based on their skillset and knowledge so that they can deliver better service to the company. Bad recruitment decisions can cause a lot of loss to the company. Anand et al. (2018) had mentioned in their study regarding the importance of effective recruitment for the company. The study had mentioned that the organisation should focus on all the procedures of recruitment which can help them in getting an appropriate candidate for the job role. If the candidate suits well with the roles and responsibilities of the job, then the training which is being provided to the candidate would be more effective as they will be able to learn the skills. The results of the study had suggested that if the selection of candidates had been made in an effective manner, then the training programmes which are being offered by the company to sharpen their skills will help them a lot and will have a positive impact on the training outcomes for both the company and the individual as well.

Leonard, (2019) had also mentioned in his article regarding the importance of effective recruitment and selection. The study had mentioned that the selecting the quality candidates is important for the company which can help them in developing the skills easily in the candidates which are required for them to work effectively as per their job roles. While selecting the candidate if an appropriate candidate is chosen by the company, then it became easy for the company to train the employees and save excess of training time and cost. Along with this better selection also promotes effective results of the training and help them in training the employees effectively to deliver

high performance in the company as per their job roles. It can be said that selected the best candidate as per the job roles, and description can help the company in having an effective workforce in the company which can deliver high-quality work in the firm.

In the context of hospitality industry, the organisations need to recruit a lot of employees for the different departments and then the employees need to be very specific as per their job roles and description. Employee needs different skillset and knowledge for working in the departments such as front office, housekeeping, food and beverage service department and food production. It is important for the company to describe the job in an effective manner and should focus on it while selecting a candidate for the job role. The job description also plays a significant role in the training, which is being provided to the candidates. Yang, (2010) had mentioned in his study regarding the importance of staff training for the hotel industry. The study had mentioned that the if the employees working in the hospitality industry are given proper training as per the specific need of skills and knowledge of the department for which they are working then it will help them in using their abilities to learn the skills and work effectively in the organisation.

If the company decides to improve the training and development in the organisation, then it is important that they should make changes in the organisational culture. The way in which the employees interact in the organisation and the underlying beliefs, assumption and values of the employees who are reflected in the company are having an impact on their learning attitude. The company should try to develop a culture in which the employees have an attitude to learn new skills and gain knowledge. Also, the company should have effective communication and cooperation among the employee who can help them in being motivated to learn new things and skills of other employees as well. Kanwal and Arshad (2017) had mentioned in their study regarding the influence of organisational culture on training effectiveness. The study had mentioned that organisational culture plays a significant role in the company, and training is influenced by the organisational culture. If the company has a strong culture, then the training programme which is being initiated by the company be more effective in improving the employee cognitive abilities and lead the company towards growth.

Wadhwa (2013) had also mentioned in their study of how the organisational culture can be developed so that it can promote better outcomes of the training programmes. According to this study, the organisation should try to create a culture which easily adopts the policies, strategies, and efforts to promote and encourage the employees for attending the training programmes and learning new things effectively.

Along with this, the company should try to create a culture which promotes the concept of continuous learning. Also, the management of the company should support the innovation, values and norms which can motivate the trainers to learn effectively and enhance their performance in the organisation. It can be said that culture can make a great difference in the way the employees attain the training and have an influence on the effectiveness of the training programmes.

The organisation should focus on improving the performance management system of the company, which can help them in evaluating the performance of the entire company and the individual employees in an effective manner. If the company knows about the strengths and weakness of the workers, then it will help them in developing a better training programme as per the skills and knowledge required by the employees. It is important for the organisation to have effective performance management as it is an important aspect of human resource management. Jain and Gautam (2014) had mentioned in their study regarding the performance management system. The study had mentioned that for a successful organisation it is important that they should have potential candidates for the specific job roles and the performance management system should focus on managing the performance effectively and should develop better training programmes. Along with this, they should try to develop a highly motivated workforce which can have a positive attitude towards the training and makes it more successful.

Osmani and Maliqi (2012) had also mentioned in their study that performance management is important for the company as it helps them in developing better skills among the workers. The study had mentioned that effective performance management can specifically focus on individual performance and can develop better training and has a positive impact on the training outcomes as well. If the performance management system works effectively, then it will help the company in reducing the chances of improper training programs and will help them in developing effective and appropriate training programs for the employees.

In the context of the hospitality industry as the employees belong to diverse social backgrounds, it becomes more important for organisations to train them in an effective manner. In such a workplace, the organisation should focus on developing effective communication which can help them in improving the performance of the employees working in the company. Better information sharing should be the core focus on the management so that they can develop better idea sharing in the company and will also help them in keeping everyone up to date with all the important information.

Effective communication should be enforced when the training is being provided to the employees as it helps them in sharing the learning in an effective manner and also helps them in making sure that everyone understands the training. When the individual is providing training to the employees, then it is essential that they should have better communication skills which can help them in communicating the trainees and helps them in providing effective training as well.

The companies should also focus on motivating the employees to work effectively in the organisation and delivering high-quality work which is essential for improving the performance of the employees in the company. Ali et al. (2018) had mentioned in their study that if the employee is motivated, then they are more attentive towards delivering better performance in the company. When the employees are encouraged to focus on their own roles and responsibilities and are quite motivated to work effectively, then it is having a positive impact on the training.

Motivated employees are having a learning attitude and are more likely to attain the training in a serious manner so that they can positively develop the skills and knowledge of which the training is being provided to them. Khan, (2012) had also mentioned in their study regarding the relationship among motivation, training, and performance of the employees. According to this study, these factors are interconnected and are having an influence on each other so the companies should focus on developing all of them. If the organisation has motivated employees, then the training will have effective outcomes as the employees will try to develop their skills to their fullest through the training and it will lead to having a positive impact on the employee performance.

Satisfaction level of the employees is also an important challenge for the company while providing training to the employees. If the individual is satisfied with his job, then they will have an attitude to learn new thing. Building a positive attitude towards learning is important for the organisation as it motivates the employee to learn new concepts every day in the workplace. Job satisfaction is an important element which shapes the employee attitude in the organisation. Bakoti (2013) had mentioned in their study regarding the relationship between job satisfaction and organisational performance. According to the study if the employees are satisfied with their jobs, then they deliver high-quality work in the company. The organisations should focus on satisfying the employees with the offering them high pay, better rewards, a healthy and positive work environment and offering them better advantages as well. If the

employees are satisfied with their jobs, then it will lead to the development of a positive attitude, and the employee would try to work more effectively in the company.

Learning attitude of the employees is having a positive impact on the effectiveness of the training. Vnouckova (2016) had mentioned in his study about the impact of personality attitude of the individual on employee learning. The study had mentioned that if the individual has a learning attitude, then it will help him in willingly participating in the training and learning programs as they will see it as an opportunity to develop their skills and learn something new which can help them in enhancing the quality of the work which is being delivered by them in the organisation. In support to this the results of the study of Lord et al., (2010) had also revealed that satisfies employee generally appreciate the opportunities of education and learning and evaluates it as an essential element for working effectively in the organisation. It can be said that if the organisations develop a positive attitude in the employee towards the training programs, then the employees will see it as an opportunity and might also try to learn the maximum skills which can help them in being an effective employee for the organisation.

Resources which are used in training is also a challenge for the company. If the company invests better capital for the training programs with all the essential resources, then it will help them in conducting better and effective training programs for the development of skills and knowledge. If we discuss this in the context of the hostel industry, then the organisation should conduct different training programs for the candidates working in diverse departments which can help them in getting better results of the training. All the different things which are having the potential of creating a challenge for the company to receive better outcomes of the training needs to be managed and overcome effectively by the company.

2.3 Hospitality Industry

The hospitality industry is one of the biggest businesses in this world, which has 200 million individuals utilizing, and producing above 10% of worldwide GDP (United Nations 2008) According to report from United Nations (2008) neighbourliness industry is becoming quicker than different areas of the worldwide economy and furthermore stamping 33% of the absolute worldwide help exchange. Anuradha depicts about the accommodation business is the more extensive area than a large portion of different enterprises (Anuradha 2011).

Through the globalization business area has spread worldwide and individuals have begun to go all throughout the planet for business purposes. Individuals who are going for the business purposes have powered for the friendliness business (Olsen, Zhao, 2008). Because of movement and the travel industry, cordiality industry has expanded a great deal as of late in 21st century and there are numerous different jobs have played to foster the neighbourliness business (Pizam 2005).

Conrad Lashley and Alison Morrison, (Lashley and Morrison (eds.), 2000), start from the view that the comprehension of accommodation has been weakened by a mechanical near-sightedness. They propose to work on the comprehension by; “reflecting insights into the study of hospitality that encompass the commercial provision of hospitality and the hospitality industry, yet at the same time recognise that hospitality needs to be explored in a private domestic setting and studies hospitality as a social phenomenon involving relationships between people.” (Lashley and Morrison (eds.), 2000: xvi).

Indeed, even with the emotional change in the obligation markets throughout the most recent couple of months, lodging industry area basics keep on being solid. Selwyn says that; “The basic function of hospitality is to establish a relationship or to promote exchange of goods and services, both material and symbolic, between those who give hospitality (hosts) and those who receive it (guests)... One of the principal functions of any act of hospitality...is to consolidate the recognition that hosts, and guests share the same moral universe or...to enable the construction of a moral universe to which both host and guest agree to belong”. (Lashley and Morrison (eds.), 2000:19)

Lashley accepts that, 'to more likely comprehend neighbourliness exercises we need to comprehend the arrangement of food, drink and convenience in the family unit' (Lashley and Morrison (eds.), 2000:10). He additionally points out that, 'the arrangement of food, drink and convenience addresses a demonstration of fellowship,

it makes representative ties between individuals which set up connections between those associated with sharing accommodation' (Lashley and Morrison (eds.), 2000:11). Then, at that point more for the most part he presumes that, 'neighbourliness is basically a relationship dependent on hosts and visitors' (Lashley and Morrison (eds.), 2000:15).

The Telfer part presents the private space inside which she characterizes friendliness as, 'the giving of food, drink and here and there convenience to individuals who are not ordinary individuals from a family' (Lashley and Morrison (eds.), 2000:39) and presumes that; "if a business have cares for his visitors well out of real worry for their joy and charges them sensibly, instead of exploitatively, for what he does, his exercises can be called neighbourly." (Lashley and Morrison (eds.), 2000:45). She gives no knowledge into what, explicitly, is involved in caring for visitors well; what, explicitly, is certified worry for bliss; and what, explicitly, establishes sensible as opposed to exploitative charges. Neither does she give any sign with regards to how any of these terms would be estimated. Statements of this sort on the friendliness business must be viewed as tattle and of no worth to experts in the hospitality business.

Hospitality Industry alludes basically to organizations that give dwelling/facilities and foodservices for individuals when they are away from their homes. (Turkson 2009)

Training and development programmes in hospitality industry

The significance of training to the accommodation business has been featured by Peterson and Hicks (1996). As indicated by Peterson and Hicks (1996) training is imperative on account of the unavoidable changes that happen in associations. To accomplish proceeding with progress effective associations will reconstruct themselves and retrain their representatives appropriately, for example to acquire an upper hand over their rivals by further developing help quality in their inn and so forth Peterson and Hicks (1996) are likewise resolved that those associations that are effective as of now however proceed with unaltered and become self-satisfied will be in for a major shock. They contend that preparation is a constant interaction and that relationship building abilities should be ceaselessly refreshed to try not to become out of date very much like advances, which become out-dated in case improvement is not on going.

Training, in hospitality industry, basically implies showing individuals how to manage their responsibilities (Muller, Porter and Drummond) you might teach

and guide a student toward learning information (like certain realities and methods), abilities important to do the standard required, (for example, stacking the dish machine), or mentalities, (for example, client situated demeanour). Three sorts of training are required in food and housing activities: work guidance, retraining, and direction (Ting et. al, 2019). Occupation guidance is only that-guidance in what to do and how to do it in everything about a given occupation in each undertaking.

Retraining applies to current representatives. It is vital when laborers are not comparing norms, when another strategy or menu or piece of hardware is presented, or when a specialist requests it. It happens at whatever point it is required.

Direction is the underlying prologue to the work and the association. It establishes the vibe of what it resembles to work for the association and clarifies the office and the low down of days and hours and rules and approaches. It requires toward the start of the very first moment. As per Mathis (1991), successful training is a significant factor in accomplishing upper hand through HR. In the Hospitality business in general we do very little of the relative multitude of three sorts of training. Training gets ready representatives to tackle their responsibilities viably. It portrays work methodology and assists representatives with creating abilities. In hospitality industry, training incorporates the three S's-Standards, Service, and Safety (Udin et al, 2019). Training representatives on work norms implies exhibiting and giving data about: The occupation task expected of the worker in their work.

Successful help training ought to incorporate an outline of accommodation and what it makes the friendliness business unique. How visitor input is utilized as a proportion of administration. The contrast between outside clients (visitors) and inner clients (associates and different divisions) and the significance of offering support to both behaviour modelling of fitting assistance (Verevka, 2019). Wellbeing training includes training representatives how to keep up with their very own security, keep up with visitor security perceive security dangers and respond during a crisis.

Regularly the workers you are training will need to know why they are there and how the training will help them. You must assist students with seeing and see how the undertaking you are training fit into the "10,000-foot view" of their work, the division, and the property. In the event that representatives „buy in" to the training, they will be more persuaded and will at last find out more and perform better at work (Nwachukwu, 1998).

Types of training programmes in hospitality industry

There are various practices continued in various enterprises and associations. Need of training relies upon work job and authoritative prerequisites (Yusliza et. al, 2019). There are various sorts of training and development programs by various creators as follows. On job training and off the work trainings are fundamental two classifications on training types. Hands on training is representative gain proficiency with the work by doing the work really (Dessler, 2005: Sims, 2006) According to Tennanat on job training is a strategy which implies the student can learn, foster their abilities in an equivalent workplace by utilizing the gears and materials during the training (Tennanat et al, 2002).

Coles clarifies that on work is a powerful technique as representatives who are learning can apply training guidelines in genuine works and it is staying away from failing to remember what they have realized in the homeroom when return to work (Coles, 2000). Van der Klink and Streumer recommend the utilization of on work training type originates from three motivators, Training cost and advantages identified with one another, train representative in time is an obligation, positive assumption what workers figured out how to the work circumstance (Van der Klink and Streumer2002). As indicated by the Jacobs examination with respect to the on-job training cost and advantages are not good consistently Jacobs et al, (1995).

Technology based training is another training technique which is intuitive for staff. As Dessler says in PC based training staff needs to utilize the PC base or DVDs to create and build the abilities and information (Dessler, 2005). Climate of the preparation can be controlled to limit the interruption and it help to make valuable for students. As Smith clarifies that study hall training technique supportive for students, can include for novel thoughts, coaches can direct the students box the cycle with successful composed and oral relational abilities and furthermore to urge the learners to show their abilities in workplace (Smith2000).

2.4 Technology

Innovation gives another shape for our lives the manner in which we play for instance we reshape the game we play on the web, correspondence style has reshaped in to PDAs or individual advanced associates, our life arranging style from paper base schedule to computerized schedule or web access framework and furthermore our work style can change headquarters work framework utilizing PC and web, training framework at work has moved to paper adaptation to online trainings on PC based

(Arjona-Fuentes et. al, 2019). Technology is driving the world towards a new era of technological advancement and innovation in all the diverse sectors. Using technologies for working is becoming much important in the present world as it is having a positive impact on the outcomes. As indicated by Swain technology can be all over the place however to see it would be hard as it was embedded in the illustration and content. (Lover, 2005, p. 225) being familiarity with innovation implies having the option to utilize the innovation, which will be prerequisite in association.

Technologies are changing the way of working of the individuals and significantly changing the patter of learning. The ongoing technological advancement had made learning more effective and efficient. Technologies are having a remarkable impact on the society and specially on the businesses. Beyrouti, (2016) had mentioned in their study regarding the impact of technological innovation on organisations, work environment and personal lives. The study had mentioned that the technologies are leading the businesses towards better management system and effective leadership as well. The study concluded that the emerging technologies would lead the way in which the employees are hired, trained, and will change the overall working patters of the organisations and this will have a positive impact on the success of the company. It can be said that technologies are having an significant impact on the way in which the employees work in the organisation and the way in which the firm manages their employees.

Technology in training programmes

Innovation or technology is assuming a significant part in training, improvement, arranging and the executives. Technology has pushed ahead in beyond a long time from freebee manual figuring out how to mix media internet training and social learning for innovation stages. Training techniques has been changed and extended through innovation (Sadler-smith et al, 2000). As the technological advancement has changed the way in which the individuals learn new things and concepts it had also improvement the learning programs. In the context of the businesses the companies need to teach a lot of new things, concepts, and skills to their employee. Technologies are helping the organisation to make modifications in their training programs so that they can effectively train the employees.

Kumpikaite and Ciarniene, (2008) had mentioned in their study regarding the use of technologies in the training. One of the most important tasks of the management system is to focus on operating effectively with the changing environment and

continuously updating the skills and knowledge of the employees so that they can work effectively in the changing environment. If the organisations implement better technologies in the training, then it can help them in improving the skills and knowledge of the employees effectively. The training professionals and the educationalists are focusing on using the technologies which can improve and facilitates the learning process. Due to the technological advancement, e-learning had become much popular, and it is leading to significant changes in training and leaning programs.

E-learning is being widely used in the training and education for improving the quality of the learning and teaching processes. The evolution of the e-learning is having a positive impact on the personal and professional learning of the individuals. Using the technologies for learning and training is providing several opportunities to individuals such as convenience training as per the capability of the learners. Different types of technologies are being used by the organisation for training the employees. If the company is using the technology for the higher level of then it will focus on job related factors and tries to train the employees so that they can meet the needs of the company. Moreover, for the low level of learning the technologies in the training would focus on facilitating communication among the trainees and the trainers. The organisations are making use of computer-based training, multimedia for training, testing assessment and e-learning for making training effectively. The also mentioned that the organisations should strategically align the company aims and objectives with the effective leadership so that the training and development can be more successful in leading the company towards its goals.

The greater part of the organisations is utilizing the E-Learning for their training and development programs, as it is viable and productive to foster the colleagues (Maity, 2019). As Martyn Sloman clarifies association needs a successful training to accomplish the objectives and contend with their rivals. As he discloses no compelling reason to stress to acquaint the e learning with the association when individuals include to the e learning trainings then they will want to take care of their work appropriately. Innovation can offer a chance to training and development to tackle their work adequately (Sloman, 2001, p. 30). “There is no need, however, for those responsible for training to stare at the new technology like a snake at a mongoose.” (Sloman, 2001, p. 30).

Maxwell, (2012) had also mentioned in their study regarding technological advancement in the methods of training. The study had mentioned that technologies are having greater potential to offer several benefits to learning and training programs. With

the technological advancement the online learning and training market had become much popular in the entire world. The author had defined e-learning as the automation of the process of learning and training with the help of information technologies. In most of the business depends on the e-learning for training the employees and for coordinating all the different activities in the organisation. Also, the development of the computers and the networks is working as a dynamic force in training and learning processes. The study had concluded that use of online training and technologies can be used in many ways in training such as it can be a sole source of learning, a follows up to the traditional training, alternative to the traditional training and can also be a supplement for supplement to the traditional training.

Pramjeeth, et al., (2017) had mentioned in their study that the increasing technological advancement in the educational technologies had a significant impact on the training and development of the organisation. The report had mentioned that if the organisation uses better technologies for training the employees, then it can help the companies in making training more efficient, fun, accessible and convenient for the employee which is having an positive impact on the outcomes of the training programs.

As per Sloman in some point technology can be a limitation to training and advancement where individuals think it is a simple method to learn and train which thinks no compelling reason to become familiar with the hypothesis behind what they are realizing. Furthermore, this case Christian brought the expression "troublesome innovation " when association bringing the new methods and technology for training and development in to rehearse it won't be troublesome, yet mentors will likewise loathe the reality (Christensen, 1997, p. 36).

With start of web-based media associations have begun to adjust and refresh the training techniques. Adjoining advances as web recordings, online journals and online courses significant and important stage for training and development programs in mechanical world. (CIPD, 2012, p. 11). As indicated by Michelle Skelton new technology required the assistance to keep revenue in learning and improvement, as it is useful for learning and advancement. As she proceeds with the contention, if the association or doesn't screen and control it appropriately it very well may be risky. To save the documentation for effective course culmination, which is for explicit training programs needed by controllers, is a significant goal to the business. A portion of the representatives needed by the law to finish wellbeing and security instructional class, patient consideration methodology (Udin et al, 2019). Innovation assists representatives with recognizing and

track the training programs, which they have effectively finished, and to distinguish what training openings are accessible for them or impending. Innovation assumes a part in training to decrease the preparation cost and it help to administrators to follow the training programs, which can diminish the repetition cost. When the representative completion their trainings post training assessment plays become most significant part as innovation can assume a major part on it. Through the post training assessment can assess the staff has the proper information after the trainings. Shelagh (Dillon, 2014) additionally states “Training in a real classroom or group environment with a trainer cannot be entirely replaced by automated or distance courses. By working personally with trainees in smaller groups, the trainer is better able to establish whether the training is proving effective.”

The organisations operating in diverse industries needs to understand that the using the technologies in the using the technologies for the training purpose will provide them several benefits. Better training is having a direct impact on the performance of the employees of the organisation and having an impact on the overall performance and productivity of the company. If the technologies are properly used in the training programs, then it can help the employees to fit appropriately in the job roles and allows them to deliver high quality work to the company. Alves, et al., (2017) had mentioned in their study regarding the relation between the technology and training. The study had mentioned that when technologies are being used in the education and training sector then it is having a positive impact on the interactive relationship among the trainees and the trainer which leads to better understanding and learning.

The companies need to develop an environment in the organisation which can lead to the positive impact on the attitude of the individuals regarding using the technologies for training the employees. If the organisation culture supports, the use of technologies in training and is having proper knowledge regarding how to use the technologies for training the employees then it can lead to better outcomes. The organisations need to focus on all the pros and cons of using technologies for training purposes. One of the most important benefit of using the technologies for training is that it reduces the extra cost of conducting the trainings and instead of it help the company in providing training to the employees in a cost-effective manner.

E-learning is majorly used for training the employees in different organisation operating across the globe. Cazamecka and Dardczi, (2017) had mentioned in their study on e-learning as a method of employee’s development and training. The research study mentioned that the companies are focusing more on the employees in the present

world as the human resource is most important resource for the organisations. It is important for the organisations to focus on the professional development of the employees working in the firm. The quality and effectiveness of the training which is being provided to the employees is having an impact on their performance in the company and the overall professional development as well.

The development of better technologies such as e-learning had developed an opportunity for the businesses to use the technologies for making training more effective. E-learning offers the assess to use the technologies such as texts, images, videos and virtual rooms for providing training to the employees. The use of e-learning for training the employees is providing several advantages to the organisations such as:

- Reducing the cost of learning and training of employees.
- Offering great flexibility to the trainees and avoiding the lack of trainers.
- Standardization of the knowledge and improving the quality of training.
- Providing greater flexibility to the human resource department in providing better training to the employees.
- Enhancing communication among the stakeholders of training which is making the information sharing more convenient.

Apart from these advantages it is having a positive impact on the outcomes of the training programs and benefiting all the stakeholders of the training programs. Although there are several limitations are also associated with the use of technologies in training but in the changing world it has become essential to use the technologies for training for increasing the efficiency and effectiveness of the training programs. Several studies had mentioned that offering online training programs to the employees can help the companies in retaining the employees and developed better skilled, motivates and productive workforce which is essential for the success and development of the organisations. Along with this it is also discussed that the companies are investing an higher amount of capital in transportation and housing of the trainees instead of investing the money in the actual training programs. The researchers had mentioned in their study that using technologies for training provide both cost saving and time saving benefits to the organisations.

Modern training methods are mainly focusing on the changing world by paying attention on the globalisation, technological advancements, privatisation and increasing competition and on focusing on all this it had become essential for the organisations to make use of technologies for training. With the changing lifestyles using the modern technologies provide access to better training programs which focus on the concepts

such as just in time tools, self-paced online learning and learning on demand. It can be said that using the technologies in training is offering several benefits to the businesses and with the changing world it had become essential for the business to shift from the traditional training methods to the modern training methods which are using the technologies for training the employees.

Training technologies in hospitality industry

Technological advancement in the teaching and learning processes had gained a lot of importance in the present world and due to which the businesses operating in diverse industries had started using the technologies for training the employees. Similar to all other industries hospitality industry is also using technology for training the employees. For hospitality service providing organisations it is essential to have highly trained employees which can deliver high quality service to the customers. Hospitality sector is the fastest growing sector, and it is a people-oriented sector due to which in this sector the training needs to be much effective. New technologies had led to the development of new tools which can be used by the organisations for training the employees.

Batla, (2008) had mentioned in their study about the new technologies which are being used for providing training to the employees of hospitality sector. The study had mentioned that due to the technological advancement a major part of the hospitality businesses is shifting towards online and due to which it had become important for the adopt the changing training mediums so that the employees can be trained in an effective manner. The organisations operating in the hospitality industry had started using the internet tutorial system for training the employees. Both the new hired and existing employees are being trained by using this system. The companies are using elearning and internet tutorial system for training the employees and focusing on online assignment, training videos, online guidelines for training the employees.

Kizildag and Kim, (2010) had mentioned about the changing technologies in the training system of the hospitality industry. The study had mentioned that the tools and techniques which are being used for training the employees are having great impact on the effectiveness of the training programmes, so the companies need to use the best technology. The tools and techniques which are being used for training the employees in the hospitality sector had drastically changes over the last decades. The study had mentioned that the hospitality companies are using the information technology in a systematic and strategical manner for training the employees. As the mobile networks and portable devices are becoming more popular the organisations had started using the mobile learning (M-learning).

Using the M-learning is offering training to the employees with accessible learning resources, effective interaction anytime, strong searching capacity and easy access as per the time. The study had mentioned that the use of m-learning is providing better opportunities to both the trainers and trainees to interact effectively and access the educational material independent of the time and space. Moreover, using this technology is helping the hospitality sector in training the employees effectively and enhancing their performance and quality of service. Electronic learning has become a type of training in the hospitality industry. Using the electronic is bringing significant change in the way the employee develops their skills and knowledge for delivering better service to the customers.

According to Berge (2008) training is the action of teaching through instructions, that goals and expectations can be reached through the process of focusing on skills and knowledge. Romanova, et al., (2016) had mentioned in their study that hospitality industry is a competitive industry, and it is important for the organisations operating in this sector to effectively focus on the improvement of the performance of the employees. It can be said that if the organisation uses the tools and techniques as per the changing world then they can deliver better training to the employees and can improve the performance of the employees. Moreover, using technologies for training purpose is much effective and efficient as compared to the traditional system of training, so the organisations of hospitality sector should use better technologies for training purpose.

2.5 The Case Company: Mitchell and Butler

Mitchell and Butler are one of the largest hospitality company in the UK; the cited company is having a larger number of restaurants, pubs and bars and the organisation is serving a wide range of eating and drinking choices to their customers. The company is focusing on offering a wide range of quality food and drink to the customers and fast and friendly services to the customers. The company is working on its aim of bringing innovation, listening to the customer's feedback, and working on it. Along with this, the company is focusing on having passionate staff and providing them the best training so that they can work effectively in the organisation.

The cited company is focusing on investing a large amount of capital on the training of the employees so that they can be trained effectively. The company is using better technologies and advanced tools so that they can provide better- and high-quality training to their employees. Using better technology and high-quality training to the

employees is providing benefits to the company such as a significant increase in the employee retention and creating a highly trained workforce which can deliver quality services to the customers. Mitchell and Butler are focusing on attracting the most talented candidates belonging to the best universities.

Along with investing in attracting talented candidates, then the company is also focusing on providing them with high-quality training with greater efficiency and effectiveness. The company is providing an innovative training program for training employees. Mitchell and Butler rank among one of the best companies of the UK which are providing the best job training to the employees. The company is using technological advancement to the fullest and using Mable training for the employees training. MABLE stands for Mitchells and Butlers learning environment, which is an online training program developed by Mitchell and Butler for effectively training the employees. Mable is a system of learning which is completely based on online learning approach. This system is providing support to the employees by learning as per their needs, and it engages the employees effectively in the training program and giving remarkable outcomes to the cited company.

Using the technologically advanced approach and techniques for training the employees is providing benefits to the company. The learners mentioned that using the Mable for training is proving them excellent experience is helping them in learning the concepts in an effective and appropriate manner. The quality of the services which is being offered by the Mitchell and Butler had increased remarkable, and this tool is continuously helping the cited company to train the employees effectively. Using better technologies and the technologically advanced tool is the focus of the company so that they can provide the best experience to their customers. The engagement level of the employees is higher as the company is providing better training to the employees. Using better technologies in training and highly trained employees of Mitchell and Butler are helping the company in maintaining a better position in the hospitality industry of the UK.

Summary

The writing explored the training and development programs, effectiveness of the training and development, innovation, technology, and utilization of technology in training and development programmes, and how the training and improvement functions in hospitality industry. Considered have discovered that training and advancement work on representative's abilities and information and furthermore make them certainty to their work job. Training and development make a solid supervisory

group to foster their group in a powerful way. As there were numerous trainings and improvement techniques investigations have discovered that technology assumes a significant part in training and development in hospitality industry just as all enterprises.

The literature review had also mentioned about the different challenges which are being faced by the organisation in providing effective training to the employees and gaining better outcomes from the training programs. The discussion had suggested that the factors such as organisational culture, employee job satisfaction, communication in the workforce and several other factors are also having an impact on the training programs. Later on, the discussion had mentioned about the solutions which are being faced by the organisations while providing training to the employees.

Also, the review of literature discusses the about the use of technologies in training the employees of hospitality industry and how the organisations are using elearning and modern tools and techniques for providing effective and efficient training to the employees. Training and development in hospitality industry is most significant job to get compelling and productivity administration. Assessing the training and advancement programs assists with understanding the adequacy of the training programs, distinguish the shortcomings and qualities. In this examination have explored about Kirk Patrick models and CIRO model to comprehend the viability of training and development. The usefulness of technology training and development is firmly understood and appreciated. The literature suggests that using the technologies in the training provides several benefits to the company and leads to better development of skills and knowledge of the employees. Moreover, it can be said that organisations of hospitality industry should focus on using the latest technologies for training the employees so that better outcomes can be obtained.

At the end of the literature review, researcher was able to cover wide area through information. the chapter 03 is explained about research methodology which evaluates validity and reliability of research.

03. CHAPTER THREE:
RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter explains about validity and reliability of the data. And this is the precise method to identify, select, process, analyse the information about the relevant research topic.

3.0 Introduction

“Methodology is the analytical framework within which the research is conducted or the foundation upon which the research is based” (Brown, 2006).

Lgwenagu, (2016) had mentioned in his study that research methodology is a set of systematic techniques which are being used by the researcher for conducting the research. In general term the author defined that research methodology is a guide which helps the researcher while conducting research. In this study the research had also mentioned about the advantages of research methodology for the research study which includes advantages such as:

- It helps in developing a critical and scientific attitude among the researcher which is required for making the observations more accurate.
- It also enriches the research process and increases the chances for the in depth research study which helps in understanding the aims and objectives of the research in an effective manner.
- Develops the ability to use the results of the study confidently and promotes better decision making in the context of the research study.
- Enhances the ability to think critically and inculcates the ability to read and learn the different concepts effectively which are important for a better research study.
- It enhances the ability of the researcher to conduct and well structures and appropriate research in his/her upcoming future.

In this study the researcher had also mentioned about the different types of research which includes action research, creative research, descriptive research, experimental research, ex-post facto research, expository research and historical research. This research varies from each other based on the research methodology which is being used for conducting the research. Types of researchers are briefly explained below such as:

- Descriptive research: it's a type of research in which the researcher focuses on the case study or the situation for conducting the research.
- Experimental research: in these types of research its aim is to identify the variables of interest for which the research is being conducted.

- Creative research: these types of research focus on development of new theories and concepts and new inventions.
- Action research: these types of researchers focus on implanting recommended changes to the research.
- Historical research: these types of research focus on using the previous events for examining the current situations which can also help in future predictions.
- Expository research: these type of research focuses on the using the existing information and these researchers are generally the review reports.

Goundar, (2012) had also mentioned in their study that research methodology is a systematic way the research can be solved, or it is defined as the methods which are used for carrying out research. In this study the researcher had mentioned that research methodology helps in collecting samples, conducting systematic research, and drawing solution to a problem.

As indicated by Kothari (2005), the use of logical techniques joined with exploration should assist the peruse with finding the secret truth. The methodology produces results of studies and pick the right technique to direct the examination adequately to meet the scientist's points and goals of the exploration.

The research methodology continued in this exposition presents themes on various types of exploration which are used to track down the best methodology and strategy in this investigation (Book and Kim, 2019). Aims and objectives of thesis is in Chapter 1 hence the motivation behind this part is to:

- Introduce research philosophy corresponding to embraced approach in this investigation
- Discuss research strategy clarified in ebb and flow study, including the methodology
- Present the instruments of exploration technique which were created and used in the accomplishment of the scientist' objectives
- Explain why the particular methods were used in connection with data collection and considering limitations about the introduced research

Further, the part talks about the issues followed as: research philosophy; research approaches; research plan; information assortment strategy; information examination; data reliability and restrictions or limitations of research.

3.1 RESEARCH PHILOSOPHY

Research philosophy is referred as a belief regarding the way which is being used by the researcher while conducting the research which includes the ways in which the data is being collected, analysed, and used in the research. While conducting the research the researcher can use different philosophies for conducting the research. Mainly four types of research philosophies are present such as pragmatism, positivism, realism and interpretivism. According to Saunders et al, (2012) research philosophy refers to how the development of knowledge on the study and the subject and the nature of how knowledge is pertinent to the research study. Further explanations of main philosophies there are two main philosophies such as positivism and interpretivism, besides pragmatic philosophies too.

Basically, four sorts of research philosophies are sober pragmatism, positivism, realism and interpretivism. As per Saunders et al, (2012) research reasoning alludes to how the advancement of information on the examination and the subject and furthermore the idea of how information is relevant to the exploration study. Further clarifications of primary methods of reasoning there are two principal ways of thinking like positivism and interpretivism, other than pragmatic philosophies as well.

As per Proctor (2005), all scholarly exploration ought to be created insightfully. Exploration ought to be followed with a technique for study expounded to more likely clarify and work with the investigation of the subject. Taking a gander at this unique circumstance, the philosophical methodology gives structure of the exploration as per its setup, essential proof, assembling the information and the method of its translation to give the right responses to the research questions (Soon, 2020). The research begins with its initial step which is the meaning of the philosophical technique for research that should be inspected. There are a few unique methodologies of exploration theory, like positivism, phenomenology, and authenticity. (Saunders et. al., 2003). It is important that each approach sets hypotheses and various methodological implications according to its position and the brief description of the characteristics of each research philosophy will be interpreted below.

Andriukaitiene, et al., (2018) had mentioned in their study that research philosophy is method which is being used by the researcher for generating the ideas into

the knowledge in the context of research studies. This study had mentioned about the different research philosophy. Two main types of research philosophy are positivism and interpretivism, according to the positivism research philosophy the social world can be explained in an objective context. On the other hand, interpretivism mentions that on the basis of the principles it is not easy to understand the social world with an objective. Moreover, the pragmatism mentions that the research philosophy is based on the research problem so the researcher should focus on identifying the philosophy which suits well to the research question and then apply it in the research. The different types of research philosophies are mentioned below.

Positivism

According to this research philosophy the actual knowledge is what had gained from the facts and figures which have being gained through measurements and observations. The research which follows this approach needs to focus on data collection and interpretation of the data for extracting useful information for the research. Positivism depends on the quantifiable observations so that further statistical analysis can be applied on the research for drawing conclusions of the research. This research philosophy is based on some principles which are mentioned below such as:

- According to this philosophy the research should focus on explaining
- This philosophy believes in the concept that the researcher's common sense should not make him/her biased while conducting the research and should not have an impact on the research findings.
- The research should be based on the logics and concepts.
- The researcher should try to develop a hypothesis so that it can be tested in the research.

Also, Ryan, (2018) had discussed in his study that positivism is a philosophy which believes that the knowledge which is being used in the research or have been found in the research should be objective and should be free from bias which means that it should not be based on the ideas and thoughts of the researcher. According to Currie (2003), the positivist methodology creates general guidelines and standards utilizing the efficient procedures of logical strategy. The positivist methodology starts with problem, thought or perception as it is the initial step related with this way of thinking. Following this way of approach, the researcher analyses the facts and objectives of the study in order to create the logical method of thinking to explain the subject of the study. Following this method of approach, the scientist examines current realities and goals of the investigation to make the legitimate strategy for speculation to clarify the subject of

the examination. As per Newman (2005) this methodology depends on a quantitative examination. Expectation of forthcoming conduct is utilized in the positivist methodology by creating general laws from the point of view of target truth (Fisher, 2004). Considering analyst's conviction on exact and esteem free information, this methodology decides individuals and their activity to be concentrated as equitably as the piece of the regular world.

Madafg, (2017) had mentioned in their article about several advantages and disadvantages of using positivism philosophy in the research. Positivism is better as it allows value freedom, it is representative, it can be generalising, it only focuses on the objective data, and it is quite reliable. On the other hand, the disadvantages associated with using this philosophy includes that it is having low validity and does not provide in depth data regarding the research. Apart from this other advantage associated with the use of positivism philosophy is that it relies on the quantitative data which is more reliable as compared to the qualitative research. Along with this it is more scientific which makes it more trustworthy. Moreover, the positivism focuses on a well-defined structure for conducting research which is having a positive impact on the quality of the research. Hence it can be said that using positivism can help the researcher in conducting more accurate research.

Interpretivism

In interpretivism research philosophy it states that the research should be based on the interest of the researcher so that an outcome depending on it can be obtained by the researcher. The development of the interpretivism had being forced by the critiques of positivism. This philosophy is associated with the philosophical concepts of idealism and this approach is also used for grouping different types of other approaches such as social constructivism, hermeneutics, and phenomenology. Interpretivism mentions that it is important in the research that the social character of the researcher should play a significant role in the research, and it also appreciates the individual differences.

One of the best advantages of using the interpretivism is that it is based on the qualitative research which makes it more reliable and at focuses on the cross-cultural differences among the organisations, ethical issues, impact of leadership and all the different factors can be studied in depth. If the researcher is using an interpretivism research philosophy, then it will help them in conducting in-depth research. On the other hand, one of the biggest disadvantages of using this approach is that as this approach involves the researcher itself than it increases the risk of bias can be involved in the

research by the researcher's side. Different frameworks of interpretivism is also present which can be opted by the researcher while conducting the research.

(Fisher 2004). Phenomenology is a research philosophy which focuses on the experiences and events which pay least focuses on the external and physical reality. Several advantages of using this type of research philosophy are that it enables the researcher to focus on all the changing process over time and it also promotes better contribution to development of new theories.

Hermeneutics is a type of methodology for interpretation which focuses on the interpretivism research philosophy. This type of interpretation pay concern on solving the issues which arises due to the meaningful human actions. This approach is basically used for the creating a bridge between the mindsets of the research and the mindset of the biblical writer by providing the knowledge of languages, comparison among the scripture with another scripture and previous history. Moreover, Social Constructivism is also a type of interpretive framework which is being used by the researchers when they are implementing an interpretivism research philosophy in the research.

Pragmatism is a research philosophy which is based on the concept that the concepts and strategies which are being used in the research should not only focus on a specific method instead of it the researcher should focus on using the combination of the things which can help them in addressing the issue in an appropriate manner. This approach believes that single viewpoint is not enough to give an entire picture of all the concepts which are having an impact on the research topics. The research questions are having a remarkable impact on the ways in which the research analysis the different things and choices an appropriate research method and design for conducting the research. If the researcher is using this research philosophy, then they can be both inductive and deductive research approach and both subjective and objective viewpoints. In the research if the researcher is using a pragmatic research philosophy is used in the research, then combination of both positivism and interpretivism can be used in a single research on the basis of the research question for conducting an indepth research. One of the best advantages of this research is that it helps the researcher in conducting a better and quality research as it is using mixture of approaches and research methods.

Quantitative information assortment measures are for the most part utilized in this research, yet qualitative data also will be gathered to develop the degree of connection between factors. Along these lines, Pragmatism as an examination philosophical point of view is utilized analytically: Here the analyst hopes to utilize

Pragmatism as the specialist is intending to utilize the blended strategy for information assortment (Patiar et. al, 2021). In view of the three unique kinds of research methods of reasoning, this exploration followed phenomenology approach with the targets of the exploration project. Created on this methodology, analysts had the option to characterize the idea of the issue being explored and to improve comprehension of the climate inside the issue. Usage of phenomenology approach provided a comprehensive description of the main aim of the research referring to the importance of training and development in the hospitality industry. In the present research study, the researcher is using phenomenology and the pragmatism in this research study. The research is using pragmatism which will help him a lot in implementing the combination so methods and strategies which can provide better and in-depth knowledge regarding the research questions.

3.2 RESEARCH APPROACH

Research approach is defined as the different plans and procedures which are being used by the researcher in conducting the research. It consists of all the steps which are includes in data collection, analysis, and interpretation of the information relevant to the research study. Grover, (2015) had described in their study that the research approach is interconnected with the research design, research methods and the philosophical viewpoint.

The entire research approach is divided into two categories which are the approach of data collection and the approach of data analysis. Both these approaches play a significant role in the research and due to which it is important for the researcher to choose an appropriate research approach for the research. The researcher can use qualitative or quantitative method for collecting the data and can also use both inductive and deductive approach for analysing the data. The research approach can be broadly classified into three different types such as deductive research approach, inductive research approach and abductive research approach.

Inductive research approach is a type of research approach according to which the researcher should focus on the research questions, its aims and objectives while conducting the research and should try to receive the results. When the researcher is focusing on the qualitative research and qualitative data collection methods than inductive approach is used for analysing the data. The researchers in which the

qualitative data collection approach and inductive data analysis approach is being used then it generally focuses on the secondary data. When the inductive approach is applied in the research then in the beginning it is not important to develop the hypothesis instead of it the researcher should focus on the reasoning and the researcher also focus on collecting the data which can help them in identifying the relationships among the studies so that theories regarding the research can be build.

While applying the inductive research approach the researcher should focus on combination of the secondary data which is being collected from the previous research studies. Along with this in inductive research it tries to create a link between the research aim and objectives with the results of the raw data which is being extracted from the secondary data collection methods. In inductive approach the hypothesis is not being developed and tested but instead of it the data analysis methods are being used for analysing the qualitative data. Thematic analysis is one of the most popular analysis, which is used in the inductive approach, as it helps the researcher in providing detail understanding of the research topic.

On the other hand, when the researcher is focusing on the qualitative data collection approach then deductive approach is used for analysing the data. A deductive research approach focuses on development of the hypothesis based on the theories which is being tested in the research and the results are being obtained in the research. In general terms it can be said that the deductive approach concern with deducting the conclusions for known premises. Using the deductive approach provides several advantages such as it provides the advantages to measure the concepts quantitatively, allows the researcher to generalise the research findings and explains the relationships among the concepts and the variables associated with the research questions. When the researcher is using the deductive research approach then several stages are including in it which includes deducing the hypothesis, formulation of hypothesis, testing of hypothesis, examination of the outcomes and the modification of the theory.

Sallem and Burney, (2008) had mentioned in their study regarding the research approaches. According to this study the deductive research approach works from generalise to the specific system, it means that in deductive approach starts with a broader context and then focuses specifically on the research topic. On the other hand, the inductive research works opposite to that of the deductive approach. Inductive research approach moves from the specific observations to the broader context. The research can implement any of the research approach based on their research strategy, design, and process.

As per Sekaran and Bougie, inductive and deductive methodologies are two fundamental exploration draws near (Sekaran and Bougie 2010). Basically, in the inductive methodology specialist would start the exploration with gathering information to develop a hypothesis. On the other hand, the deductive methodology starts with earlier broad speculations and analysts will use by placing these hypotheses into a particular case. As per Saunders quantitative explores are associated with deductive methodologies Saunders et al, (2012).

It is significant that some subjective exploration will begin with the deductive methodology, meaning to rest a current hypothesis utilizing the subjective information gathered through an examination. Likewise, generally the subjective explores will utilize adductive and deductive methodologies, where inductive derivations are created and will test existing guidelines separately (Yin, 2009). In this examination it will essentially utilize the inductive methodology, as there is no standard hypothesis to test the connection between research factors.

Different authors had defined and explained the inductive and deductive research approach, but the researcher should focus on selecting an appropriate research study which can suit well to the research aims and objectives. In this present research the researcher had develop the hypothesis which are being tested in the research, hence the researcher is implementing the deductive research approach in the dissertation. In the present dissertation the researcher is focusing on deducing the unknown premises. When the research is focusing on the case study then both the inductive and deductive research approach can be used by the researcher buy in the present research as the researcher is focusing on conducting qualitative research due to which using a deductive approach would be the best for this research.

3.3 RESEARCH DESIGN

Research design refers to the framework which is being used by the researcher for integrating the different components of the research which includes research methods and techniques. It is important for the researcher to select an appropriate research design for a successful research study. There are four different characteristics of the research design. Neutrality is one of the most important characteristics of the research design so it is essential that the research design should not be biased. Also, if the research design would be reliable then only the researcher would be able to reach at the expected results from the research study. Validity of the research design is also

essential so that the results of the research would be valid for a longer period. Along with this the research design should focus on the idea of generalisations so that the results drawn from the study can be applied to the population and should not only restrict to the sample which is being used in the research study. When the researcher is implementing any of the research design then it is important that it should have some elements such as methods of research analysis, timeline, analysis methods, probable objectives for conducting the research study, data collection methods and type of research methodology.

The researcher needs to understand the various types of research designs for selecting an appropriate research design so that a better one can be chosen for their research study. The research designs are broadly classified into the qualitative and quantitative research design. Qualitative research design tries to determine the relationships between the data, which is collected, and the observations based on the mathematical calculations. When the research implements the qualitative research then the research would answer the questions such as why and how the theories exists and what are the reasons behind these concepts. On the other hand, the quantitative research design is generally used for the studies in which statistical conclusions are being drawn for the research. Quantitative research design is more effective as they provide the results of the research in the numbers which make it more reliable.

Both the qualitative and quantitative research designs are furthermore categories into different types of research designs which are mentioned below such as: •
Descriptive Research Design: in this type of research design the researcher aims at describing the case or the situation which is being studied in the research study. It is categorised as a theory-based research design which

focuses on collecting, analysing, and representing the information which is being gathered.

- Exploratory Research Design: this type of research design is being implemented in the study in which no further research had being conducted in the context of the research questions. Also, these type of research does not focus on providing any kind of final or fix answer from the research, but it tries to explore the research topic in detail.
- Experimental Research Design: this research design focuses on creating a relationship among the independent and dependent variables of the research study. These types of research try to identify the impact of the independent

variables on the dependent variables of the study. This research approach is practical as it provides knowledge for solving the problem.

- Correlational Research Design: this type of research design is used by the researcher for establishing a relationship among the connected variables. The research in which this research design is used usually focuses on statistical analysis for calculating and determining the relationships among the two variables.
- Diagnostic Research Design: in this type of research design the researcher tries to identify the cause of the phenomenon on which the research is based upon. These types of research are generally having three different stages such as inception of the issue, diagnosis of the issue and solution of the issue.
- Explanatory Research Design: this type of research design is used for the research in which the aim of the research is to explore and explain the ideas and theories related to the research questions.

It is important for the researcher to select an appropriate research design for conducting an effective and well-structured research. It is significant for the analyst to choose a proper exploration plan for directing a successful and very much organized examination (Dwesini, 2019). The exploration configuration is utilized to address the examination questions, which were thought about in this research. The examination configuration shows up from questions straightforwardly deciding the primary objectives being examined in this proposition. Yin (2003) states that exploration configuration is a reliable component for an examination project assisting the specialist with choosing what inquiries to contemplate, which data are applicable to the current contextual investigation, how to gather information and to do investigation of introduced discoveries. In the perspective on Saunders et al. (2003), there are three different kinds of examination plan like Exploratory, Descriptive, Explanatory. Exploratory examination is developed to reply "what" questions, as per Yin (2003), and much of the time incorporates new investigations, which can be consequence of the presence of new marvels or deficient information regarding the matter of any investigation. This methodology is additionally prescribed to support scientists' goals by acquiring new experiences about explicit issue, which fit well and present a decent match to this exploration. Saunders et. al (2003) states use of this methodology particularly for understanding the issue communicating the principal steps to direct an exploratory examination: looking and considering the writing and conversing with specialists in the subject through interviews (Daghfous and Belkhodja, 2019). This idea is portrayed as

adaptable and versatile to everyday changes as aftereffect of new data forthcoming or new theory showing up.

In the present research study as the researcher is trying to explore about the case study so that they can provide a detailed discussion of the research topics. In this research study the researcher is using the exploratory research design for conducting the research. Using this research design allow the researcher to be more flexible and adaptive to changes which helps the researcher to explore all the concepts associated with the research question in detail. Along with this using this research design also leads to develop of several research topics which are related with the current research topic as it explores all the different concepts in detail. As this examination base on the hospitality business in the UK, specialists are hoping to utilize the Mitchells and Butlers bar and eatery network as a contextual analysis (Patiar et. al, 2021). Mitchells and Butlers Company has 1700 bars and restaurants all around the UK with various brand names in addition to premium help. Specialists are hoping to have semi-structured interviews with top management in the human asset office just as the learning and improvement division in Mitchells and Butlers to gather data and the information. Simultaneously analysts will utilize organization reports and information as auxiliary information to assess the viability of current preparing and improvement programs (Dashper, 2020).

Through utilizing the semi structured interviews specialist will see what the training programs are accessible for mid degree of representatives and will unveil the utilization of innovation on those training programs. Researcher is intending to assemble data concerning what are the progressions occurring inside the organization with respect training and development programs. What were the accessible instruments and projects inside 10 years? How the Technology upgraded the training and development programs. Simultaneously Researcher is hoping to do the assessor with sending the questioners via emails to the management level staff. Analysts will utilize open-finished and close ended questions to convey the assessor.

As indicated by Saunders et. al. (2003), generally reasonable and valuable for new examinations is that of exploratory exploration plan which gives a critical commitment to the comprehension of the aftereffects of the primary subject. Along these lines, this examination is of an exploratory nature and the exploratory exploration was created to characterize the nature training and development programs in the hospitality business and clarify and explain the comprehension of use and viability of training and development in the cordiality business in the UK. The analyst of the

introduced issue needed to investigate the discoveries with the hypothesis communicated in writing audit and had the option to give the idea and suggestion to the organization or different organizations in the cordiality business and future imminent through exploratory examination plan, which is momentarily introduced (Anderson and Sanga, 2019).

3.4 RESEARCH STRATEGY

Research strategy is defined as the step-by-step actions which are being taken by the researcher while conducting research. In methodically structured research project, the research strategy usually uses to generalize identified research problems or the research issue. Research Strategy mainly focuses on the data collection methodologies in the research process (Franklin 2012). Choosing the best strategy for the dissertation or a research study is important for the researcher. It is important for the researcher to explain the research design strategy which is being implemented by him in his research. The researcher needs to understand all the different types of research strategies so that they can select an appropriate research strategy on the basis of their research methodology and the research questions as well. As Saunders likewise clarifies research techniques rely upon philosophy of the examination as it is quantitative or subjective exploration (Saunders 2012). Be that as it may, in this examination the specialist hopes to utilize both qualitative and quantitative techniques and to foster a scientific and more obvious end result on the issue, and to quantify the level of the relationship in a numerical translation. The analyst is relied upon to execute the two-information assortment strategies; primary and secondary

Most common type of research strategies includes case studies, surveys, interviews and action research or action-oriented research. These research strategies have been discussed in detail such as:

- **Case Study:** in this type of research strategy the researcher focuses on the in-depth investigation by focusing on the single case or a situation or it can also focus on the small numbers of diverse cases. In the case study research, the data is being collected by the researcher is gathered from different sources such as observations interviews, surveys, and document analysis. In case study research the researcher is having an opportunity to conduct detailed research and can investigate the issue appropriately. Generally, case study researchers are descriptive and uses the qualitative method for the research.

- Survey: generally, the survey is used in the researcher which focuses on social context and in social science research and market research as well. In this type of research study, the researcher collects qualitative or quantitative data by using the open-ended questions. Data which is being collected in the research needs to be analysed effectively so that the results can be obtained for the research questions. Using this strategy can help the research in being flexible as the survey can collect wide range of information from small or large population or sample size.
- Interviews: in this type of research strategy the research conducts interviews with one or more peoples to gather useful information in the context of the research study. Interviews are quite flexible and are usually divided into three diverse types based on the degree to which they are structured such as structured, semi-structured and unstructured. Conducting an interview requires extensive planning which include the development of the structure, selecting the individuals for the interview and the person who will conduct the interview, deciding that whether the interview would be group interview or personal interview and the ways how the data is being recorded and analysing them.
- Action Oriented Research: these types of research directly focus on directing changing in the practical business by recommending the changes. This research is a type of participatory process which aims at bringing the theories, practice, actions and reflections. Using this type of research strategy is not a task as it is a complex approach to use. The researcher who uses this research strategy needs to be highly skills and having great knowledge about the research studies, so that they can conduct an effective action research. Action research are also known as participatory research, and it requires the collaborative inquiry which can be used as a process of research for drawing the conclusions for the research.

The above-mentioned discussion is of the research strategies which can be used by the research while conducting the research. In the present research study, the researcher is focusing on a case study of a hospitality service providing organisation and for this the research is being conducted. Along with using the case study the researcher will also focus on the interviews for collecting the information regarding the research topic. Using the case study research strategy will provide several benefits to

the researcher such as it will provide them detailed information regarding the research topic and also provide an insight for further research.

Moreover, while using the case study the research is also focusing on conducting a semi-structured interview which will add value to the research by providing them additional benefits. This strategy will provide benefit to the researcher by encouraging the two-way communication in the research study and it also creates opportunities for the researcher to understand the reasons behind the answers of the interviewees. Using this research strategy will help the research in conducting quality research.

3.5 RESEARCH METHOD

Research methods refer to the distinctive manners by which information can be gathered and broke down (Collis and Hussey, 2003). The examination included the assortment of both primary data and secondary information, being data. The entire research is based on the research method which is being chosen by the researcher before conducting the research. There are two types of research methods such as qualitative research method and quantitative research methods. The qualitative research methods focus on the conducting in-depth interviews and reviews the different types of documents which can help in gathering the detail information regarding the research topic. On the basis of the information which is being collected the researcher develops several themes which are based on the research topics. On the other hand, the quantitative research method focuses on the surveys, observations, reviews of the records, structured interviews and the analysing the documents which are having an numerical information which is required in the research. Both the research methods are quite diverse, some of the differences among the qualitative research method and quantitative research methods are discussed such as:

- The qualitative research is text bases on the other hand the quantitative research is based on the numbers.
- For analysing the data of qualitative research statistical methods are not applied on the other hand the data of quantitative requires to be analysed by the statistical methods.
- Qualitative research depends on the skills of the researcher on the other hand quantitative research is depended on the measurements and the instruments which are used for collecting and analysing the tools.

- The data which is collected by the qualitative research is less generalizable on the other hand the data which is gathered from the quantitative research can be applied to a larger population i.e., it is more generalizable.

Moreover, both the qualitative and quantitative research methods are explained in detail also. Quantitative exploration is a conventional goal (Bums and Grove, 1991). Exploration can be characterized as the quest for information, or as any orderly examination, with a receptive outlook, to build up realities, tackle new or existing issues, demonstrate ground-breaking thoughts, or foster new hypotheses.

This thesis deals with single case study in order to provide a general understanding of phenomena using a particular case. Mitchells and Butlers Company has selected as a case study as it is one of the largest restaurants and pub chain in which has got 1700 branches across UK. Random sampling will be used in this research to collect data and sample will be randomly selected 100 to 150 management level of employees over 1700 businesses. As indicated by Shankar, (2008) auxiliary information can be utilized to uncover significant hypothetical base proof those can sustain the examination. As analyst is doing semi structured interviews and overview polls, semi organized meetings with top management in learning and development will come out ahead of the pack of the information assortment measure (Dwesini, 2019). As analyst is hoping to assemble the data in regard to what are the accessible training and development programs for mid degree of representatives and utilization of technology in preparing projects to compose the presentation and write the introduction and literature, that information should get from top management from human asset division. Then, at that point furthermore assembling the data and auxiliary information from similar meetings (Daghfous and Belkhodja, 2019).

Finally moving to gather the quantitative data through questionnaire surveyor from management level of employee in Mitchel and butlers. Researcher has decided to choose management level of employees as sample of this research. They are the people who have already got more experiences regarding the training and development programmes as well as training and development tools. As they need to complete those training programmes to sign off as managers management level of employee has got more experience regarding training and development programmes. They have experienced how the technology impacted on training programmes through their journey.

Aside from the distributed writing utilized in the exploration auxiliary information will be gathered principally through interior records of Mitchell and Butler

and furthermore some other web electronic materials those are accessible comparable to the examination subject (Otoo, 2019). This information can be administrative hierarchical materials, neighbourliness mechanical reports.

3.6 DATA COLLECTION METHOD

Data collection refers to the process which is being used by the researcher for collecting the important information from all the sources available which can help them in answering the research questions, testing the hypothesis and evaluating the outcomes of the research study as well. It is important for the researcher to select a better data collection method. The data collection method should be chosen by the researcher based on the research questions and the way in the researcher wants to conduct the research. The data collection methods are divided into two categories such as: secondary data collection and primary data collection.

In general context the secondary data collection methods refers to the method of collecting the data from the information which is already present in the exiting literature such as books, journals, online portals, magazines, newspapers, and all other sources which provide the information of the existing literature. On the other hand, the primary data collection methods refer to the data collection method in which the research itself conduct the interviews, surveys, and observations for collecting the primary data. It is essential for the researcher to have proper knowledge regarding the data collection methods.

Primary data are recognized information those will straightforwardly be applicable to the exploration and will additionally give more engaged and properly important data and confirmations (Ma, 2020). As indicated by Barzun there are two kinds of perceptions to gather the essential information like member perception and organized perception (Barzun 2000). Directing semi-organized meetings and review surveys are the fundamental two techniques gather the essential information. As Ritchie and Lewis clarify semi-organized meeting is a quantitative examination technique (Ritchie and Lewis (2003). Poll is related with quantitative information, which is gathering information from bigger example (Saunders et al, 2012).

Primary data alludes to assortment of information by analysts utilizing the different strategies and methods like meetings, interviews, questionnaires perceptions, and examinations to accumulate the most important information fundamental for specialists' undertaking (Blayney and Young, 2020). The interview was carried out by contacting the recruited participants. They were contacted by the researcher through

various means and were explained the role and importance of the research study. Participants were provided with a consent form that not only explained the research study to them, but it also took their consent stating that they willingly participated in the study. Various questions were asked to the participants during the interview. Although they had the option of not answering any question(s) that they did not, but they answered all the questions.

The primary research which is qualitative data was supposed to collect through in two types of ways such as email questioners to management level of employees and face to face interviews with 10 top management staff in HR department, IT department and leaning and development department. But due to travel restrictions and health safety of Covid-19, the researcher has decided to conduct the face-to-face interview as a phone interview. The researcher was able to complete the interview within 15-30 minutes and participants were happily answered without skipping the questions.

Conversely, the point of subjective information is to give a total, nitty gritty depiction and this cycle is suggested during before periods of exploration work. Subjective methodology is more emotional and accumulated data cannot be mathematically examined (Shulga and Busser, 2019). Hence, that information has use and usage in examination about individuals' viewpoint, mentality, fears, and expectations, which cannot be important for quantitative investigation. Subjective information brings about more 'rich' significance in term of tedious, and less likelihood to be summed up.

- Structured interviews imply utilizing explicit polls and this exploration strategy is normally utilized for quantitative reviews. The organized meetings include the questioner failure to change the construction of inquiry by adding or eliminating a portion of its arrangement (Book and Kim, 2019). Led in proper manner, respondents' reactions are recorded on a poll normalized structure during the screening. Therefore, the examination of the organized meetings has quantitative nature.

- Semi-organized meeting is research instrument used to give more noteworthy volume to conversation and information about the issue, assessment, and respondent's perspective on specific subject (Golubovskaya and Robinson, 2019). This methodology is adaptable as far as changing a few inquiries during the meetings interaction giving the specialist opportunity to pose somewhat comparable inquiry to cover rundown of currently pre-arranged subjects. The inquiries can shift starting with one meeting then onto the next after the way of conversation with respondent. Consequently, the gathered

information can sum up both subjective and quantitative data and have sway in exploratory investigation.

- Unstructured interviews are additionally called "top to bottom" interviews (Soon, 2020). The unstructured meetings are led in casual way as primer advance in research to questioner produces theory about the idea of subject being explored.

Embracing this examination instrument questioner knows about capacity to assemble the information important for research theme, matters and reactions in some profundity. Those meetings are directed by predefined rundown of theory, and they are not constrained by explicit inquiries (Filimonau et. al, 2019). The principal motivation behind picking top to bottom meetings lies in questioner's need to discover people's opinion and way how they respond to issues. The respondent is urged to uncover and to discuss all that he/she thinks on issues important to the analyst. The questioner is observing (or copying) for all features that would significantly add to the exploration.

In the current study, the data was collected by sending questionnaire survey through emails to management level employees working in the cited hotel organisation. Furthermore, the researcher also conducted a face-to-face interview of ten top management level staff in HR, Training and Development and IT departments of the hotel. However, the process of data collection was severely impacted by the COVID19 crisis. Due to this reason, travelling related difficulties arose; and to counter them, the researcher decided to conduct online face-to-face interviews, while the questionnaires were sent through emails. The interviews lasted for 15-20 minutes each for the participants.

3.7 SAMPLING METHOD

Sampling refers to the method which is being used by the researcher for selecting the sample of the numbers from the population. While conducting the data the researcher uses sampling so that easily the population can be selected which are being interviewed or surveyed for collecting the information regarding the research topic and conducting systematic research. If the researcher focuses on the sampling, then it will help them in collecting the data in a practical, convenient, manageable and costeffective manner. Different types of sampling methods can be used by the researcher for selecting a sample from the population. Types of sampling had been mentioned below such as:

- Random Sampling: this is a type of sampling method in which all the individuals are having an equal opportunity of being selected and this sampling encloses the

entire population. Among all the individuals the sample is being selected randomly.

- **Systematic Sampling:** in this type of sampling method the individuals are selected by listing them and then chosen the individuals at the regular intervals. This method is somewhat like the random sampling, but it is quite easily to conduct as compared to it.
- **Convenience Sampling:** in this sampling method the individuals who are more accessible to the research are being selected by the researcher. But one of the drawbacks of using this method is it does not produces generalise data. Moreover, it is easy and cost-effective method of sampling.
- **Cluster Sampling:** in this type of sampling method the researcher needs to divide the population into the subgroups and but in this method, it is necessary that each subgroup should have similar characteristics of the whole sample. For this method the researcher needs to randomly select the entire subgroup rather than selected an individual of the subgroup.
- **Stratified Sampling:** this type of sampling method is usually used when the population is having a mixed characteristics and the researcher wants that every characteristic should have a fixed proportion in the sample. For selecting the individuals through this method, the entire population needs to be divided into different subgroups which is based on the characteristics.

Based on the above-mentioned discussion of the sampling methods the researcher can select an appropriate method which suits well with the aims and objectives of the research. Several authors had also mentioned about the sampling methods in their studies and articles. According to Sekaran and Bougie (2010), an effective and unbiased method of respondent choice in the process of collecting research data is that of sampling. Primary and secondary data are required in this process. On completing the information assortment measure in the connected overview, it will think about testing techniques and more consideration in being put on picking people for interviews and studies (Johnson et. al, 2019). There hope to direct a semi-organized meeting with the top administration of the human asset office and learning and improvement division. On doing the review poll it is relied upon to set up the survey with including 20 inquiries that are relevant to the exploration point alongside two standard inquiries stressing the connection between two key factors. The members have the decision to address these inquiries giving weightage from 1 to 5, strongly agree to strongly disagree respectively. Members for the study poll will chiefly engaged the management level of employees in

Mitchels and Butlers Company. 100-150 members are relied upon to decide for the study polls.

Questionnaire will send via emails around 300 Mitchells and Butlers restaurants across the UK. Targeted respondents are management level of employee in Mitchell and butlers. Sample can be Kitchen managers, Assistant managers, or General managers from each individual business. The aim of this study was to assess effectiveness of training in hospitality industry. The questionnaire of the survey was divided into three parts. The first part is related to the demographic and background information of the respondents, the second part dealt with effectiveness of training programmes held in the Mitchell and butlers and the third part represented the respondent's general feelings about the training and development also technological impact on it.

3.8 DATA ANALYSIS METHOD

Data analysis method is defined as the method which is being used by the research for analysing the data which is being collected by the data collection methods. Extracting the useful information from the collected is important as it helps the researcher in drawing results for the research study. In other words, data analysis refers to the process which is being used for evaluation of the data by using logical and analytical reasoning. This helps the researchers to carefully analyse every component of the data which is being collected in the research study. The method which is being used by the researcher for analysing the data depends upon the nature of the research, research design and the data collection methods used in the research study.

Data analysis methods are applied in the research study on the basis of the data which is collected such as if the researcher had collected the quantitative data, then different methods are applied and if they had collected qualitative data then other methods would be applied. The most commonly used data analysis methods for quantitative data are descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. And on the other hand, for analysing the qualitative data the data analysis methods are context analysis, discourse analysis, narrative analysis, and grounded theory.

Descriptive analysis is a used for analysing a statistical data and this analysis helps the researcher in summarizing the statistical data and finding the common patters. Among the different tool and techniques of descriptive analysis it is important for the research to choose the best suited techniques based on the research question and the manner in which the researcher wants to reflect the results of the research study. Mean, mode,

median, percentage, frequency and range are some of the mostly used tool for descriptive analysis. Some of the software are also used for descriptive analysis such as Statistical Package of Social Science (SPSS). This analysis helps the researcher a lot by providing exact numbers and this is most useful for the research studies in which the sample size is limited, and the results does not needs to be generalise rather than needs to be specific.

Other than this Inferential analysis is also used for analysing the quantitative data. This analysis method is based on the predictions and inference about the population bases sample. This is generally a considered to be a complex method for analysing the data and this method focuses on reflecting a relationship among the multiple variables for generalizing the results and for making predictions as well. Some of the common techniques which are used for inferential analysis are correlation, regression, and analysis of the variables.

Data analysis is one of the most common method, which is used for analysing the qualitative data, it is generally used for analysing the data which is in the documented form. Mostly this method is being used for analysing the response of the response of the interviewees. Moreover, for analysing the different interactions among the individual's narrative analysis and discourse analysis are generally used. Narrative analysis focus on the research questions and analyse the data of the interviews, observation, and survey. On the other hand, the discourse analysis focuses on analysing the social context in which the interaction had taken place. Other than these methods grounded theory is also a method which is used for analysing the qualitative data, but it is only applied when the research focuses on explaining a particular phenomenon. Apart from these data analysis methods several other methods are also available for analysing the data in the research study such as prescriptive analysis, predictive analysis, diagnostic analysis and many more. In the present study the research is although focusing on the case study of an organisation operating in the hospitality industry but is also conducting the survey. For analysing the data which is being collected by the survey the researcher implements the SPSS for data analysis. According to Henry, (2012) when analysing the collected data in a research, it is useful to use a range of data analysis tools and functions. Here a clear data analysis plan is essential to the structure and functions, vital to the analysis and programs that are needed. An identical step in the data analysis process is using the SPSS software in order to generate the charts and mathematical output, if those are available within the research context.

Although SPSS is considered to be effective for analysing both the qualitative and quantitative data, but it is widely used for analysing quantitative data. SPSS is considered to be one of the powerful tool for analysing the survey data. This method allows the research to analyse the data effectively and allows them to spend more time on identifying the trends and drawing better conclusions of the research study. This SPSS software should be used in generating the qualitative data gathered from the survey questionnaire, in the research. According to Wolcott, (2001) this gives a critical and indistinguishable yield for quantitative information design. The principle of the examination is to investigate the effectiveness of current training programs. Thus, it is relied upon to quantify the level of connection between these two utilizing above programming and estimating the Pearson relationship coefficient (Filimonau and Pettit, 2019). Likewise, the auxiliary information just as essential information gathered through subjective information with centre gathering conversations will be investigated for a situation study strategy to foster a level-headed and intelligent recognizable proof of relationship among key factors.

3.9 ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Ethical considerations are one of the major and important part of the research study. Chetty, (2016) had mentioned that ethical consideration is essential to be focused while doing a research study as it promotes the aims of the research to impart authentic knowledge, preventing errors and truth. If the research pay attention on all the essential ethical considerations of the research study than it will bring accountability, trust, fairness, and mutual respect among all the stakeholders of the research study. Fouka and Mantzorou, (2011) had mentioned in their study about the major ethics which includes the informed consent, avoiding any kind of harm to any of the stakeholder, respect for anonymity and confidentiality of the information, respect for privacy and conducting the research in an ethical manner by following all the principles of the ethical code of conduct.

Several authors had mentioned about the importance of ethical considerations for a researcher. Bell and Bryman, (2011) had mentioned that there are numerous pathways and roads run over for social event the information on research measure. As to Bell and Bryman clarify moral elements are imperative to lead the examination just as progress the exploration cycle (Bell and Bryman, 2011). It is relied upon to get the information gathered through both essential and auxiliary strategies. Likewise, the authorization will be acquired on completing the examination on the organization and

furthermore applicable consent to get top administration for conversations and use organization email to send survey and get reactions through organization email (Blayney and Young, 2020). At the same time protection for pronouncing that information will be guaranteed. Analyst will announce the references on utilizing optional information where appropriately.

While working on a research project ethical consideration need to be focused significantly by the researcher. Ethical consideration is one of the most important part of the research study. If the research does not focus on the ethical consideration while doing research project, then it can create a lot of issues for them. While working on the dissertation or research needs to focus on all the ethical considerations which are mentioned below such as:

- When the researcher is involving the participation of the individuals or the respondents in the research study that it is important that they should not be forced to be a part of the research instead of it they should voluntarily participate in the research project. Moreover, the participants are having a right to leave the study at any stage of the study, the researcher is not having any kind of right to stop the participants by doing this as this totally depends on the participants choice.
- Whenever the participant is involved in the study then their participation should be on the basis of the informed consent and if the individual agrees to it then then the participant decides to be a part of the research or not. In the consent letter the researcher needs to mention all the important and sufficient information regarding the research and the respondents are allowed freely to make a decision that they want to be in the research or not, the researcher cannot pressurise the participants.
- While asking questions in the personal interviews, group interviews or during the formulation of the questionnaires the researcher is not allowed to use unacceptable language, offensive language and discrimination should not be practised.
- The researcher needs to focus on the Data protection act (1998) while working on a research project.
- Plagiarism is an important ethical consideration in the research. It means that the content which is being written in the research study should not be copied form any of the electronic resources. The researcher needs to write their own content and are not allowed to copy it from anywhere.

- In the research projects the researcher needs to pay attention on the privacy, respect, and dignity of the research participants. The researcher needs to ensure the protection of the privacy of the participants and should also maintain high level of confidentiality.
- Confidentiality and protection of the data needs to be ensured by the researcher while working on research.
- The researcher should not try to avoid being biased while representing the results of the primary research on the basis of his/her own opinion or on the basis of the aims and objectives of the research.
- The communication which is involved in any of the stage or section of the research needs to be exact, transparent, and honest.
- Acknowledgement of the work of other authors needs to be paid special attention by the research. In the secondary research when the researcher is using any kind of information from the work of other authors then the researcher needs to properly cite the work of other authors. The researcher needs to use appropriate reference style such as Harvard/APA/Vancouver or any other referencing system while citing the work of other authors in their research study.

All the above-mentioned ethical considerations are important for the researcher, and they need to focus on following all the ethics while working on research project. Apart from these ethical considerations most of the universities are having tier own code of ethical practices which needs to be focused by the student while working on the dissertation, thesis, or a research project. In the present research study, the researcher had focused on all the ethical consideration while working on the research project. The work of other authors in the literature reviews had been cited carefully to avoid any kind of ethical violations. Along with this all the ethical considerations had been kept in mind while conducting the semi-structured questionnaire and safety and privacy of all the research participants had been kept in mind by the researcher. The researcher had focussed on the ethical consideration and had avoided the chances of plagiarism while working on this research project.

Finally, the researcher was able to use appropriate techniques and methods to get reliable and valid results through the research. The pragmatism philosophy which uses mixed or multiple method designs has applied to the research. Because research is analysed by both primary and secondary data. The inductive and deductive which are known as Qualitative and quantitative were discussed and applied both research approaches in the thesis. Moreover, the research design types were explained, and

exploratory design has selected to conduct the research due to the research type. The researcher has chosen case study and qualitative interview as research strategies. The researcher has chosen random sampling to collect the data and targeted participants were 100-150 management level employees in the Mitchel and Butlers company. As well as telephone interview was conducted between 15-30 minutes with 10 management employees. The researcher has collected the secondary data through websites, books, articles, publications and many more sources. The researcher has followed all the ethical principles to avoid the misconduct and made safe environment to all participants by ensuring no one is harmed end of the research.

The data analysis is explained in chapter 04 by researcher and all the qualitative and quantitative and qualitative data are analysed.

04. CHAPTER FOUR: DATA
ANALYSIS

This study focused on assessing and evaluating the effectiveness of training programmes conducted by hospitality organisations in the UK for employees working at the mid-level management position. In order to conduct this study, the researcher used both interviews and questionnaire surveys to collect the relevant data. In the following paragraphs, this data has been analysed using qualitative methods of thematic analysis.

4.0 Data Reliability

Case Processing Summary			
		N	%
Cases	Valid	100	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	100	100.0
a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.			

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha ^a	N of Items
-.166	4
a. The value is negative due to a negative average covariance among items. This violates reliability model assumptions. You may want to check item codings.	

The above table shows Cronbach's alpha comes out to be -0.166, meaning that the questionnaire items were not reliable because as a rule of thumb, the data collected through questionnaire is reliable if the Cronbach's alpha comes out to be more than 0.70

Item-Total Statistics				
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted

Team leader workbooks, (paper version) are more effective than online workbooks for development of management level of employees	10.16	4.035	-.139	.024
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Online trainings are more effective to develop the career development of management employees	8.55	3.644	-.037	-.177 ^a
Class room seminars are effective than webinars	10.13	3.710	-.068	-.116 ^a
Impact of technology for training and development is more faster for career progression	8.48	3.464	-.014	-.229 ^a
a. The value is negative due to a negative average covariance among items. This violates reliability model assumptions. You may want to check item codings.				

The above table shows Cronbach's alpha value if any of the items is deleted from the questionnaire.

4.1 Qualitative Analysis

Theme 1 Training is very important part of job profile for midlevel management employees

The Director of Talent Development at Mitchells & Butlers has stated that: *"Developing our people is absolutely critical to our success and the launch of the Training Academy underpins our commitment to be one of the best companies to work for where our employees feel that they are continually learning"*. During the study it was found that most of the participants believe training is a crucial part of job profile for the midlevel management employees. Herein it can be said that the data suggests taking frequent training helps employees in improving their skills and thus their overall performance as well, so that they can contribute maximum towards firms' goals and objectives. During the survey it was further observed that those managers who received regular training experienced an overall improvement in their satisfaction with the workplace, but were also able to perform well, achieving the various KPIs set by the top management of the firm. Out of the 100 participants, 85 replied that training is a crucial part of their

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professional life. This means that the mid-level management employees tend to value their training activities highly. Through training sessions, the mid-level management employees regularly take different training activities to enhance their various skills and abilities.

The current study further revealed that training is an important part of their career for the mid-level management employees. In this regard, many of the previous studies have highlighted that training and development sessions motivates employees to perform to the best of their skills and capabilities, thereby adding to overall performance of the company and thus help it to achieve its goals and targets. Herein the past studies further showed that such training sessions expand employees' capabilities and motivates them. This way the firm can gain their loyalty and also expect the best performance out of them. Several authors and experts have shown that training instils a feeling of loyalty among the employees, as they feel that they must work for the company, as it has spent a considerable number of resources on training them and improving their skills. Thus, "through training a company can gain loyalty of the employees and also encourage them to work for the betterment of the firm and attainment of its goals and targets as well". Five employees during the survey stated that they believe training is a crucial part of their job profile and therefore they try to take every possible opportunity to improve their skills and learn something new so they can perform better at the workplace.

During this study, it was noted that the mid-level management employees accord high value and importance to training and development. Many researchers found that since these individuals are in such a position that they must aim for further growth and progression, because if they do not, then they will either be stuck in the same position for a long time, or they will be demoted to lower position(s). This is one of the main reasons for such importance and value to be given on the training function. Therefore, taking regular training and development helps the mid-level managers in progressing their careers and take advantage of the opportunities presented to them. On this basis, it can be said that mid-level management employees are set to gain considerably by undergoing regular training and development sessions.

During the study it was further noted that training is an important part of professional lives for the mid-level management employees. This shows that training is a crucial aspect for such employees. It can be considered as an opportunity that motivates the mid-level management employees to develop technical and specialised skills, which can be greatly beneficial for their careers and help them to achieve professional growth and development. Likewise, as somebody ascends the positions of an organization, it's

critical to concentrate on more particular or explicit preparing in explicit jobs. “Helping a mid-level worker centre in around a specific aptitude or confirmation makes the way for vocation development and objective setting. Push representatives to go past the fundamental or nonexclusive section level preparing to locate a more particular aptitude. Laying on shrubs at the mid-level is simple. Representatives are sandwiched among levels, and the consistency can get settled”. At the point when working environments underscore development and preparing, they're making an impression on representatives, principally mid-level, that groups ought to make progress toward development. With an attention on the board, mentorship, correspondence and specialized aptitudes, organizations can benefit from developing the ability they have, and make a more grounded and more beneficial work environment.

Theme 2 Role of technology is prominent in training for midlevel management employees

“In recent years, technology has emerged to become a crucial part of different organisational functions and processes. In similar manner, it plays a pivotal role in the way training is provided to the mid-level management employees. It also tends to have an influence on the overall effectiveness of the training function as well”. During the study it was seen that technology helps in providing effective training to the mid-level management employees; and thus, also play a crucial role in enabling the company to achieve its goals and targets. Researcher, during the study, also found that using the latest technology helps in improving the overall quality and effectiveness of the training sessions.

Many of the past authors stated that companies are shifting to using latest technologies for training related purposes. As per several studies, technology not only simplifies the training process, but it also helps the mid-level management level employees in speeding up the whole process. In this regard, during the study it was further noted that technology has added whole new dimensions to the training process itself, such as just in time training. It is very similar to that of just-in-time supply strategy. According to one of the respondents, “training is provided to the employees at the right time and in the right manner, so that they can gain the most benefit out of it. Through such form of training, the mid-level management employees can receive the right type of training at the right time and through the right medium, thereby enabling them to improve their skills in a significant manner”. In such type of training, focus is on using digital and online methods for training the employees. During the study, it was further observed that some of the mid-level management employees might think that the company is not

training them for the future and is only focusing on improving their skills for firm's current requirements. But using the just-in-time approach for training can help such employees to remain associated with the training and also recall it at a later stage as well.

Several studies further showed that such virtual training methods, just like the just-in-time training approach can align with and fulfil needs and requirements of the trainee or the learner. This means that such training methods can be useful in terms of providing best and effective training to the mid-level management employees. The virtual training consists of different methods and techniques such as e-learning which can be either web-based or self-paced and blended learning which is a combination of different courses and options. The study also revealed that in current times of the pandemic, using online and digital methods of training can be useful since a large chunk of workforce for companies is working remotely. Therefore, use of e-learning and training methods can provide satisfactory results in terms of training the employees and enhancing their performance and contribution towards firms' goals and objectives. The web has associated a huge number of individuals, offering ascend to the assortment of purchaser shopping propensities, excursion timetables, areas, and many other data. Web-based social networking and publicizing blended, giving organizations phenomenal access to purchasers and this data is mined (gathered) and put away for investigation and use. Adroit entrepreneurs comprehend the significance of mining and how they can utilize this information to improve dynamic on the side of clients and workers. Proprietors and directors ought to put resources into developing their aptitudes.

Theme 3 Technology is being used for training at Mitchells and Butlers

“High performance working practice is a new training technique in hospitality industry. During the study it was seen that by reducing management responsibilities or job titles, encouraging with higher task autonomy, implementing new training programmes, encouraging information sharing programmes and pay based on employees' performances can bring the high practices in hospitality industry”. “Training, in hospitality setting, simply means teaching people how to do their jobs the managers may instruct and guide a trainee toward learning knowledge (such as certain facts and procedures), skills necessary to do the standard required (such as loading the dish machine), or attitudes (such as customer-oriented attitude)”. Three kinds of training are needed in food and lodging operations: job instruction, retraining, and orientation.

During the study it was further noted that Mitchells and Butlers uses the latest technologies for training its employees at the mid-level. Training methods has been changed and expanded through technology. As the technological advancement has changed the way in which the individuals learn new things and concepts it had also improvement the learning programs. “In the context of the businesses the companies need to teach a lot of new things, concepts and skills to their employee. Technologies are helping the organisation to make modifications in their training programs so that they can effectively train the employees”. Several authors have mentioned in their study regarding the use of technologies in the training. One of the most important tasks of the management system is to focus on operating effectively with the changing environment and continuously updating the skills and knowledge of the employees so that they can work effectively in the changing environment. If the organisations implement better technologies in the training, then it can help them in improving the skills and knowledge of the employees effectively. The training professionals and the educationalists are focusing on using the technologies which can improve and facilitates the learning process. Due to the technological advancement, e-learning had become much popular, and it is leading to significant changes in training and leaning programs. E-learning is being widely used in the training and education for improving the quality of the learning and teaching processes. The evolution of the e-learning is having positive impact on the personal and professional learning of the individuals. Using the technologies for learning and training is providing several opportunities to individuals such as convenience training as per the capability of the learners.

Theme 4 Technology improve efficacy of the training function

Planning and improvement have reliably been a sorted out and semi-obvious formula using age-old courses of action. With the climb of millennial masters and their preference for web-based life and smart and "now" learning methods, the planning and progression affiliation is moving from ordinary structures to on the web and in-time learning. Various immense associations with high responsibility, for instance, Amazon and Google, have established new learning systems for their developing wonders and use advancement in an adroit, social way. With getting ready as fluid as sitting with a chief and finding some new data at the time it's required, completing the task self-ruling,

and a while later being assessed during a "practices got the hang of" meeting, agents are starting to respond to setting up that doesn't require the ordinary planning request.

While this one-on-one strategy is positively a pro, various agents find that without a second to save planning can obscure their need to orchestrate and create utilizing outside courses. It also requires some speculation from bosses to follow progress, assess laborers and offer information. With this at the last possible second methodology, a couple of laborers may calculate the board isn't making them for the future and is simply based on their ability to complete their current tasks. That can transform into a positive con if laborers feel tricked on their overall capable unforeseen development. "One favoured situation to getting using advancement is that types of progress are consistent. Melding advancement into the learning condition makes an especially open course, anyway it moreover prepares the workforce for the accompanying surge of development, for instance, modernized thinking, gamification and enlarged reality". Development engaged learning can be a feasible contraption if the activities are organized by instructional arrangement norms.

Similarly, electronic getting ready isn't restricted to a specific time or region. Agents can complete the process of getting ready materials at whatever point and wherever they have an Internet affiliation. Destinations can pass on the basic instructional substance or extend and improve getting ready substance. Various online agent getting ready projects require enlistment and have the ability to screen labourer execution utilizing a learning the board system. Dynamically affiliations are using development enabled instructional systems that utilization advancement, for instance, electronic learning through web based getting ready, flexible development, for instance, I-pads, and amusements in the transport of direction. A fundamental bit of leeway of development based getting ready is using the scale and degree of delegate planning programs. If an affiliation is required to set up various agents development offers endless choices reliant on tolerably insignificant exertion and specialist accessibility.

"Different types of innovations are being utilized by the association for preparing the workers. On the off chance that the organization is utilizing the innovation for the more elevated level of, at that point it will concentrate on work related factors and attempts to prepare the representatives with the goal that they can address the issues of the organization". Also, for the low degree of learning the innovations in the preparation would concentrate on encouraging correspondence among the students and the coaches.

The associations are utilizing PC based preparing, mixed media for preparing, testing appraisal and e-learning for making preparing viably. The likewise referenced that the associations ought to deliberately adjust the organization points and destinations with the powerful administration so the preparation and advancement can be more effective in driving the organization towards its objectives. A large portion of the organizations are utilizing the eLearning for their preparation and improvement programs, as it is viable and productive to build up the colleagues. As per a few creators' association needs a successful preparing to accomplish the objectives and rival their rivals. As he discloses no compelling reason to stress to acquaint the e learning with the association when individuals include to the e learning trainings then they will have the option to carry out their responsibility appropriately. Innovation can offer a chance to preparing and improvement to carry out their responsibility viably. A few creators have likewise referenced in their investigation with respect to mechanical headway in the strategies for preparing.

The investigation had referenced those innovations are having the capacity to offer a few advantages to learning and preparing programs. With the mechanical progression the web-based learning and preparing market had gotten a lot of wellknown in the whole world. The creator had characterized e-learning as the robotization of the way toward learning and preparing with the assistance of data innovations. In the current world dominant part of the business relies upon the e-learning for preparing the representatives and for planning all the various exercises in the association. Additionally, the advancement of the PCs and the systems is filling in as a powerful power in preparing and learning forms.

The examination had inferred that utilization of web based preparing and advancements can be utilized from numerous points of view in preparing, for example, it very well may be a sole wellspring of learning, a follows up to the conventional preparing, option in contrast to the customary preparing and can likewise be an enhancement for supplement to the conventional preparing.

Theme 5 Training is positively associated with organisational performance

Training and development are important for every organisation operating in diverse industries. Effective training is important for the employees as it helps them in developing their skills and enhancing their knowledge which is important for delivering

high quality performance in the organisation. Training enables the representatives in dealing with their shortcoming and utilizing their qualities without limit so they too can convey better administrations in the firm. It is significant for the association to concentrate on the preparation and advancement of the representatives as it is having huge effect on a few different things. "Worker execution is one of the exceptionally influenced factors which is straightforwardly connected with the preparation gave to the representatives to conveying better execution in the association. It is significant for the associations to create various types of preparing programs for the representatives of the association dependent on the different offices in which they are working and furthermore based on their activity jobs". Execution of the representative is likewise relied upon the degree of their activity fulfilment.

Fulfilling the representatives with their activity jobs ought to be the centre duty of the association as it is affecting the worker execution. In the event that the organization is arranging viable preparing programs for the worker which are giving positive results and are improving the aptitudes of the representatives then it will prompt occupation fulfilment which will prompt better execution of the worker in the association. It's anything but a simple assignment for the organizations to build up a preparation programs as it requires a ton of assets, and it should be fruitful in building up the abilities of the representatives.

The organizations need to concentrate on all the components which are affecting the preparation and advancement of the representatives in the association. Preparing is explicitly significant for the new recruited representatives as it is significant for the organization to fill the ability hole among the workers aptitudes and the aptitudes required for the employment job.

Huge number of representatives are working in a neighbourliness administration giving associations in the various offices. In this industry all the various offices are significant as they are conveying a differing administration to the clients. Representatives working in all the different offices, for example, front office, food and refreshment, housekeeping and others needs to have explicit range of abilities dependent on the division in which they are working, and on the administration, they are conveying to the clients.

Associations working in this industry needs to sort out viable preparing programs which can help the representatives in building up their abilities. Accommodation administration giving associations working in UK centres around the preparation and improvement of their representatives. Various scope of preparing

programs are being led for the representatives by the associations. On the off chance that the associations simply recruit the representatives without giving them better preparing regarding their jobs and obligations and for the advancement of abilities which is significant for conveying better quality work to the association. It is significant for the associations to comprehend the significance of preparing and advancement of workers and its effect on the profitability and occupation fulfilment of the representatives.

Alongside this the organizations needs to comprehend that how preparing is affecting the general execution of the association and it achievement. In the event that better preparing is given to the representatives and they are conveying top notch work to the association and fulfilling the clients with their administrations then it will drove the organization towards progress. “It is basic for the HR division to build up the staff aptitudes and stay up with the latest”. Creators have effectively recognized the requirement for HR division to stay informed concerning the progressions that are going on universally with various parts of the business functionalities and the connection between these capacities can modify the whole business process. With the progressing changes on the planet, innovation is assuming a significant job in each division and in all the enterprises.

With regards to the preparation which is being given to the workers the organizations need to concentrate on utilizing better advances which can help them in giving compelling preparing to the representatives. Human asset branch of the organization should concentrate on sorting out appropriate and powerful preparing and improvement programs for the representatives. Innovative headway is giving better chances to the associations to utilize the advances for giving powerful preparing to the representatives.

Theme 6 Mitchells and Butlers focuses on training its employees

Along with investing in attracting talented candidates, Mitchells and Butlers also focuses on providing them with high-quality training with greater efficiency and effectiveness. The company is providing an innovative training program for training employees. Mitchell and Butler rank among one of the best companies of the UK which are providing the best job training to the employees.

“The company is using technological advancement to the fullest and using Mable training for the employees training. MABLE stands for Mitchells and Butlers learning environment, which is an online training program developed by Mitchell and Butler for effectively training the employees. Mable is a system of learning which is completely based on online learning approach”. This system is providing support to the employees by learning as per their needs, and it engages the employees effectively in the training program and giving remarkable outcomes to the cited company.

Utilizing the innovatively propelled approach and strategies for preparing the workers is giving advantages to the organization. The students referenced that utilizing the Mable for preparing is demonstrating them great experience is helping them in learning the ideas in a viable and suitable way. The nature of the administrations which is being offered by the Mitchell and Butler had expanded striking, and this instrument is constantly helping the referred to organization to prepare the representatives adequately.

“Using better innovations and the innovatively propelled apparatus is the focal point of the organization with the goal that they can give the best understanding to their clients. The commitment level of the workers is higher as the organization is giving better preparing to the representatives”. Utilizing better advancements in preparing and exceptionally prepared workers of Mitchell and Butler are helping the organization in keeping up a superior situation in the accommodation business of the UK.

Training is one of the most significant things which is overall affecting the activity of the workers. It influences the people in various manners and makes it a significant piece of the activity profile for centre level administration representatives. The consequences of the current examination show that preparation is a fundamental and significant piece of the activity profile. The investigation had referenced about the few jobs and obligations which are being performed by the centre level heads and which is significant for the association. The aftereffects of the examination had referenced that based on the jobs played by the centre level chiefs, they are required to give successful preparing programs so they can build up their aptitudes and information.

The examination additionally referenced that it is basic that the centre level administration representatives ought to be prepared. Based on the consequences of the current examination and the aftereffects of the past investigations referenced in the writing survey, it very well may be said that compelling preparing assumes a significant job hands on profile of the workers and particularly for the centre level administration representatives.

The associations need to concentrate on giving the best preparing to the centre level administration workers by concentrating on better and innovatively propelled preparing apparatuses and procedures. Innovation is assuming a significant job in all the different business divisions, and the firm needs to see how advancements can help them in functioning all the more adequately and proficiently. The consequences of the current investigation notice that innovation is assuming an unmistakable job in the preparation of the representatives. Better innovations are making it simpler for the workers and for the organizations themselves. It very well may be said that on the off chance that the associations are creating preparing programs for centre level representatives, at that point they should utilize advancements, for example, e-learning and internet preparing programs.

Utilizing innovations for preparing can spare a great deal of time and superfluous cash. Alongside these advances can help the workers in getting to prepare in a more advantageous way. In addition, it very well may be said that utilizing advances for preparing the representatives can help the organizations in preparing them successfully as innovation has a pivotal task to carry out in preparing.

“Associations working in differing enterprises are utilizing better advancements which is giving them a few advantages and helping them in keeping up a superior situation in their particular businesses. The referred to organization Mitchell and Butler is likewise utilizing better advancements in the association for preparing the representatives”. Wide scope of advances is being utilized by the Mitchell and Butler for preparing the workers as the organization is utilizing the web-based learning and elearning approaches for preparing the representatives in a compelling way. The organization had referenced on their site with respect to the innovative propelled instruments and strategies which are being utilized by them from preparing the workers. The referred to organization had additionally referenced that better innovations are helping them a ton in preparing the representatives and expanding worker fulfilment and worker commitment with the organization. Mitchell and Butler had built up their own online framework for preparing the workers, which are named as Mable.

Theme 7 Online training is more effective than normal training function

The organisations operating in the hospitality industry are using the existing methods for providing the training to the employees, but they should look forwards towards using latest technologies which can help them in providing the training in an easy and effective manner. “The development of the technologies in the hospitality industry had

made it possible for the company to enhance the effectiveness of the training and learning among the employees. Using the latest technologies for providing the training is not easy for the organisations as it is quite costly”. On the other hand, introducing the technologies such as e-learning for training the employees provide several benefits due to which it is beneficial for the companies to use technologies for providing training to the employees.

Although training and development usually go hand in hand, they differ in that case all staff can do training, whereas the trainee’s supervisors or managers usually undertake development.

“Getting ready and improvement has reliably been a sorted out and semiobvious formula using age-old game plans. With the climb of millennial authorities and their preference for web-based life and smart and "now" learning procedures, the planning and progression affiliation is moving from traditional structures to on the web and in-time learning”. Various enormous associations with high duty, for instance, Amazon and Google, have established new learning techniques for their developing wonders and use advancement in an insightful, social way. With getting ready as fluid as sitting with a chief and finding some new data at the particular time it's required, completing the task self-ruling, and a while later being assessed during a "practices mastered" meeting, delegates are starting to respond to setting up that doesn't require the ordinary planning request. While this one-on-one technique is absolutely a pro, various agents find that without a second to save planning can overshadow their need to mastermind and create utilizing outside courses.

It furthermore requires some speculation from bosses to follow progress, assess laborers and offer information. With this at the last possible second methodology, a couple of laborers may calculate the board isn't making them for the future and is simply based on their ability to complete their current tasks. That can transform into a positive con if laborers feel hoodwinked on their overall capable unforeseen development. “One favoured situation to getting using advancement is that types of progress are consistent. Intertwining development into the learning condition makes an extraordinarily open course, anyway it moreover prepares the workforce for the accompanying surge of advancement, for instance, modernized thinking, gamification and increased reality”. Advancement enabled learning can be a reasonable mechanical assembly if the activities are organized by instructional arrangement guidelines. Additionally, electronic planning isn't restricted to a specific time or zone. Agents can complete the

process of getting ready materials at whatever point and wherever they have an Internet affiliation.

Destinations can pass on the fundamental instructional substance or grow and improve planning content. Various online delegate getting ready projects require enlistment and have the ability to screen labour execution utilizing a learning the board structure. Logically affiliations are using development engaged instructional systems that utilization advancement, for instance, electronic learning through web based getting ready, flexible advancement, for instance, I-pads, and diversions in the transport of direction. A fundamental favourable position of development-based planning is using the scale and degree of delegate getting ready projects. If an affiliation is required to set up various delegates advancement offers unfathomable options subject to reasonably negligible exertion and labour accessibility.

Theme 8 Training improves performance of the employees

Hospitality industry generally deals into very complex and dynamic environment that simply means that employees and workers of the company always need advanced training and development sessions. And for dealing in such waste industry training is extremely essential. The industry is getting day by day more advanced filled with innovative technology; business who are operating their organization within hospitality industry need to develop and operate their business with advancement. “Customers in hospitality industry have extremely wide scope they have several alternatives, so for operating business effectively and making their company leader then it has to provide training to their employees”.

Training and development are always essential for the keeping employees engaged and making them specialised in their field. More skills in their job are provide ability to complete tasks with more efficient manner. Training and development programme helps an individual to enhance their core ability and developed new skills which are essential for performing tasks. Within hospitality industry every level and divisions’ workers need training. The business environment is constantly changing and for becoming frontrunner companies need to adopt several new and advanced technologies. Herein, for operating and functioning well with new technology company has to provide training to their employees so that they can effectively operating function well with technology.

Businesses that are operating within the hospitality industry are providing effective training to their employees. At present they are focusing on introducing new and fresh talent within their business but for recruiting them company also provide training to

them. So, this is clear that the company has to provide training to all the workers whether they are fresher or older staff. In the competitive environment of hospitality industry every company is focusing on creating their company on top. And for making company on top business need high quality technology, effective human resource, and strong relationship with clients and effective management. With proper training structure company can enjoy more benefits.

“Along proper structure also not create havoc and burden on employees head. If the company does not create it properly employees think that it is an extra burden that they have to be performing with their tasks”. They really do not enjoy their learning session and less concentrate while workshops. That simply reflect less engaged employees, and this will turn decline in the level of performance of employees as well as organisation as whole. Company who has effective and engaged workforce that business achieve success; on the other hand if company does not effective employees that company does not achieve their desirable position within the market.

Staff training and development is generally beneficial to any industry and any organisation. In this study, the researcher focusses on the effectiveness and impact of such training programmes aimed at mid-level management staff in UK hospitality industry.

Theme 9 The training content at Mitchells and Butlers is appropriate for employee needs

The Group HR Director Mitchells & Butlers acknowledged that: *"Our new training Academy is an exciting development providing additional facilities to further up-skill and develop our people. Ultimately, it will play a central role in ensuring that our guests have a fantastic experience in our businesses"*.

The Chief Executive, BII said: *"The BII wanted to recognise Mitchells & Butlers commitment to providing quality training facilities for its employees. We congratulate them on this excellent development and are delighted to be associated with an organisation which places a huge emphasis on training"*.

Mitchell and Butler are one of the largest hospitality company in the UK; the cited company is having a larger number of restaurants, pubs and bars and the organisation is serving a wide range of eating and drinking choices to their customers. The company is focusing on offering a wide range of quality food and drink to the customers and fast

and friendly services to the customers. The company is working on its aim of bringing innovation, listening to the customer's feedback, and working on it. Along with this, the company is focusing on having passionate staff and providing them the best training so that they can work effectively in the organisation. The cited company is focusing on investing a large amount of capital on the training of the employees so that they can be trained effectively.

“The company is using better technologies and advanced tools so that they can provide better- and high-quality training to their employees. Using better technology and high-quality training to the employees is providing benefits to the company such as a significant increase in the employee retention and creating a highly trained workforce which is capable of delivering quality services to the customers”. Mitchell and Butler are focusing on attracting the most talented candidates belonging to the best universities.

This system can provide training to the employee in a different manner which is a most convenient and effective manner. Mable provides the training to the employees based on their capacity and based on their needs. The individuals can easily log in to the Mable and can start the training based on their need of the requirement and whenever and wherever they think that they need to develop there any of the skills or enhance their knowledge regarding any of the concept of the hospitality industry. The results of the present research study reveal that Mitchell and Butler are using highly advanced technologies for providing training to the employees.

Use of better technologies had helped them a lot in training the employees in an effective manner and also the company is looking forward to investing in their research and development department so that they can use the best technologically advanced training tools for providing training to the employees. Using technologies in training is aimed at increasing the efficacy of the training programs so that the organisations can train the employees in a well organised and in an effective manner. The results of the study suggest that there is a positive relationship between the use of technologies in the training and efficacy of the training programs.

Mitchell and Butler are understanding this concept in an effective manner that their employees are playing a crucial role in the performance. The Mitchell and Butler are focusing on the development of the skills and knowledge of their employees as they understand that they are the one who is responsible for providing high-quality service to the customer who is having a positive impact on the customer experience. The cited company is especially focusing on providing training to the employees in an effective

manner, and due to this, the company is investing high capital and resources in training the employees in an effective manner.

With this mindset and goal of providing effective learning to the employees, the company had a partnership with the companies such as Kineo and Totara, which had led to the development of the learning system MABLE. This is helping the company in training in an effective manner and developing the skills and knowledge of the employees. Along with this, the company is also using other technologically advanced tools and technique for making the training programs more effective and convenient for the employees.

4.2 Quantitative Analysis

		Age			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	18-21 Years	31	31.0	31.0	31.0
	21-30 Years	21	21.0	21.0	52.0
	31-40 Years	32	32.0	32.0	84.0
	Above 40 Years	16	16.0	16.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Here it can be seen that most of the participants were aged between 31-40 years closely followed by 31 individuals from the 18-21 years bracket. This means the company promotes young individuals to managerial positions as well. On the other hand, there were only 21 participants who were between the ages of 21-30 years and the least number of participants belonged to the age group of 40 years and above.

		Gender			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	54	54.0	54.0	54.0

Female	46	46.0	46.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Majority of the participants were male (n = 54) and while 46 were female participants. This shows that the company mostly promotes male to the managerial positions.

Nationality

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	British	62	62.0	62.0	62.0
	Asian	9	9.0	9.0	71.0
	American	9	9.0	9.0	80.0
	African	11	11.0	11.0	91.0
	Chinese	9	9.0	9.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Most of the participants were British national (n = 62) followed by African (n = 11). There were nine individuals each from Chinese, Asian and American nationalities. Since it is a UK based hospitality organisation, it is only right for the company to promote more British nationals to managerial positions.

Job Role

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	General Manager	34	34.0	34.0	34.0
	Deputy Manager	20	20.0	20.0	54.0
	Assistant Manager	19	19.0	19.0	73.0
	Kitchen Manager	27	27.0	27.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

34 participants were working on the position of General Manager and 20 were on Deputy Manager positions. 27 participants were employed on Kitchen Manager positions and then 19 were working as Assistant Manager in the organisation.

Length of Service

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	<1 Year	26	26.0	26.0	26.0

1-5 Years	23	23.0	23.0	49.0
5-10 Years	35	35.0	35.0	84.0
More than 10 Years	16	16.0	16.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Majority of the participants had served 5-10 years in the company (n = 35). 26 participants had spent less than one year in the company while 23 had spent 1-5 years and 16 had been associated with the company for more than ten years.

Position at the time of Joining

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	General Manager	16	16.0	16.0	16.0
	Assistant/Kitchen Manager	42	42.0	42.0	58.0
	Back of House Team Member	23	23.0	23.0	81.0
	Front of House Team Member	19	19.0	19.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

42 participants had joined the restaurant at Assistant Manager or Kitchen Manager positions, while 23 worked as a team member in the Back of House at the time of joining the organisation. 16 participants joined the company at General Manager position and 19 at the time of joining were employed in the Front of House team.

Training programmes and Tools Received for Development

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Workbook	12	12.0	12.0	12.0
	Online Workbook	5	5.0	5.0	17.0
	Seminar and Workshops	15	15.0	15.0	32.0
	Webinars	8	8.0	8.0	40.0
	All of them	60	60.0	60.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Five participants replied that they receive online workbook as training tool while eight replied that they received webinars as tool for training and development function. 15 replied that they attended seminars and workshops for improving their skills; while 12 replied that they received workbooks. On the other hand, 60 participants replied that they received all the tools for their training and development functions.

Most Effective Training Programmes for Development

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Online Training	30	30.0	30.0	30.0
	Webinars	24	24.0	24.0	54.0
	Workbook	22	22.0	22.0	76.0
	Seminars	24	24.0	24.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Majority (n = 30) of the participants stated that they think online training to be a more effective training and development tool. 24 participants stated that webinars were more effective; similarly 24 participants also stated that seminars are more effective; while 22 replied that they think workbooks are more effective as training programs.

Impact of Online Training on Development

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Excellent	31	31.0	31.0	31.0
	Better than normal training	54	54.0	54.0	85.0
	Very good	15	15.0	15.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

54 participants stated that online training is much better than normal training; while 31 participants replied that online training is an excellent training and development plan. On the other hand, 15 participants replied that online training has a significant impact on their development.

Impact of Workbook and seminars on development

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Excellent	39	39.0	39.0	39.0
	Better than online training	16	16.0	16.0	55.0
	Very good	45	45.0	45.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

45 participants replied that impact of workbook and seminars on development is very good, while 39 stated that it is an excellent option for development of skills among the

employees and managers. On the other, only 16 participants replied that seminars and workbooks are better than online training option.

Relevance of Training Content

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Totally relevant	31	31.0	31.0	31.0
	Not relevant	30	30.0	30.0	61.0
	Cannot Tell	39	39.0	39.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

39 participants were not sure if the training content was relevant or not; while 31 replied that the content was total relevant, and 30 participants believed it was not relevant.

Team leader workbooks, (paper version) are more effective than online workbooks for development of management level of employees

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	32	32.0	32.0	32.0
	Disagree	31	31.0	31.0	63.0
	Neither Agree not Disagree	17	17.0	17.0	80.0
	Agree	17	17.0	17.0	97.0
	Strongly Agree	3	3.0	3.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

32 participants strongly disagreed that paper version of team leaders' workbooks were not more effective than the online workbooks for development of the midlevel management employees. 31 participants also disagreed with this statement. On the other hand, 17 participants remained neutral and 17 other agreed with the statement; while only three participants strongly agreed with the statement.

Online trainings are more effective to develop the career development of management employees

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	5	5.0	5.0	5.0
	Disagree	9	9.0	9.0	14.0
	Neither Agree not Disagree	12	12.0	12.0	26.0

Agree	40	40.0	40.0	66.0
Strongly Agree	34	34.0	34.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Only 5% of the participants strongly disagreed with the statement that online training is more effective way of developing careers of the mid-level management employees. Similarly, nine participants also showed their disagreement with the statement. 12 were neutral while 40 agreed and 34 strongly agreed with the statement.

Classroom seminars are effective than webinars

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	30	30.0	30.0	30.0
	Disagree	29	29.0	29.0	59.0
	Neither Agree not Disagree	27	27.0	27.0	86.0
	Agree	8	8.0	8.0	94.0
	Strongly Agree	6	6.0	6.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

30 participants strongly disagreed with the statement that classrooms are more effective than webinars and 29% participants also disagreed with the statement. 27 participants remained neutral but only eight agreed and six strongly agreed with the statement.

Impact of technology for training and development is more faster for career progression

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	8	8.0	8.0	8.0
	Disagree	5	5.0	5.0	13.0
	Neither Agree not Disagree	6	6.0	6.0	19.0
	Agree	45	45.0	45.0	64.0
	Strongly Agree	36	36.0	36.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

36% participants strongly agreed that the impact of technology for training and development is faster and more effective for career progression and 45% agreed with the statement. Six participants were neutral, while five disagreed and eight strongly disagreed.

All the qualitative and quantitative data were analyzed through gathered secondary resources, questioners, and interviews. Through analyzing all the data, researcher has proved that how training and development programs and new technology are important to midlevel management to work efficiently in the hospital industry.

The next chapter is Discussion. This chapter allows researcher to think about findings in different outlook. Because after being analyzed all the data, the researcher is able to introduce the research as a new finding of relevant topic. As well as the researcher can express new and original ideas through the discussion.

05. CHAPTER FIVE: DISCUSSION

Training is one of the most important things which is having an overall impact on the job of the employees. It affects the individuals in different ways and makes it a very important part of the job profile for middle-level management employees. The results of the present study show that training is an essential and important part of the job profile. In support of this Heyden, et al., (2018), had also mentioned in their study regarding the training of the employee working in the middle level of the organisation. The study had mentioned about the several roles and responsibilities which are being performed by the middle-level executives and which is crucial for the organisation. The results of the study had mentioned that on the basis of the roles played by the middlelevel executives, they are required to provide effective training programs so that they can develop their skills and knowledge.

Also, the study of Spencer, & McLaren, (2017), had discussed that for developing better communication and interpersonal skills of the middle-level employees, better training is required. The study also mentioned that it is essential that the middle-level management employees should be trained. On the basis of the results of the present study and the results of the previous studies mentioned in the literature review, it can be said that effective training plays an important role on the job profile of the employees and especially for the middle-level management employees. The organisations need to focus on providing the best training to the middle-level management employees by focusing on better and technologically advanced training tools and techniques.

Technology is playing an important role in all the diverse business sectors, and the firm needs to understand how technologies can help them in working more effectively and efficiently. The results of the present study mention that technology is playing a prominent role in the training of the employees. Better technologies are making it easier for the employees and for the companies themselves. In support of the results of this study, Alves, et al., (2017) had also mentioned in their study regarding the relationship between technology and training. If the organisations start using latest technologies for training the employees, then it will become easier for the employees to fit properly into their job roles. Middle-level employees should be trained by using better technologies so that they can be trained in the least possible time. Several studies had revealed that as compared to the traditional methods of training if the organisations have used technologies and the latest training tools for training the employees that it had provided them with several benefits.

Also, the study of Cazamecka and Dardczi, (2017), showed that technologies such as e-learning are more effective in training the employees. It can be said that if the organisations are developing training programs for middle-level employees, then they should use technologies such as e-learning and online training programs. Using technologies for training can save a lot of time and unnecessary money. Along with these technologies can help the employees in getting training in a more convenient manner. Moreover, it can be said that using technologies for training the employees can help the companies in training them effectively as technology has a crucial role to play in training.

Organisations operating in diverse industries are making use of better technologies which is providing them several benefits and helping them in maintaining a better position in their respective industries. The cited company Mitchell and Butler is also using better technologies in the organisation for training the employees. Wide range of technologies is being used by the Mitchell and Butler for training the employees as the company is using the online learning and e-learning approaches for training the employees in an effective manner. The company had mentioned on their website regarding the technological advanced tools and techniques which are being used by them from training the employees. The cited company had also mentioned that better technologies are helping them a lot in training the employees and increasing employee satisfaction and employee engagement with the company. Mitchell and Butler had developed their own online system for training the employees, which are named as Mable.

This system is capable of providing training to the employee in a different manner which is a most convenient and effective manner. Mable provides the training to the employees on the basis of their capacity and on the basis of their needs. The individuals can easily log in to the Mable and can start the training on the basis of their need of the requirement and whenever and wherever they think that they need to develop there any of the skills or enhance their knowledge regarding any of the concept of the hospitality industry. The results of the present research study reveal that Mitchell and Butler are using highly advanced technologies for providing training to the employees. Use of better technologies had helped them a lot in training the employees in an effective manner and also the company is looking forward to investing in their research and development department so that they can use the best technologically advanced training tools for providing training to the employees.

Using technologies in training is aimed at increasing the efficacy of the training programs so that the organisations can train the employees in a well organised and in an effective manner. The results of the study suggest that there is a positive relationship between the use of technologies in the training and efficacy of the training programs. The study of Kumpikaite and Ciarniene, (2008) support the results of the present study as this also mentions that if the technologies are being used for providing training to the employees, it can help the organisations in developing the skills and knowledge of the employees in an effective manner which is having a positive impact on the overall efficacy of the training programs.

Also, Maxwell, (2012) supports this that if the technologies are being used in the training of the employees, then it can provide several benefits to both the trainees and trainers as well. Several other studies had also suggested the relationship among the use of technologies in the training programs and providing better outcomes of the training programs. It can be said that if the organisations focus on providing effective training to the employee, then they should use best technologies and technologically advanced tools such as e-learning, online learning, web-based learning, and many more for increasing the effectiveness and efficacy of the training programs.

Employees are one of the most important resources for the organisation, and in the context of the hospitality industry, the employees and their performance become more important. The results of the study reveal that the training of the employees and their performance is having an impact on the overall organisational performance. The study of Breiter and Woods (1997) also supports that the training is having a positive impact on the overall performance of the organisation. The study also mentions that if the employees are not trained effectively, then it will have a negative impact on employee retention and leads to lowers the performance of the organisation. Bakoti (2013) had also mentioned in their study that training is having a positive impact on organisational performance. The study had discussed that better training programs are having a positive impact on the job satisfaction of the employees and if the employees of the organisation are satisfied with their jobs, they will deliver better work to the company which is having a positive impact on the organisational performance. It can be said that the organisations need to focus on making their training programs effectively so that they can improve the performance of all the employees working in the organisation which is having a positive impact on the organisational performance of the company.

Mitchell and Butler are understanding this concept in an effective manner that their employees are playing a crucial role in the performance. The Mitchell and Butler are focusing on the development of the skills and knowledge of their employees as they understand that they are the one who is responsible for providing high-quality service to the customer who is having a positive impact on the customer experience. The cited company is especially focusing on providing training to the employees in an effective manner, and due to this, the company is investing high capital and resources in training the employees in an effective manner. With this mindset and goal of providing effective learning to the employees, the company had a partnership with the companies such as Kineo and Totara, which had led to the development of the learning system MABLE. This is helping the company in training in an effective manner and developing the skills and knowledge of the employees. Along with this, the company is also using other technologically advanced tools and technique for making the training programs more effective and convenient for the employees.

The way in which the Mitchell and Butler are investing time, cost, and resources for improving the skills and knowledge of the employee reflect that the company is much concerned regarding the training of the employee. The Mitchell and Butler are working effectively on the training of the employees as the company aims at providing an excellent experience to their customers and want to deliver high-quality service to the customers. In the present study, the research had mentioned that the method which is being used by Mitchell and Butler is appropriate and is satisfying the needs of the employees. Also, the description of the training program mentioned by the Mitchell and Butler shows that they have designed the MABLE with this mindset and aim so that the employees can assess the training programs as per their needs and requirements. Along with this, it is more convenient for the employees to use the training tool on the basis of their preferences and the best time which suits them well. Hence, it can be said that the training content at Mitchells and Butlers is appropriate for employee needs. This is helping the company a lot in proving the best training to the employees and developing their skills and knowledge in an effective and convenient manner.

The way in which Mitchell and Butler are using the technologies for training of the employee's other companies should also shift towards using modern technological training tools rather than the traditional methods of training. The result of the present study mentions that modern methods of training are more effective as compared to the traditional methods of training. In support of the results, Dillon, 2014, had also mentioned in their study that the way in which the training had shifted from traditional

to the digital classes had increased the training outcomes in an effective manner. Also, the study of Cazamecka and Dardczy, (2017) supports the results that with the ongoing technological advancement in the world, it has become important for the organisations to use modern training techniques.

The modern methods of training are more convenient to use and can provide learning as per the needs and requirements of the learners, which was not possible earlier in the traditional training methods. It can be said that as the world is changing and becoming technologically advanced day by day, it is essential for the organisations to use technologies for providing training to the employees as the traditional methods can no longer provide effective training to the employees of the modern era.

Online training programs which make use of the images, videos and e-learning approach is significantly changing the training programs and the way in which training is being provided to the employees. For enhancing the performance of the employees working in the firm, it is essential to train them in an effective manner. If the training which is providing to the employees is successfully developing the skills and knowledge of the employees, then it will have a positive impact on the overall performance of the employees. The results of the present study had also shown a positive relationship between the training of the employees and their performance. Grimpe, et al., (2019) also supports that effective training programs help the employees a lot in developing their skillset and knowledge so that they can fit appropriately in the job profile and can deliver high-quality work and better performance in the organisation. Bratton and Gold, (2003) had also mentioned in their study that training can help the employees in the number of ways in developing their skills which can help them in delivering high-quality work in the organisation.

On concluding the results of the present research study, it reveals that the use of technology enables faster career progression. With the growing globalisation, modernisation and technological advancement using the technologies for training the employees had become important as the world will become digitally advanced day by day and for training the employees to work properly in the changing world, it is essential to make use of the technologies. Along with this, the results of the research study also mentions that the technology improves the quality and effectiveness of the training programs. Several studies are also supporting these results. Pramjeeth, et al., (2017) had also discussed that the increasing technological advancement in the educational technologies had a significant impact on the training and development of the organisation.

The results also showed that the organisations operating in the hospitality industry of the UK are widely the technologies for training the employees in an effective manner which is helping the firm in developing highly trained and effective workforce. Similar results have also been shown from the case study analysis of the Mitchells and Butlers. In support of this, several studies had shown how the technologies are being used in the training of the employees. Kizildag and Kim (2010) had mentioned about the changing technologies in the training system of the hospitality industry. Also, the study of Batla, (2008) had mentioned in their study about the latest technologies which are being used for providing training to the employees of the hospitality sector.

The study had mentioned that due to technological advancement, the major part of the hospitality businesses is shifting towards online training methods from the traditional methods. It had become important for the organisations to adopt the changing training mediums so that the employees can be trained in an effective manner. From the results of the research study and the similar results which are also found in other studies, it can be said that the hospitality industry of UK the organisations needs to focus on the technologies for providing training to the employees. The results of the present research study directly show a relation among the latest technologies which are being used for training the employees and its effectiveness on the training of the employees. It can be said that better technologies are being used for training the employees, then effective results can be obtained especially in the hospitality sector. At end of the discussion the researcher clearly shows that how objectives, research questions and findings are important to the thesis. Because these important aspects guide researcher from start to the end. The research questions are very essential aspect in the thesis and guide to find out what researcher exactly needs. As same as aim, objectives and research questions, findings also one of the main important aspects in the thesis which can only confirm or reject the hypothesis. The researcher was able to get the successful research outcome through clear aim, objectives, research questions and its findings. The next chapter is conclusion of the research. The researcher has explained about outcome of the whole research.

06. CHAPTER SIX:
CONCLUSION

Introduction:

Hospitality is that sort of industry that by and large incorporates lodgings, club, carnivals, occasions, travels, amusement, cafés, clubs and bistros alongside other traveller related administrations. This industry isn't only fundamental for organizations yet additionally significant for clients, workers, and economies also. Hospitality industry is for the most part separated into four fragments that are food and drinks, travel and the tourism industry, lodging and entertainment. A cordiality unit like a bistro, hold up, or an event congregation comprises of divisions, for example, office shielding and straight system. Workers, maids, doormen, kitchen staff, barkeeps, the executives, promoting, and HR, and a lot more are additionally remembered for this industry. The cordiality business is a multibillion-dollar industry that relies upon the openness of recreation event, dispensable returns, and total purchaser satisfaction.

The food and beverage sector of the hotel generally present food stuffs which are unique in taste. Along with every hotel tries to create food that gives healthy and rich taste to the customers. As hospitality industry is diverse and dynamic for that reason company must create foods which are obtainable by every customer who visit their hotels. Travel and tourism are also part of hospitality industry this part serve services to the customers and help them to move from one place to another. And for moving from one place to another customer needs buses, cabs, ships, trains, planes, and other transport to travel; all these comes under travel industry.

Hospitality industry by and large arrangements into exceptionally intricate and dynamic condition that essentially implies that representatives and laborers of the organization consistently need propelled preparing and advancement meetings. Also, for managing in such waste industry preparing is incredibly basic. The business is getting step by step further developed loaded up with inventive innovation; business who are working their association inside friendliness industry need to create and work

their business with progression. Clients in friendliness industry have very wide extension they have a few other options, so for working business viably and making their organization chief then it needs to give preparing to their representatives.

In UK the organization in cordiality industry centre around giving half preparing to the workers. That implies preparing is fundamental factor in association framework. Preparing and improvement meeting increment and created new aptitudes that give nature of work. Alongside it likewise give inspiration to the laborers which in the end results positive and increment their presentation level just as associations execution as entirety. From the above information plainly, organization do worry for giving preparing to their representatives. So, in this for working adequately and working with smooth consistency organization need to give preparing and improvement meetings and workshops for their representatives. For giving proper preparing organization need satisfactory structure and cost.

With appropriate preparing structure organization can appreciate more advantages. Along appropriate structure likewise not make ruin and weight on representative's head. On the off chance that the organization doesn't make it appropriately workers believe that it is an additional weight that they must perform with their assignments. They truly hate their learning meeting and less concentrate while workshops. That essentially reflect less drew in workers and this will turn decrease in the degree of execution of representatives just as association as entirety. Organization who has viable and connected with workforce that business certainly make progress; then again if organization doesn't viable representatives that organization doesn't accomplish their attractive situation inside the market. Staff training and development is generally beneficial to any industry and any organisation. In this particular study, the researcher focusses on the effectiveness and impact of such training programmes aimed at mid-level management staff in UK hospitality industry. Training and development for mid-level of worker can be powerful for an association as they have very much prepared and created supervisory group to foster their colleagues to accomplish the objectives, further develop the assistance quality and usefulness.

Training and development have pushed ahead to an alternate route in 21st century. With the innovative transformation, utilizing PCs and Internet for learning, trainings and improvement has taken another time. Preparing programs used to be exercise manuals, which representatives needs to take an interest in homeroom talks or workshops to top off the book. Improvement programs has planned studios, bunch

works or exercises. Innovation has played a job in preparing and improvement as online trainings, e – learning's, online courses, and a lot more applications.

The training programs which are being used by the organisations for providing training to the employees depends on the several factors. In the context of hospitality industry several types of traditional training methods are being used for providing training to the employees such as on job training, lectures, cases, role playing, job instructions and many more. But the technological development had shifted the learning towards e-learning and this is being used by the organisations for providing training to the employees. Using technologies for the training helps the hospitality industry to trainee the employees in an effective manner and developing the skills and knowledge of the employees.

Satisfying the employees with their job roles should be the core responsibility of the organisation as it is having an impact on the employee performance. If the company is organising effective training programs for the employee which are providing positive outcomes and are improving the skills of the employees, then it will lead to job satisfaction which will lead to better performance of the employee in the organisation. It is not an easy task for the companies to develop a training program as it requires a lot of resources and it needs to be successful in developing the skills of the employees. The firms need to focus on all the factors which are having an impact on the training and development of the employees in the organisation. Training is specifically important for the new hired employees as it is important for the company to fill the skill gap among the employee's skills and the skills required for the specific job role.

If we discuss training and development of employees in the context of hospitality industry, then it becomes more significant. Hospitality industry is a customer driven industry and the satisfaction level of the customer play a major role in the success of the organisation. Development of skills and knowledge of employee working in hospitality industry is essentials as it is having an impact on the way in which the employee interact with the customers and quality of the service which is being delivered to the customers. Quality of the service delivered to the customer is directly having an impact on the brand value and reputation of the organisation and due to this the organisations providing hospitality service needs to pay more focus on training and development of their employees.

Enormous number of representatives are working in a neighbourliness administration giving associations in the different divisions. In this industry all the

various divisions are significant as they are conveying a different support of the clients. Representatives working in all the various divisions, for example, front office, food and refreshment, housekeeping and others needs to have explicit range of abilities dependent on the office in which they are working and, on the administration, they are conveying to the clients. Associations working in this industry needs to sort out successful preparing programs which can help the representatives in building up their aptitudes.

Cordiality administration giving associations working in UK centres around the preparation and advancement of their representatives. Assorted scope of preparing programs is being directed for the representatives by the associations. On the off chance that the associations simply recruit the representatives without giving them better preparing in regard to their jobs and duties and for the advancement of aptitudes which is significant for conveying better quality work to the association. It is significant for the associations to comprehend the significance of preparing and advancement of representatives and its effect on the efficiency and occupation fulfilment of the workers. Alongside this the organizations needs to comprehend that how preparing is affecting the general execution of the association and its achievement. In the event that better preparing is given to the representatives and they are conveying top notch work to the association and fulfilling the clients with their administrations then it will drove the organization towards progress.

I have acquired a Baccalaureate degree studying Economics. Along these lines, I was keen on advanced education and effectively accomplished my Master's in Business Administration. Further to my advanced education, I decided to seek after my profession in the accommodation business and have acquired significant experience. During my work, I had perceived the "significance of preparing in the cordiality business". Around the world, the United Kingdom neighbourliness industry has lofty acknowledgment.

Preparing and advancement are a significant factor for the association and the organizations needs to concentrate on this point. These preparation programs are huge affecting the organization as it is connected with the efficiency of the association. At the point when the organization structures the preparation programs for the worker then they have to concentrate on the increasing most extreme profit by the preparation programs and these projects ought to effectively build up the abilities and information on the representatives.

For the accommodation business the preparation gave to the representatives is more significant as it is affecting the work which is being conveyed by the workers in the association. It is significant point for the association to have appropriate information with respect to the essentialness of the preparation and advancement of the workers. In this examination study the specialist is concentrating on the investigating that does the advances driving the associations towards building up a viable preparing program for the representatives. This exploration is explicitly concentrating on the friendliness business of UK and the improvement of mid-level neighbourliness staff. Restricted writing is available on this point, so it is essential to concentrate on this examination subject for giving better comprehension to the associations with respect to utilizing advances in the preparation and improvement programs.

In accommodation industry, the utilization of innovation for giving preparing programs has not been assessed. Thus, there is a need to gauge the quantitative and subjective adequacy of innovation to give such preparing programs effectively and measure how it helps the improvement of staff to their fullest potential. In this exploration, specialist is assessing the ebb and flow preparing programs through the meetings and auxiliary information, just as scientist is hoping to accumulate the data about what are the current preparing programs. This exploration will initially build up a writing audit on the related territories, cordiality industry, innovation, preparing projects to create neighbourliness staff abilities. In this manner, scientist gives models to evaluate the viability of such preparing programs.

To get an extensive view quantitative and subjective information is gotten and it further sets up the attributes of examination addresses that are significant around there of study. The reason for this investigation is to quantify and distinguish the connection between factors to see how the mid-level administration staff in UK friendliness industry see the innovation perspectives as significant and valuable for their advancement programs.

Through trainings individuals can change their mentalities and their conduct. Armstrong has plainly clarified about preparing is the adjusting of individual conduct through learning and encounters. McClelland says preparing is an action to change individuals' conduct. Through preparing individuals can improve their aptitudes and information as per the activity job and regarding works. As per Edwin B Filippo preparing is a demonstration to expand the information and abilities on indicated work. Preparing and worker's exhibitions have direct relationship. Through training,

guidelines, advancement, and encounters are official changes representative's conduct.

Preparing demonstrated the way toward changing and improving representative's perspectives and conduct to perform well on their activity job and work. It assists with assuming control over the new gifts of them and update the abilities and aptitudes which workers had. Chris clarifies about the preparation and improvement expect to specialized turn of events, human and administrative turn of events and selfawareness for individual and hierarchical development. Motivation behind preparing and advancement is to build up the aptitudes and procuring the information through trainings.

Rosner contends that preparation isn't the answer for execution in certain circumstances, as preparing experts might suspect preparing could be a misuse of cash and assets and a few times it could be a wise speculation. Some preparation comes up short, as it needs more targets to centre and give guidance to the representatives. As Mullins said absence of the executives develop and support are significant motivations to come up short on trainings. Preparing is seen as one of the most noteworthy human assets rehearses in any industry.

Armstrong expresses that the principal point of preparing is to assist associations with accomplishing their motivation by adding to their secret weapons for example the individuals they utilize. Putting resources into preparing implies that representatives will have the option to perform better and enable themselves to utilize their characteristic capacities. Preparing and advancement are strategies retransferring to representatives' significant abilities, information, and capability to improve workers' presentation in current positions and future task.

It is not easy to refute for relationship to enough train their delegates for capable and ideal execution toward the affirmation of their set destinations and focuses on Employees' arrangement and headway is a vital confirmation to empower learning of the movement related data, aptitudes, limit and lead that are basic for useful execution fit for redesigning progressive sufficiency Training is basic to further developing experts capacity, thinking staff and ability which will work on legitimate execution and furthermore help in expanding genuine edge Training and improvement constructs laborers' efficiencies, advancement, creation, capacity to recognize new advances and strategies It is crucial for observe that affiliations should have the alternative to recognize the prerequisites for planning and headway and select techniques proper for these necessities, plan how to realize them and starting there survey result. The

objective of preparing the representatives is to empower them to dominate the information, abilities and practices featured in the preparation programs and to empower them to apply them to their everyday work practice. '...There can be no single assertion of what the job of a preparation expert ought to be. It is adapted by a mix of the target necessities in his firm, emotional and individual components brought out by the perspectives of chiefs, and his own origination of his job and individual abilities – he and the work help to make one another.' T. Leduchowicz There are fluctuated course reading meanings of preparing, yet the one by Edwin B Flippo is for the most part very much acknowledged. As indicated by Flippo, "Preparing is the demonstration of expanding the information and abilities of a worker for making a specific showing".

There have been different hypotheses propounded to clarify the significance of preparing needs in any foundation of association. In social learning hypothesis, workers procure new abilities and information by noticing different individuals from staff whom they believe in and accept to be trustworthy and more educated.

Globalization, need of administration, increased worth put on elusive resources and human resources, Focus on connection to business technique, Customer's administrations and quality accentuation, New innovation, High exhibitions model at work framework, Economic changes, Attracting and holding ability are the requirements of coming down programs. Examining the preparation needs is a key to redesign and reshape the advancement programs in all businesses and requirements of preparing can recognize the hole between what are the abilities representative ought to need to finish on their task job and what are the abilities worker really needs to do their task job. As indicated by Breiter and woods needs of preparing is an appraisal of the ID of hole between ideal exhibitions and real exhibitions.

If the important of training is discussed in the context of the hospitality industry, then it became more significant topic of concern for the organisations. With the increasing globalisation across the world, it has become essential for the organisations to provide training to the employees so that they can develop the skills and knowledge which is important to fit appropriately in the job role and description. In the context of the hospitality industry the employee belonging to diverse socio-economic backgrounds are working together in the industry and along with this they are offering services to the customers belonging to diverse socio-economic backgrounds. When the employees are working in such an industry then it is training become more important for them so that they can deliver better- and high-quality service to the peoples belonging to different parts of the world. Globalisation had led the training and development to be more

important for the hospitality sector and also needs to be effective so that the employees can be trained in a better way.

Training programs are also having an impact on the employee retention and job satisfaction of the employees. The organisations need to understand that if they are providing better training to the employees then it will help the employees in working effectively and delivering better service in the organisation. If the employees are delivering better performance in the organisation, then it is having positive impact on the job satisfaction of the employees and helps the company in employee retention. If the talented employees are leaving the company, then it became difficult for the organisation to regularly hire new employees and it also has a negative impact on the organisational performance.

Technological development had also increased the demand of effective training in the hospitality industry. Latest technologies are being used by the hospitality service providing organisation due to which it has become important for the organisations to trainee the employees so that they can also use the technologies for delivering better service to the customers. For using latest technologies such as big data and information from the social media platforms it is essential to have proper knowledge so that the employees can develop their skillset for improving the quality of the service which is provided to the customers.

With the changing world, training is becoming more important day by day. All the employees already working in the organisation and the new hired employees both needs to develop the skills effectively and continuously focus on developing the skills and should have a learning attitude towards new concepts. The organisation should organise the training programs for all the employees of the organisation in a particular time period which can help them in better developing and also promote improvement in the overall performance and productivity of the organisation. It can be said that it is essential for the organisations to understand the importance of training and development.

It may be possible, with certain categories of training that the performance of employees regarding fixed operational tasks can be measured prior to and then post training through different approaches. Although it is possible to measure improvements in organizational performance resulting from training programs, there are definite limitations to the opportunity to conduct these kinds of studies. Success of the task would be measured by the accurate recording of any definite improvements in the organisation after employee training. Using an example, there should be seen an

increase in profit post training program, and it should be evident that training is at the core of improvements rather than any other factor. It could be argued that a training program should not be given too much credence when it cannot be properly assessed as to direct impact on organisational performance. Therefore, it is essential that acceptable criteria of measuring the effectiveness of training in departments beside operations must be established.

The actual organization and management of training should be studied to fully understand training effectiveness. There are two major elements of measuring training effectiveness, the first being “output benefit” which is the traditional approach. Through this method the effectiveness of training is measured in improvements in individual performance. The second is the training process effectiveness, which is used to assess improvements to an organisation irrespective of the individuals on training courses. Studies may find that despite intensive or specialised training programs an organisation finds very little improvement. Whereas competitors may be found that gain enormous success with similar training programs. This is due to the training process; effectiveness of training varies with individuals and groups being trained; perhaps management has little control on who is being trained, whereas it could be honed to better suited trainees. Thus, the difference between two extreme outcomes previously described lies in training management, not only in the training department but in the organization generally.

Response assessment implies sensation of the training, and it is the manner by which individuals respond in the wake of training programs and their encounters. Learning assessment is the estimation of the information before the preparation and programs and after the preparation programs. Conduct assessment is fundamentally did the students utilize their insight through trainings in a powerful manner at work? Result assessment is the impact on the associations after the further developed abilities and information through the training.

Training is characterized as a deliberate course of analysing the value, worth, or which means of an action or an interaction. Nobody strategy is fit to each assessment subsequently a few strategies for estimation have been created. While there are a few models created for estimating HRD and preparing viability, the most acknowledged model is that created by Kirkpatrick. The model states that there are four spaces of a preparation program that require estimating for adequacy: that is enthusiastic response, accomplishment of destinations, social changes, and hierarchical effect. Moreover,

creators have recognized a four-level course of preparing assessment: These being response, learning, conduct and results.

Due to globalization, there are many customers who are travel oriented travel and explore around the world and increasing the number of travellers and visitors ultimately increase the revenue of hospitality business. It can be said that globalization has positive influence on hospitality industry. Globalization is boom for the hospitality business it is because due to it companies get better technology, productive employees and rich traders and stakeholder as well.

Increasing the number of visitors and attracting them hospitality business have to create more luxurious and tourist-friendly destination. And this could be possible after providing effective training to the employees. As globalization deals in global context so herein companies have to train their employees accordingly. Cultural differences around the world become hurdle and challenge for hospitality industry. Due to the globalization business access foreign culture as well as new technology that eventually assists employees to serve quality services and enhance the level of customer satisfaction.

For hospitality business it is most significant that their potential customers will get satisfied by their services so that they can visit hotel again. And for serving quality services employees' training is one of the essential factors in increasing the productivity and growth of the companies. Globalization is leading to raise international standardization of training challenges and systems. Training has strong relationship with globalization. As many corporations reach crossways nation boundaries and globalization of the workplace turn out to be the fresh standard, industries have to frequently settle into transforms.

Experts of every company must study to communicate in a different way. Company procedures are repeatedly adjusted to fit in with the increasing number of diverse background and ethnic group that associations work with. Businesses that are developing with this change ultimately gain a cutthroat benefit in excess of those who do not change their working pattern as per the globalization. For increasing productivity companies have to provide quality training to their employees.

In hospitality industry adequate training of employees is essential feature, by providing training to workers as per the requirements of globalization that a hotel will become more productive and gaining competitive advantages. Cultural sensitivity, teamwork, managing intelligence, tech savvy individuals, change management and

adopting customer behaviour are the core areas where hospitality industry needs to focus on for dealing with the challenges of globalization.

Innovative leadership is that kind of technique which contributes and influencing employees to produced innovative and creative ideas, services, and products. Innovative thinking is one of the crucial aspects in addition to the traditional business thinking. It eventually allows employees to bring new and fresh opinions that help company to solve challenges. Along with it also increase the pace of working of organization. The importance of leadership quality of manager in hospitality industry leads teamwork and eventually provides productivity to the business. Moreover, teamwork can be increased by rewarding for accomplishment and this could be done by a leader or executor of the team. Along with by respecting employees also increase the team efforts and results into effective work done by workers.

Hospitality industry has been including extremely wide scope of vocation alternative. An individual can work in numerous regions inside the neighbourliness business. One thing is generally normal in all the business that they require a compelling initiative with the goal that they can oversee assorted variety on working environment. Overseeing decent variety is absolutely relying on the administration arrangement of the organization. The administration of the organization needs to set model for the laborers. For overseeing decent variety inside the friendliness business organization must be consistently aware. It is responsibility of the administration of the organization to show their laborers how they need them to carry on and treat each other.

The executives can accomplish this by being reasonable, reliable, and open with their work power. Considering the way that purchaser administration is a key period of the friendliness business, representatives of the organization will undoubtedly contrast and have different traditions of managing the clients and inconveniences that happen. At the point when such difficulties occur, the executives need to try the characteristics referenced over and treat everyone consistently. Another method of overseeing decent variety inside the work environment is the executives needs to make profession improvement program for their cordiality representatives. In cordiality industry there are loads of chances accessible to push ahead and an individual can learn new abilities.

Communicating with all of laborers about their vocation objectives and gain incredible strides to help them achieve them, for example, helping them round out an accommodation for a delivery position in another inn or bistro enact by their organization. By rehearsing the board can successfully deal with their various workforce alongside each work will get more occupied with their occupations. Assorted

variety inside work environment is critical it in the long run encourages organization to expand their profitability, correspondence level, inventiveness, and advancement. Alongside this decent variety in the work environment licenses business to delivered and plan more innovative and propelled administrations to their visitors and clients. In this, overseeing assorted variety is one of the significant parts and the administration of the organization must give preparing to the senior's agents who by and large oversee groups.

The organizations who give preparing to be overseeing decent variety that organization in the end increment the efficiency and capability alongside get more piece of the overall industry inside neighbourliness industry. There are quantities of lodgings that are working universally, and it faces critical effect of globalization. On the off chance that any association that is working in unfamiliar nation and that area is rich with multi-culture society in this, organization has obligation to prepare their representatives according to the inclination and culture of the specific culture. On the off chance that the organization isn't doing its activities as indicated by the public, at that point it may confront difficulties that drag down its level into accommodation advertise. Through powerful overseeing decent variety business may well upgrade their client administrations. Hence, it is basic that each organization need to more turn out to be more participate in giving preparing to their workers so they can improve their centre capacities and ready to serve better administrations to the clients. In accommodation industry it is huge that each specialist must act naturally mindful by their own feelings and mind-sets. Alongside association must give preparing identified with enthusiastic insight. It is on the grounds that each worker must have order on their own feelings while managing clients. Each specialist of the association must learn for overseeing pressure. As plainly friendliness showcase needs to manage unique and differing society individuals, along these lines it is important to give preparing and lead workshops to stretch administration.

Alongside, above abilities one more expertise is significant that is social aptitudes. This incorporates the fitness to oversee relationship, make solid systems, discover shared view and construct interface. It will every now and again help when driving change, being persuasive, structure capability and getting enormous introduction from gatherings. Simultaneously as multifaceted and somewhat dicey, Emotional Intelligence reproduce a focal arrangement of skills inside what it is to be specific. Learning in this part stays central inside the occupation however in the

increasingly more much requesting environmental factors in front it may make the divergence among accomplishment and breakdown.

After embracing imaginative innovation organization need to construct legitimate structure of preparing and lead workshops for those representatives who are satisfactory for performing and managing propelled technology. In addition, give preparing and making each representative well informed is significant for each business that is working in neighbourliness advertise. Advanced arrangements can give purchasers next-level straightforwardness and personalization simultaneously as giving brands included up and coming into client best option. In-room tablets license guests to set up 'Don't Disturb' codes, request room administration, book transport, oversee enlightenment and brilliance, modify TV channels, and lock/open their rooms. Then again, innovation likewise present new set out to hoteliers. In the advanced period, clients much of the time experience like they beforehand recognize the inn before they even reach on the goal. In the advanced region business must give legitimate preparing to their laborers so they adequately manage clients.

It is then huge for the chief in the cordiality business to perceive how the clients make appraisal on the sort of administrations they require and from where to gain the administrations. an assortment of models has been created in the most recent point of reference that push to give subtleties how the clients make a decision, at last procure, and utilize a decent and administration. Intellectual methodology is purchaser conduct model that can be utilized by the organization for managing and understanding the conduct of customers. In the intellectual methodology, the conduct of a customer is predominantly able to one's inside psychological inclination, the capacity to recognize and course little information.

It is profoundly joining to the ground of Cognitive Psychology. As per the method, the outside issues like environmental factors of an individual are determined as inspiration that makes data for inward administration technique. In this, there is requirement for legitimate preparing given to the laborers with the goal that they can comprehend and perceive conduct of clients. As it is referenced above conversation friendliness advertise has includes and manages differing scope of client so the business peer the conduct of clients and offer preparing to the workers appropriately. Culture is for the most part prevailing for relationship in the accommodation business that have drawn out their system to an overall market. Culture and way of life of people additionally influence the purchasing conduct of an individual subsequently it impacts the tasks of association in the friendliness business.

The bleeding edge the executives incorporates exceptionally talented administrators and even utilitarian masters. A first line agent is best arranged when they centre around ascertaining and direct explicit specialists. On the off chance that a first line chief thinks in quite a while of bosses, group pioneers, line administrators, and venture directors he could grow new open door in its current occupation. First line administrators have various aptitudes and capacity. They need two distinct abilities, for example, relational just as specialized aptitudes. Relational ability is required for dealing with the human asset and specialized aptitude is required for executing practical undertakings. As a result, cutting edge directors are regularly critical colleagues with the versatility and adaptability to contribute to different undertakings and activity inside the organization.

At the point when the associations choose to make changes in the association and are searching for giving preparing to the workers, at that point a few difficulties are being looked by the challenges in the preparation results because of a few variables. If the association has an assorted workforce, at that point it got mind boggling for the association to convey compelling preparing to all the representatives as all the workers have a place with various financial foundations and because of which they have alternate points of view towards the things. While giving the preparation, various components can create obstructions for the association and human asset division for giving appropriate and viable preparing to the workers.

The investigation had referenced that component, for example, inspiration, mentality, passionate knowledge, support from the administration and pioneers, preparing style and condition, the receptiveness of mentor and certain activity related elements are having an impact on the preparation results. This investigation recommended that the association should concentrate on all the elements which are affecting the preparation and should concentrate on utilizing these elements successfully so greatest results can be increased through the preparation and execution of the representatives and the whole association can be improved.

For the associations working in the accommodation, it is imperative to give viable preparing to the representatives with the goal that they can convey better execution in the organization and better administrations to the clients. Numerous variables can make a snag for the neighbourliness association in conveying better preparing to the workers. These elements incorporate the various variables identified with the human mentality and conduct, factors identified with the outer condition in

which the organization is working and a few elements of the inward condition of the organization.

During the examination it was discovered that most of the members think preparing is a vital piece of occupation profile for the midlevel the board representatives. In this it very well may be said that the information proposes taking incessant preparing helps representatives in improving their aptitudes and in this way their general execution too, with the goal that they can contribute most extreme towards firms' objectives and targets. During the study it was additionally seen that During the course of this study, it was noted that the mid-level management employees accord high value and importance to training and development. Many researchers found that since these individuals are in such a position that they have to aim for further growth and progression, because if they do not, then they will either be stuck in the same position for a long time, or they will be demoted to lower position(s). This is one of the main reasons for such importance and value to be given on the training function. Therefore, taking regular training and development helps the mid-level managers in progressing their careers and also take advantage of the opportunities presented to them. On this basis, it can be said that mid-level management employees are set to gain considerably by undergoing regular training and development sessions.

During the study it was further noted that training is an important part of professional lives for the mid-level management employees. This shows that training is a crucial aspect for such employees. It can be considered as an opportunity that motivates the mid-level management employees to develop technical and specialised skills, which can be greatly beneficial for their careers and help them to achieve professional growth and development.

Many of the past authors stated that companies are shifting to using latest technologies for training related purposes. As per several studies, technology not only simplifies the training process, but it also helps the mid-level management level employees in speeding up the whole process. In this regard, during the study it was further noted that technology has added whole new dimensions to the training process itself, such as just in time training. It is very similar to that of just-in-time supply strategy. According to it, training is provided to the employees at the right time and in the right manner, so that they can gain the most benefit out of it. Through such form of training, the mid-level management employees can receive the right type of training at the right time and through the right medium, thereby enabling them to improve their skills in a significant manner.

In such type of training, focus is on using digital and online methods for training the employees. During the study, it was further observed that some of the mid-level management employees might think that the company is not training them for the future and is only focusing on improving their skills for firm's current requirements. But using the just-in-time approach for training can help such employees to remain associated with the training and also recall it at a later stage as well.

Several studies further showed that such virtual training methods, just like the just-in-time training approach can align with and fulfil needs and requirements of the trainee or the learner. This means that such training methods can be useful in terms of providing best and effective training to the mid-level management employees. The virtual training consists of different methods and techniques such as e-learning which can be either web-based or self-paced and blended learning which is a combination of different courses and options.

The study also revealed that in current times of the pandemic, using online and digital methods of training can be useful since a large chunk of workforce for companies is working remotely. Therefore, use of e-learning and training methods can provide satisfactory results in terms of training the employees and enhancing their performance and contribution towards firms' goals and objectives.

The hospitality industry utilizes a few techniques for their worker trainings like tests, Seminars, studios, on work trainings, on to one training, shadowing projects, and abilities tests. Those training strategies are the normal in neighbourliness industry have utilized and presently a portion of the organizations in hospitality industry have moved to mechanical training techniques. A few organizations use show as you go idea instead of having an all-around prepared coach in to an organization, which is a modest method to prepare representatives. Elite working practice is another training method in cordiality industry.

During the investigation it was seen that by lessening the executives' obligations or occupation titles, empowering with higher errand independence, carrying out new training programs, empowering data sharing projects and pay dependent on representatives' exhibitions can acquire the high practices accommodation industry. In hospitality industry training has a helpless standing and organizations should discover exchanging projects to upgrade the assistance quality which representatives produce.

The explanation is for the helpless training in hospitality is in house the executive issues. Giving reasonable training projects to chiefs to create at all levels of their work

job including the abilities and information to oversee and prepare representatives and change in association for any business climate.

The significance of training to the cordiality business has been featured. As per a few creators training is imperative on account of the unavoidable changes that happen in associations. To accomplish proceeding with progress effective associations will reconstruct themselves and retrain their workers appropriately, for example to acquire a strategic advantage over their rivals by further developing help quality in their inn and so on the mid-level staff representatives are additionally resolved that those associations that are effective as of now however proceed with unaltered and become careless will be in for a major shock. They contend that preparation is a nonstop cycle and that relationship building abilities should be ceaselessly refreshed to try not to become out of date very much like advancements, which become out-dated in case improvement isn't on going.

Training, in cordiality setting, just means showing individuals how to take care of their responsibilities the troughs might teach and guide a learner toward learning information (like certain realities and techniques), abilities important to do the standard required, (for example, stacking the dish machine), or perspectives, (for example, client arranged disposition). Three sorts of training are required in food and housing activities: work guidance, retraining, and direction. Occupation guidance is only that-guidance in what to do and how to do it in everything about a given occupation in each endeavour. Retraining applies to current representatives. It is important when laborers are not comparing norms, when another strategy or menu or piece of hardware is presented, or when a specialist requests it. It happens at whatever point it is required.

During the research it was additionally noticed that Mitchells and Butlers utilizes the most recent advancements for training its workers at the mid-level. Innovation is assuming a significant part in preparing, advancement, arranging and the executives. Innovation has pushed ahead in beyond a long time from freebee manual figuring out how to sight and sound internet preparing and social learning for innovation stages. training strategies has been changed and extended through technology

As the technological advancement has changed the way in which the individuals learn new things and concepts it had also improvement the learning programs. In the context of the businesses the companies need to teach a lot of new things, concepts, and skills to their employee. Technologies are helping the organisation to make modifications in their training programs so that they can effectively train the employees. Several authors have mentioned in their study regarding the use of technologies in the training. One of

the most important tasks of the management system is to focus on operating effectively with the changing environment and continuously updating the skills and knowledge of the employees so that they can work effectively in the changing environment.

If the organisations implement better technologies in the training, then it can help them in improving the skills and knowledge of the employees effectively. The training professionals and the educationalists are focusing on using the technologies which can improve and facilitates the learning process. Due to the technological advancement, e-learning had become much popular, and it is leading to significant changes in training and leaning programs. E-learning is being widely used in the training and education for improving the quality of the learning and teaching processes. The evolution of the e-learning is having a positive impact on the personal and professional learning of the individuals. Using the technologies for learning and training is providing several opportunities to individuals such as convenience training as per the capability of the learners.

Different types of technologies are being used by the organisation for training the employees. If the company is using the technology for the higher level of then it will focus on job related factors and tries to train the employees so that they can meet the needs of the company. Moreover, for the low level of learning the technologies in the training would focus on facilitating communication among the trainees and the trainers. The organisations are making use of computer-based training, multimedia for training, testing assessment and e-learning for making training effectively. The also mentioned that the organisations should strategically align the company aims and objectives with the effective leadership so that the training and development can be more successful in leading the company towards its goals. The greater part of the organizations are utilizing the eLearning for their training and development programs, as it is compelling and effective to foster the colleagues. As indicated by certain creators' association needs a viable training to accomplish the objectives and rival their rivals. As he discloses no compelling reason to stress to acquaint the e learning with the association when individuals include to the e learning trainings then they will actually want to tackle their work appropriately. Innovation can offer a chance to training and improvement to take care of their work adequately.

Some authors have also mentioned in their study regarding technological advancement in the methods of training. The study had mentioned that technologies are having greater potential to offer several benefits to learning and training programs. With the

technological advancement the online learning and training market had become much popular in the entire world. The author had defined e-learning as the automation of the process of learning and training with the help of information technologies. In the present world majority of the business depends on the e-learning for training the employees and for coordinating all the different activities in the organisation. Also, the development of the computers and the networks is working as a dynamic force in training and learning processes. The study had concluded that use of online training and technologies can be used in many ways in training such as it can be a sole source of learning, a follow up to the traditional training, alternative to the traditional training and can also be a supplement for supplement to the traditional training.

Large number of employees are working in a hospitality service providing organisations in the diverse departments. In this industry all the different departments are important as they are delivering a diverse service to the customers. Employees working in all the diverse departments such as front office, food and beverage, housekeeping and others needs to have specific skillset based on the department in which they are working, and, on the service, they are delivering to the customers. Organisations operating in this industry needs to organised effective training programs which can help the employees in developing their skills. Hospitality service providing organisations operating in UK focuses on the training and development of their employees.

Diverse range of training programs are being conducted for the employees by the organisations. If the organisations just hire the employees without providing them better training regarding their roles and responsibilities and for the development of skills which is important for delivering better quality work to the organisation. It is very important for the organisations to understand the importance of training and development of employees and its impact on the productivity and job satisfaction of the employees. Along with this the companies needs to understand that how training is having an impact on the overall performance of the organisation and its success. If better training is provided to the employees and they are delivering high quality work to the organisation and satisfying the customers with their services, then it will lead the company towards success. It is imperative for the human resources department to develop the staff skills and keep them up to date. Authors have correctly identified the need for human resources department to keep abreast of the changes that are happening globally with different aspects of the business functionalities and the interaction between these functions can alter the entire business process.

07.CHAPTER SEVEN:
RECOMMENDATIONS

The recommendation is most important part of the thesis which shows issues of the research. the researcher has identified some issues in the research and provides few recommendations to overcome those issues.

The training programs which are being used by the organisations for providing training to the employees depends on the several factors. In the context of hospitality industry several types of traditional training methods are being used for providing training to the employees such as on job training, lectures, cases, role playing, job instructions and many more. But the technological development had shifted the learning towards e-learning and this is being used by the organisations for providing training to the employees. Using technologies for the training helps the hospitality industry to trainee the employees in an effective manner and developing the skills and knowledge of the employees.

The organisations are using different technologies for providing training such as videos, computer-based instructions, online training programs, web-based training, and interactive video training and many more. Although it is expensive to use the technologies but once there are being established in the organisation then it provides several benefits as it reduces the cost of organising the training sessions, cutting the cost of transportation, fees of tutor and cost of meals and the cost of other resources as it. Hence, it can be said that using technologies in the training provides several benefits to the organisations so the companies should focus on using better technologies in the training and development programs.

Large number of employees are working in hospitality service providing organisations in the diverse departments. In this industry all the different departments are important as they are delivering a diverse service to the customers. Employees working in all the diverse departments such as front office, food and beverage, housekeeping and others needs to have specific skillset based on the department in which they are working and on the service, they are delivering to the customers. Organisations operating in this industry needs to organised effective training programs which can help the employees in developing their skills.

Hospitality service providing organisations operating in UK focuses on the training and development of their employees. Diverse range of training programs are being conducted for the employees by the organisations. If the organisations just hire the employees without providing them better training regarding their roles and responsibilities and for the development of skills which is important for delivering better quality work to the organisation. It is very important for the organisations to

understand the importance of training and development of employees and its impact on the productivity and job satisfaction of the employees. Along with this the companies needs to understand that how training is having an impact on the overall performance of the organisation and its success. If better training is provided to the employees and they are delivering high quality work to the organisation and satisfying the customers with their services then it will led the company towards success.

I have obtained a Baccalaureate degree majoring in Economics. Subsequently, I was interested in higher education and successfully achieved my Master's in Business Administration. Further to my higher education, I chose to pursue my career in the hospitality industry and have obtained considerable experience. During my work, I had recognised the "importance of training in the hospitality industry". Worldwide, the United Kingdom hospitality industry has prestigious recognition.

Further, at my work I realised that the organisation benefits greatly by providing adequate training to improve the skills of the staff members. It further improves their productivity and job satisfaction as well. This is in alignment with the findings by Bell et al. (2003). Despite the significance of training the staff adequately, I found that my organisation and a number of other organisations where my friends worked were forced to hire staff without any training as filling the staff vacancy was better than having none to perform certain duties that are required by the challenging environment in the hospitality industry. This seems to be the common challenge faced by organisations across the globe in this industry. It is very dynamic and fast paced and the businesses have to make use to the available talent and train them where they lack certain skills. With the ongoing changes in the world, technology is playing a major role in every department and in all the industries. In the context of the training which is being provided to the employees the companies need to focus on using better technologies which can help them in providing effective training to the employees. Human resource department of the company should focus on organising proper and effective training and development programs for the employees. Technological advancement is providing better opportunities for the organisations to make better use of the technologies for providing effective training to the employees. Incorporating the technologies in the learning environment will provide several benefits to the organisation and it will prepare the workforce for the upcoming technological advancements as well.

The organisations operating in the hospitality industry are using the existing methods for providing the training to the employees, but they should look forwards towards using latest technologies which can help them in providing the training in an

easy and effective manner. The development of the technologies in the hospitality industry had made it possible for the company to enhance the effectiveness of the training and learning among the employees. Using the latest technologies for providing the training is not easy for the organisations as it is quite costly. On the other hand, introducing the technologies such as e-learning for training the employees provide several benefits due to which it is beneficial for the companies to use technologies for providing training to the employees.

Training and development are an important factor for the organisation and the firms needs to focus on this topic. These training programs are having a huge impact on the company as it is related with the productivity of the organisation. When the company designs the training programs for the employee then they need to focus on the gaining maximum benefit from the training programs and these programs should successfully develop the skills and knowledge of the employees.

For the hospitality industry the training provided to the employees is more important as it is having an impact on the work which is being delivered by the employees in the organisation. It is important topic for the organisation to have proper knowledge regarding the significance of the training and development of the employees. In this research study the researcher is focusing on the analysing that does the technologies leading the organisations towards developing an effective training program for the employees. This research is specifically focusing on the hospitality industry of UK and the development of mid-level hospitality staff. Limited literature is present on this topic, so it is important to focus on this research topic for providing better understanding to the organisations regarding using technologies in the training and development programs.

A sensible and result arranged information assortment system is by using primary and secondary information assortment methodologies and at last utilizing current exploration approving strategies the specific connection between utilization of technology and the outcomes acquired by mid-level cordiality staff because of such training programs. The exploration will be pronounced in a numerical portrayal where the administration and related partners will acquire an extensive perspective on the examination results got from this investigation. The resultant results will carry the proposals to improve the viable training programs through utilization of technology.

The executive's advancement is that load of exercises and program when perceived and controlled have generous impact in changing the limit of the person to play out his task better and in going so all liable to expand his potential for future tasks.

Consequently, the executive's improvement is a blend of different training program, however some sort of training is vital, it is the general advancement of the capability of administrative individual in the light of the current necessity just as the future prerequisite.

Advancement a movement intended to work on the presentation of existing supervisors and to accommodate an arranged development of directors to meet future hierarchical necessities is the executives improvement. Training is a learning interaction that includes the procurement of information, honing of abilities, ideas, rules, or changing of perspectives and practices to upgrade the exhibition of representatives. Training is a constant cycle by which worker really gets the information and become more acquainted with how the individual can perform well in the association.

On Job training is really done when a representative gets the preparation while playing out their appointed errand. Off Job training is a sort of training when representatives of the association are being called for instructional course to get familiar with an assignment. There are a wide range of training and development techniques. Hands on training, casual training, classroom preparing, inner instructional classes, outer instructional classes, hands on training, life-instructing, coaching, preparing tasks and errands, abilities preparing, item preparing, specialized preparing, social advancement preparing, pretending and pretend games and activities, attitudinal preparing and improvement, certify training and development, distance learning - all piece of the training menu, accessible to utilize and apply as per individual training needs and hierarchical training needs.

Training is additionally accessible a long way past and outside the study hall. All the more significantly, training – or learning, to take a gander at it from the learner's view - is anything offering learning and formative experience. Training and development improvement incorporates viewpoints, for example, morals and ethical quality; mentality and conduct; administration and assurance, just as abilities and information. Improvement isn't confined to training - it's anything that assists an individual with developing, in capacity, abilities, certainty, resistance, responsibility, drive, between close to home abilities, understanding, poise, inspiration and that's only the tip of the iceberg.

08.CHAPTER EIGHT:
CONCLUSION

Training and development are key in each association. Very much prepared colleagues are certain and powerful on their work job. As indicated by Boella, having a fruitful training interaction and technique in each association, will persuade their workers to create and work on their abilities and award a while later. (Boella 1996). In the event that the organization doesn't have the foggiest idea how to assess their training and what is the most ideal approach to assess their training, associations can't discover the shortcomings and qualities of their training projects to assist them with improving.

This was an incredible open door and a test for analysts to assess the adequacy of training and improvement programs. In this exploration specialist's point is to assess the adequacy of the current training programs and to prescribe how innovation can be joined to improve the training programs for mid degree of workers in the hospitality business in the UK.

For accomplishing the best outcomes, the top Management, and administrator's viewpoints, through meetings and surveys individually, will be inspected and broke down. Specialists will lead the semi-structured interviews with top management in human asset office, learning and improvement office dependent on Mitchells and Butlers Company as a scientist contextual analysis.

Researchers will lead the meetings with top administration as an initial step of an information assortment technique. This will assist with social occasion optional information in regards to what are the accessible training programs for mid-level representatives, how the technology use in training and development programs, what are the progressions of training methods they have used to make more successful, And likewise to accumulate the information for most recent 3 years level of fruition of the preparation and improvement programs.

Researchers will utilize the assessor poll to accumulate quantitative information from the mid-level of workers. Scientists will arbitrarily choose 100 – 150 mid-level level staff to fill the study. The goal of this review is to assess the viability of their training and development programs.

Training programs has become more creative using technology. Scientist is anticipating prescribe the how technology can join to improve the training programs for mid degree of representatives in hospitality industry. Scientist is wanting to bring another

compelling preparing innovation or foster the current mechanical device to be more viable for mid-level representatives on organization preparing and advancement programs.

8.1 Expected Research Outcomes

The expected results of the research are related to advancement of theoretical understanding of the training and development programmes in hospitality industry. Researcher is expecting to understand and evaluate what are the available training and development programmes in hospitality industry, what are the current training platforms and tools available in Mitchells and butlers. Understanding the training development process in Mitchells and butlers with better knowledge of theoretical framework at the end one of the expected outcomes can be Training and development will be positively associate with Mitchells and Butler.

In this research researcher is expecting theoretical understanding of technology and impact of technology on training and development in hospitality industry. Researcher is expecting to see on outcome of the data analysis, how many management employees have completed their training programmes and how long it took them to complete their development journey. Researcher is looking forward to understanding what the role of technology is playing on their training programmes and how does that have affected to the completion of training journey. One of the other outcomes will be Technology always could improve and contribute training programmes for mid-level of employees in Mitchells and butlers.

Gathering information and details about the history of training and development programmes in Mitchells and Butlers, within 10-year time frame researchers can understand the transformation of the training and development programmes in Mitchells and Butlers. One expected outcome will be Mitchells and Butlers always develop training and development programmes mid-level of employees.

Conclusion can be identified as a summary of the whole thesis. the researcher has clearly explained for readers to understand that how and what did in the research. The researcher's aim was to develop the idea of how training and development important to hospitality industry. Furthermore, the thesis was not hesitated to explain how training and development have moved forward in different way in 21st century. As well as

technology development also increased of the effective training in the hospitality industry. The researcher has taken a company in the United Kingdom as a good example. The researcher has contributed to get a successful outcome by adding variety of ways to its work. The data were analysed through both primary and secondary research. The secondary data was collected by websites, publications, journals, books and many more sources. The primary data were collected through mail questioners and phone interviews. All the collected data were helped to create the successful outcome and whole process of thesis allows readers to evaluate the validity and reliability of the research.

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APPENDICES

Questionnaire

Effectiveness of the training and development programmes for mid level of the employee in UK hospitality industry. Case study Mitchells and Butlers.

Dear Sir/ Madam.

As a part of my doctorate study I am conducting a research to find out effectiveness of training and development programmes for mid-level of employees in hospitality industry. I have chosen Mitchells and butlers as a case study as it is one of the biggest chains in hospitality industry. My purpose is to collect primary information about the training and development programmes and impact of technology for training and development for mid-level of employees in hospitality industry.

If you would prefer not to take part in this research, then I really thank you for your time. If you are happy to participate, please complete this questionnaire and all information given will be treated confidentially.

1. Age where you belong 18-21 21-30 31-40
 Above 40

2. Please select your Gender Female Male Other

3. Please Indicate the nationality where you from.
.....

4. What is your current job role? General Manager
 Deputy Manager Assistant Manager
 Kitchen Manger

5. Length of the service with Mitchells and Butlers
Less than one year 1-5 years 5-10 years
 More than 10 years

6. Which position you have joined to the company?
- General manager
 - Assistant/ kitchen Manager
 - Back of house team member
 - Front of House team member
7. Form of training programmes and tools received on your development
- Work book
 - Online workbook
 - Seminars and work shops
 - Webinars
 - All of them
8. Most effective training programmes on your development
- Online training
 - webinars
 - Workbook
 - seminars
9. Impact on online trainings on you development
- Excellent
 - Better than normal training
 - Very good
10. Impact on Work book and seminars on your development
- Excellent
 - Better than online training
 - Very good
11. Relevant on training content to achieving personal goals and self development
- Totally relevant
 - Not relevant
 - Cannot tell

1. Please indicate the extent to which you agree with the following statements.

Factors	Strongly agree (5)	Agree (4)	Neither agree nor disagree (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)
Team leader workbooks, (paper version) are more effective than online workbooks for development of management level of employees.					
Online trainings are more effective to develop the career development of management employees					
Class room seminars are effective than webinars					
Impact of technology for training and development is more faster for career progression.					

2. Suggestions between old training programmes and current training programmes and tools.

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Bar Chart

Online trainings are more effective to develop the career development of management employees

Class room seminars are effective than webinars